

Project Title	ENSuring Secure and Safe CMD Design with Zero TRUST Principles		
Project Acronym	ENTRUST		
Grant Agreement No	101095634	Type of Action	Research and Innovation Action
Call / Topic	HORIZON-HLTH-2022-IND-13-01		

D4.2 – Runtime Assurance & Certification Framework – First Release

Work Package	WP4: Runtime Attestation Mechanisms and Continuous Certification for Post-Market CMD surveillance		
Lead Beneficiary	SURREY		
Contributing Beneficiaries	SURREY, UBI, QUBI, UMU, UNIS GR		
Due Date	31.06.2024	Actual Date of Submission	30.07.2024
Version	1.0		
Authors	Nada El Kassem (SURREY), Athanasios Giannetsos (UBI), Ioannis Siachos (UBI), Stefanos Vasileiadis (UBI), Vasilios Kalos (UBI), Stylianos Kazazis (QUBI), Niovi Sassalou (QUBI), Symeon Tsintzos (QUBI), Jesús García Rodríguez (UMU), Koukoulas George, Bekos George (UNIS GR)		
Abstract	The deliverable outlines the Trusted Computing Abstractions developed by ENTRUST to facilitate dynamic trust assessment within a Connected Medical Device (CMD) ecosystem, aiming for secure lifecycle management. This initial version of the Runtime Assurance and Certification Framework lays the foundation for trust bootstrapping, covering secure boot processes and runtime trust assessment, to safeguard all operational phases of CMDs. Key contributions include the documentation of Zero-Touch Onboarding (ZTO) processes, incorporating Verifiable Credentials and Signcryption schemes for secure device enrollment, and the introduction of Verifiable Credentials for identity and system attributes management. The deliverable also defines a Trusted Computing Base (TCB) using Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) for high-end CMDs and Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs) for low-end CMDs, ensuring secure, versatile infrastructure and comprehensive attestation evidence. It covers secure lifecycle management enablers, including cryptographic schemes continuous trust assessment.		
Keywords	Attestation, Verifiable Credentials, Root of Trust, OP-TEE, PUF, Connected Medical Devices, p-ABCs		

Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Author	Notes
v0.1	06.05.2024	Nada El Kassem (SURREY)	Initial Table of Contents
v0.2	25.05.2024	Ioannis Siachos (UBI), Athanasios Giannetsos (UBI), Vasilios Kalos (UBI)	Description of updated ENTRUST architecture. Construction and description of action workflows for CMD Enrollment (Chapter 2)
v0.3	30.05.2024	Nada El Kassem (SURREY), Jesús García Rodríguez (UMU)	Description of ENTRUST's underlying Cryptographic Primitives (Chapter 3)
v0.4	15.06.2024	Stylianios Kazazis (QUBI), Niovi Sassalou (QUBI), Symeon Tsintzos (QUBI)	Formulation of the PUF-based TCB (Chapter 4)
v0.5	30.06.2024	Ioannis Siachos (UBI), Athanasios Giannetsos (UBI), Koukoulas George, Bekos George (UNIS GR)	Presentation of ENTRUST's OP-TEE-based TCB (Chapter 4)
v0.55	01.07.2024	Nada El Kassem (SURREY), Athanasios Giannetsos (UBI), Ioannis Siachos (UBI), Stefanos Vasileiadis (UBI), Vasilios Kalos (UBI), Jesús García Rodríguez (UMU)	Description of ENTRUST's Secure Lifecycle Management Enablers (Chapter 5)
v0.6	07.07.24	Nada El Kassem (SURREY), Ioannis Siachos (UBI)	Formulation of Swarm Attestation Mechanisms (Chapter 6)
v0.7	09.07.24	Nada El Kassem (SURREY), Athanasios Giannetsos (UBI), Ioannis Siachos (UBI), Stefanos Vasileiadis (UBI), Vasilios Kalos (UBI), Jesús García Rodríguez (UMU), Stylianios Kazazis (QUBI), Niovi Sassalou (QUBI), Symeon Tsintzos (QUBI), Koukoulas George, Bekos George (UNIS GR)	Technical Roadmap (Chapter 7)
v0.8	13.07.24	Ioannis Siachos (UBI)	Conclusions, Executive Summary, Introduction and Abstract
v0.85	14.07.24	Ioannis Siachos (UBI)	Appendix and abbreviations list
v0.9	17.07.24	Symeon Tsintzos (QUBI), Vaios Bolgouras (UPRC)	Internal review, comments provided
v0.95	29.07.24	Ioannis Siachos (UBI), Athanasios Giannetsos (UBI)	Addressing reviewers' comments, final document polishing, submission-ready version
v1.0	30.07	Ioannis Siachos (UBI), Athanasios Giannetsos (UBI), Lina Giannakandropoulou (UNIS)	QA and submission of the deliverable

Disclaimer

The information in this document is provided “as is”, and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The content of this document reflects only the author’s view – the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. The users use the information at their sole risk and liability. This document has gone through the consortium’s internal review process and is still subject to the review of the European Commission. Updates to the content may be made at a later stage.

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

© 2023 - 2025 ENTRUST Consortium

Project co-funded by the European Commission in the Horizon Programme		
Nature of the deliverable:		OTHER
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive, confidential to ENTRUST project and Commission Services	

- * R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
- DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
- DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
- OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.
- DMP: Data Management Plan

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Term	Description
AAA	Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting
ABAC	Attribute-based Access Control
ABE	Attribute-based Encryption
ABS	Attribute-based Signatures
ACL	Access Control List
AE	Authenticated Encryption
AIC	Attestation Integrity Verification
AIK	Attestation Identity Key
AK	Attestation Key
API	Application Programming Interface
ATL	Actual Level of Trust
BIOS	Basic Input/Output System
CA	Certification Authority
CC	Conformity Certificate
CFA	Control-Flow Attestation
CIV	Configuration Integrity Verification
CMD	Connected Medical Device
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRL	Certificate Revocation List
CRTM	Core Root of Trust for Measurement
CVE	Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures
DAA	Direct Anonymous Attestation
DID	Domain Identifier

DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DM	Domain Manager
DMA	Direct Memory Access
DT	Digital Twin
EAP	Enhanced Authentication Protocol
ECU	Electronic Control Units
EK	Endorsement Key
FV	Formal Verification
FW	Firmware
HSM	Hardware Security Module
HW	Hardware
IDM	Identity Management
IDS	Intrusion Detection System
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IoC	Indicator of Compromise
IoT	Internet of Things
IOMMU	Input/Output Memory Management Unit
ISA	Instruction Set Architecture
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KMS	Key Management System
MUD	Manufacturer Usage Descriptions
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PCR	Platform Configuration Register

PSK	Pre-Shared Key
PUF	Physically Unclonable Function
p-ABC	Privacy-preserving Attribute-Based Credential
RA	Risk Assessment
RATS	Remote ATtestation procedureS
REE	Rich Execution Environment
RoT	Root of Trust
RTL	Required Level of Trustworthiness
SC	Side-Channel
SDLC	Software Development Lifecycle
SM	Security Monitor
SoC	System-on-Chip
SoS	System of Systems
SP	Service Provider
SPLC	Secure Product Life Cycle
SSI	Self-Sovereign Identity
SW	Software
TA	Trusted Application
TARA	Threat Agent Risk Assessment
TC	Trusted Component
TCB	Trusted Computing Base
TCG	Trusted Computing Group
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
TM	Threat Modelling

TOCTOU	Time of Check Time of Use
TPM	Trusted Platform Module
VC	Verifiable Credentials
VM	Virtual Machine
VP	Verifiable Presentation
ZTO	Zero-touch onboarding

Executive Summary

The present deliverable presents the Trusted Computing Abstractions developed by ENTRUST to facilitate dynamic trust assessment as part of a Connected Medical Device (CMD) ecosystem, aimed at achieving secure lifecycle management. This initial version of the Runtime Assurance and Certification Framework sets the groundwork for ENTRUST's vision by establishing a robust foundation for trust bootstrapping, from the secure boot process to runtime trust assessment. This means we aim to safeguard all phases of a device's operation, from its application, execution environment, and hardware level, to the backend system of the medical domain to which it is connected. Ultimately, these abstractions allow CMDs to attest their configuration state to prove that they possess security properties such as integrity, safety, resilience, and robustness. In this context, the present deliverable categorizes three main phases as part of this trust assessment process:

First, it describes how to prepare the CMD for trust establishment. This includes the documentation of the Zero-Touch Onboarding (ZTO) processes, incorporating Verifiable Credentials and Signcryption schemes, enhancing the security and efficiency of device onboarding. The ZTO allows the secure enrollment of devices that possess an adequate trust level and the establishment of all the necessary cryptographic primitives that enable data provisioning in a verifiable manner. Additionally, ENTRUST is the first of its kind to introduce W3C Verifiable Credentials (VCs) and Verifiable Presentations (VPs) not only for identity management but also for system attributes management. These structures are used for disclosing all the required evidence for trust assessment in a verifiable manner.

Second, D4.2 describes the establishment of a device's trust level. A key feature of this deliverable includes the definition of a Trusted Computing Base (TCB) that consists of a Trusted Execution Environment (TEE) for high-end CMDs and a Physical Unclonable Function (PUF) for low-end CMDs. These mechanisms ensure a versatile and secure infrastructure by exposing trusted services that remain agnostic to the underlying Root of Trust (RoT). In continuation of D3.2, we present how ENTRUST's TCB provides attestation evidence as a trust source for CMD and domain trust assessment. Moreover, the deliverable presents secure lifecycle management enablers, including cryptographic schemes for CMD attestation, key-restriction policies, provision of conformity certificates, and verifiable presentations. Specific solutions were developed for different CMD types, enabling their interoperability. Additionally, extensive coverage of methodologies for swarm attestation for low-end CMDs is provided, enhancing security for groups of devices operating under constrained resources.

Lastly, it outlines protocols designed for continuous trust evaluation and mechanisms for re-establishing trust in case of detected anomalies or failures, ensuring persistent device trustworthiness. As such, we design cryptographic schemes for secure and authenticated channels between devices that need to get a software/firmware update. Beyond high-end CMDs, we also provide new efficient schemes based on the use of Merkle Trees for low-end CMD authentication through its parent high-end device.

This deliverable builds on the ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base to create an Interoperable Security Stack, paving the way for comprehensive, secure management of CMDs. The advancements in trusted computing and cryptographic techniques detailed here will guide the next phases of the ENTRUST project. Future developments, including refinements and new features, will be presented in subsequent

deliverables, particularly in D4.3.

Contents

1	Introduction	15
1.1	Scope and Purpose	15
1.2	Relation to Other WPs and Deliverables	16
1.3	Deliverable Structure	17
2	ENTRUST Trusted Execution Architecture for Secure CMD Lifecycle Management	18
2.1	Device- & Domain-level Trust Assessment, Anchored to ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base	20
2.2	Core Crypto Structures & Primitives Vocabulary	25
2.3	Notations	26
2.4	Cryptographic Operations for CMD Onboarding	28
2.4.1	Secure Onboarding	31
2.4.2	High-End Device Enrollment	33
2.4.3	Low-End Device Enrolment	36
2.5	Cryptographic Operations for Runtime Operational Assurance	38
2.5.1	High-End Trust Assessment Process	38
2.5.2	Low-End Trust Assessment Process	39
3	ENTRUST Core Crypto Structures and Primitives	41
3.1	ENTRUST Security Requirements	42
3.2	The Lewko-Waters Algorithm	44
3.2.1	LSSS Matrix	45
3.2.2	ENTRUST Use Case LSSS Matrix Example	46
3.3	Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE)	49
3.3.1	FABEO KP-Attribute-Based Encryption Protocol	49
3.4	Attribute-Based signature (ABS)	50
3.5	Attribute-Based Signcryption	50
3.6	Attribute-Based Credentials	51
3.7	Direct-Anonymous-Attestation	53
3.8	Hash-based Signatures	54
3.8.1	One-Time Signatures (OTS)	54
3.8.2	Merkle Signatures	54
4	ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base	55
4.1	ENTRUST Interoperable Security Stack	55
4.2	High-End device TCB	55
4.2.1	OP-TEE	55
4.2.2	ENTRUST Key Management	57
4.2.3	OP-TEE Security Capabilities	59
4.2.4	ENTRUST Harmonized Set of TEE Key Management Extensions/Interfaces	59

4.3	Low-End device PUF- based TCB	61
4.3.1	PUF-based Key Generation and Reconstruction Scheme	61
4.3.2	Evaluation Metrics	67
4.3.3	Key Derivation Function (KDF) in the Context of ENTRUST's Low-End CMDs	67
5	ENTRUST Secure Lifecycle Management	70
5.1	Zero-Trust Onboarding	70
5.1.1	Device Authentication & VC Issuance	70
5.1.2	High- & Low-End device Enrollment to Target Domain	71
5.2	ENTRUST Runtime Trusted Execution Services	74
5.2.1	High-End Device Attestation	74
5.2.2	System Setup & Notation	75
5.2.3	Enhanced CIV - <i>High Level Overview</i>	76
5.3	Enhanced Authorization with Run-Time Verifiable Key Restriction Usage Policies	77
5.3.1	Architectural Blueprinting & Mode of Operation	78
5.4	Low-End CMD Attestation	82
5.4.1	High-end and Low-end CMD Authentication	83
5.4.2	Low-End Single-Device Attestation	85
5.5	Conformity Certificates	89
5.5.1	Low-End Device's Conformity Certificates	90
5.5.2	High-End Device's Conformity Certificates	91
5.6	VPs During Run-time Phase	93
5.6.1	ABS with Attribute Anonymity and Root Key Binding for the Run-Time Phase	93
5.6.2	ABSC with Sender's Attribute Anonymity and Key Binding During Run-Time Phase	95
5.7	Security Analysis	96
5.7.1	Configuration Integrity Verification	97
5.7.2	Attribute-Based Signatures (ABS) & Attribute-Based SignCryption (ABSC)	98
6	Towards Secure and Scalable Aggregate Attestation	100
6.1	ENTRUST Scalable Aggregate Network Attestation	101
6.1.1	Swarm Topology	102
6.1.2	Verifiers in Swarms	102
6.1.3	Prover's Attestation in Swarms	102
6.1.4	CMD Service-Graph-Chain Attestation	103
6.2	Static vs. Dynamic Swarm Attestation in ENTRUST	103
6.2.1	Trust Assumptions & Security/Privacy Requirements	103
6.3	ENTRUST Low-end Device (Swarm) Attestation	106
6.3.1	Setup Phase	106
6.3.2	Attestation & Report Phase	107
6.3.3	Verification Phase	107
6.4	Scalable Attestation in Dynamic Topologies	108
7	ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base Instantiation in Envisioned Use Cases	110
8	Technical Road-Map	112
9	Conclusions	113
A	Glossary	114
	Bibliography	118

List of Figures

1.1	Relation of D4.2 on other WPs and Deliverables.	17
2.1	ENTRUST Interoperable Security Stack	19
2.2	ENTRUST Architectural Flow of Zero Trust Onboarding	25
2.3	device Authorisation Flow	32
2.4	Issuance of the Attribute Keys by the Privacy CA	34
2.5	Enrolment Authentication for Edge devices based on AACKA[54]	35
2.6	Attestation Key Credential Issuance based on the enhanced privacy-CA solution (ePCAS) in [11]	36
2.7	Enrolment Authentication for low-end devices	37
2.8	Enrolment for Low-end devices	37
2.9	Conformity Certificates for Low-end devices	38
3.1	Example	45
3.2	LSSS Matrix transformation	45
3.3	ENTRUST Use-case example	47
4.1	Overview of (a) generation and (b) reconstruction phases utilizing a PUF instance [67].	63
4.2	Code-offset fuzzy extractor construction scheme	64
4.3	Implementation diagram using a code-offset based fuzzy extractor ($n=255$)[33].	65
4.4	Implementation diagram using a syndrome-based fuzzy extractor for generating and reconstructing a key 256-bit long from the SRAM-PUF instance of ENTRUST.	66
4.5	The SRAM modules' crucial characteristics, namely robustness (red), unpredictability (orange) and unclonability (blue), in terms of FHD, as extracted utilizing the scheme presented in Figure 4.4 i.e. at key-level. In the inset, the corresponding bit-level analysis is depicted for comparison.	68
4.6	The context of KFD utilized for ENTRUST's low-end CMDs.	69
5.1	Issuance of the Attribute Keys by the Privacy CA	71
5.2	ABSC without attribute anonymity (Signcrypt phase)	73
5.3	ABSC without attribute anonymity (Decryption phase)	73
5.4	ENTRUST Verifiable Key Restriction Policy Update: JOIN	79
5.5	ENTRUST Verifiable Key Restriction Policy Update: Run Time Attestation	82
5.6	Key generation of Merkle signature scheme with Merkle tree having height $h = 3$ and $2^h = 8$ leaves	84
5.7	Authentiacion path of the signature generated from R_2 with OTS-public key PK_{OTS}^2	85
5.8	ENTRUST Low-End Single Device Attestation	89
5.9	Enrolment Conformity Certificates for Low-end devices	90
5.10	Run-time Conformity Certificates for Low-end devices	91

- 5.11 High-end device: Creation of Conformity Certificate as VC, and usage of Conformity Certificate during interaction with third party. 92
- 5.12 ABS with attribute anonymity 95

- 6.1 System model of Swarm attestation in ENTRUST 104
- 6.2 Dynamic Swarm Attestation 108

- 7.1 The ENTRUST functionalities described in D4.2 to be evaluated in the context of the Use Cases. 111

List of Tables

2.1	Core Cryptographic Structures of ENTRUST	26
2.2	Cryptographic Keys	26
2.3	Notation Summary	27
3.1	Security Requirements	43
4.1	Key Management Interfaces	61
6.1	Swarm Attestation Properties	102
6.2	Swarm Attestation Generic Requirements	105
6.3	ENTRUST-Specific SA Requirements	105
8.1	Technical Road-Map	112

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Scope and Purpose

ENTRUST's overarching vision is to facilitate the **secure lifecycle management of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs)**, considering the strict security and safety properties that we must ensure in medical domains. To achieve this goal, ENTRUST leverages Trusted Computing technologies and cryptographic primitives towards converting CMDs into security-hardened tokens for which we can **bootstrap trust** from the secure boot all the way up to runtime trust assessment. In this context, this deliverable contains the first version of ENTRUST's **Trusted Execution Architecture**, aiming at achieving the functional specifications that were declared in D4.1.

The core functionalities, as part of the secure lifecycle of CMDs, as it was explained in D4.1, stem from:

- **Trust Assessment** (both and the CMD and the Domain level) trust assessment lies in the heart of the ENTRUST framework and in what follows we are providing the description of how to enable a CMD to establish trust, the mechanisms for establishing trust during runtime, and the appropriate protocols for re-establishing trust in the case of a failed trust assessment.
- **Secure SW/FW update distribution**, including all building blocks that operate in tandem to deliver and install, in a secure and authenticated way, a secure SW/FW patch, in order to enable the reestablishment of trust in a CMD that was rendered untrusted, due to an identified attack or failed trust assessment. It is important to note that Software update is backed up the cryptographic security enablers that are described in this deliverable, but is described in D3.2.
- **Runtime assurance mechanisms** that enable device and service **auditing** in the context of security certification schemes (**Conformity Certificates**, based on the use of Verifiable Presentations that encompass security claims reflecting the security state of CMDs).
- Ensuring **secure communication** and **bootstrapping of trust** for CMDs either within the same medical-service-graph-chain or for cross-domain communication, capitalising on secure and trust-aware **Zero-Touch (Secure) Enrollment** mechanisms.

Essentially, **D4.2 is the first important milestone of the ENTRUST's vision towards the construction of an interoperable security stack** for exposing the necessary building blocks that can enable the provisions of these functionalities in all of the stakeholders/entities comprising a CMD ecosystem, both as it relays to a CMD but also when elevating the operation of a CMD as part of a medical domain. In our project, we differentiate between **device-level** and **domain-level trust management**, considering the additional threats that may come into practise when a CMD becomes a part of a medical-service-graph-chain.

In ENTRUST, we differentiate CMDs according to their **Trusted Computing Base**. In this manner, we have the **high-end CMDs** that possess a TCB constituting of a **Trusted Execution Environment (TEE)** and low-end CMDs with a more restrained **PUF-based TCB**. Due to their computational superiority, high-end CMDs act as “parents” to low-end CMDs by helping them facilitate the various trust assessment enablers that are described in this deliverable. In D4.2, the architecture of both TCBs is presented, alongside with the corresponding cryptographic schemes that rely on those Roots of Trust.

1.2 Relation to Other WPs and Deliverables

The current deliverable paves the way for the ENTRUST’s Runtime Assurance and Certification Framework, in the heart of which resides the **Customisable Trusted Computing Base** responsible for exposing all **trusted services towards securing the entire lifecycle of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs) regardless of their computational capabilities (both high and low-end CMDs)**, - including **secure device enrolment**, thus, ensuring the trustworthiness of a device with respect to the requirements of the target domain; **runtime device integrity monitoring** through a set of novel attestation mechanisms and trust extensions; **patching** for enacting upon the change in the trust state of a device (serving as an indication of risk) leading to the possible update of the SW/FW stack of the deployed device (based on the protocol described in the context of D3.2 [20]); **security audits** through the construction of conformity certificates embodying device status attribute assertions of the device correctness and functional safety; and establishment of **secure and authenticated communication channels** as part of a deployed service-graph chain. More specifically, D4.2 is the second deliverable of WP4 and provides a detailed CMDs’ security architecture and builds the required trust extensions for guaranteeing an acceptable level of security across the whole device (high and low-end) spectrum - at both the device and application level. This culminates to the concrete definition and development of the **ENTRUST interoperable security stack**, that can run across various medical devices, and provides those necessary trusted computing capabilities based on the functional specifications defined (through engineering stories) in D4.1 [19].

Considering also the overall ENTRUST architecture (WP2), D4.2 provides a set of novel attestation and cryptographic primitives for capturing the CMDs’ trust scores. All these trust scores/states are continuously monitored for allowing the construction of a “Network of Trust” capable of reacting (efficiently) to any changes in the trust level of any deployed device. All these new sets of mechanisms, while designed in an agnostic manner to the underlying type RoT, they have been instantiated in the context of ENTRUST for ARM-based hardware architectures for high-end CMDs whereas when their low-end counterparts are considered Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs) were utilized. This allows the development of an interoperable security stack providing robust security guarantees, dynamically adjustable to the type of the device’s TCB.

All the aforementioned capabilities form the basis for future actions of WP4 (guiding the work done towards the compilation of D4.3) that will further provide an extended (and final) version of all ENTRUST trust extensions to be evaluated in the context of the envisioned use cases as part of the WP6 activities. Thus, the developments of D4.2 is a rich source of information for the other technical Work-Packages, as depicted in Figure 1.1. More specifically, it supports WP3 towards the development of a protocol for the secure and authenticated SW update distribution based on the use of authenticated encryption scheme, whereas the formal verification actions will also consider the definition and construction of the TCB which will have to enforce the security policies capturing those device (application) behaviours that cannot be formally verified prior to their deployment and guide the attestation process. WP5 will also take advantage of the WP4 developments as many of the developed crypto schemes will empower several BC-based mechanisms. The aforementioned schemes will empower the trust-aware authentication and authorisation of entities to regulate access to sensitive data stored on the blockchain, while the definition of the VPs as conformity certificates will enable BC-based auditability and certifiability of systems’ state.

As is the case for all technical WPs, the technical developments are consolidated for integration in the context of WP6. Hence, D4.2 provides this first version of technical artifacts that will be integrated and evaluated in the first version of the integrated framework of ENTRUST that will be documented in D6.1.

Figure 1.1: Relation of D4.2 on other WPs and Deliverables.

1.3 Deliverable Structure

The deliverable is organized as follows:

- **Chapter 1** introduces the scope and purpose of the document while providing the role of D4.2 in the ENTRUST framework.
- **Chapter 2** presents the detailed trusted execution architecture considered in the context of ENTRUST for the secure lifecycle management of connected medical devices.
- **Chapter 3** describes the main cryptographic building blocks utilized to support the dynamic trust assessments throughout the entire lifecycle of a CMD.
- **Chapter 4** focuses on ENTRUST's Trusted Computing Base according to the computational resources of the CMD (both high and low-end devices are considered).
- **Chapter 5** elaborates on the cryptographic operations provided by ENTRUST for enabling the secure lifecycle management of high-end and low-end CMDs.
- **Chapter 6** introduces the concept of a secure and scalable aggregate network attestation towards establishing attestable trust to groups of devices in large-scale medical domains, enabling ENTRUST to make intelligent decisions on how to adjust the execution of specific security enablers to identify the optimal balance between converging security and safety without impeding the performance of the deployed device
- **Chapter 7** provides a detailed overview of the ENTRUST's TCB instantiation in the context of the envisioned use cases
- **Chapter 8** concludes the deliverable, providing also the implementations' roadmap and the next development and evaluation steps.

Chapter 2

ENTRUST Trusted Execution Architecture for Secure CMD Lifecycle Management

Expanding on the type of functionalities and trusted services mentioned before, ENTRUST is envisioned as a technical solution advocating the integration of advanced (HW-based) trusted computing primitives for enabling the secure lifecycle management of CMDs, allowing for the continuous trust assessment of all resources and workloads deployed over medical-service-graph-chains. The distinct feature of such a task is the increase of the complexity of trust characterization from a CMD which is operating as a standalone component to a domain representing a medical-service-graph chain. As an example, we have the case of a router that relays messages that gets from deployed sensors or program logic controllers to a database deployed to a medical domain. In this environment, the core property of trust is mainly integrity (doctors want to be sure that the data reach their destination so as to be processed by them). Integrating such a router as part of an operational room that is responsible not only relaying data, but also their processing and the mediation of a secure and authenticated channel between the internal CMDs, this increases the properties of interest that define the trust level of this device. As a result, this goes beyond integrity and also affects safety, resilience, robustness etc. So, the trust characterization, when it comes to much more complicated domains, must be built from the CMD level and elevated to the medical-service-graph-chain level [1, 59].

ENTRUST provides security controls and trust extensions across all layers of a CMD's lifecycle that are enabled by its TCB. The envisioned security stack is the first-of-its-kind to provide a rich and configurable TCB appropriate for devices of different resources. Specifically, a resource rich device-targeted TCB, consisting of a TEE (OP-TEE) is provided for high-end CMDs, capable of performing asymmetric crypto and complex computational tasks. On the other hand, a much more targeted TCB, based on the innovative use of PUFs, can provide the necessary security capabilities that can benefit even low-end CMDs with limited resources. Nevertheless, the cryptographic protocols that are provided by ENTRUST are aimed for the establishment of trust relationships even when considering different Roots of Trust.

ENTRUST provides the capabilities for the harmonization layer to work in RoTs that expose different sets of properties. The schemes and protocols designed in ENTRUST are not tailored to particular RoTs; rather, they are based on common properties that a RoT can expose. Specifically, ENTRUST provides protocols and schemes for achieving these functionalities for RoTs that can expose either a rich or constrained set of capabilities, serving as a first core milestone towards the overall vision of a fully harmonized and interoperable security stack that is agnostic to RoTs. These novel security hardware extensions support ENTRUST's attestation toolkit, enabling all CMDs to produce verifiable security claims during runtime, depicting the trust state of the device. Such claims are based on runtime measurements of the CMD's operation and can capture different properties of trust, ranging from integrity to control-

Figure 2.1: ENTRUST Interoperable Security Stack

flow correctness, as well as safety, resilience, and reliability. Furthermore, ENTRUST accounts for the first-of-its-kind construction of Conformity Certificates based on the use of the W3C Verifiable Credentials (VCs) and Verifiable Presentations (VPs). These p-ABC-based structures allow for continuous monitoring and auditing of the trust state of each CMD and the overall medical-service-graph-chain in a verifiable manner. This is another core enabler for efficient reactions to changes in the trust state of a device, both at the local device level and at a medical domain level. Such certificates can be exchanged between CMDs, establishing trust relationships, while efficient revocation mechanisms are also envisioned (to be designed in the context of D4.3) for invalidating certificates when the Actual Trust Level (ATL) of a device drops below the Required Trust Level (RTL). Additionally, ENTRUST innovates by allowing Conformity Certificates to be provided to an external auditor, achieving both standard requirements on CMD binding and the necessary level of privacy through selective disclosure mechanisms. Moreover, VCs and VPs are also used for disclosing more granular trust properties and are combined with a new and efficient Attribute Based Signcryption scheme.

As already highlighted, ENTRUST designs a novel, open-source, modular, and highly portable security stack that can run on various devices using heterogeneous hardware architectures (see Figure 2.1). This translates to all of the provided security schemes and protocols being agnostic to the type of Root-of-Trust being integrated into the target device. Following the definition of the ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base (TCB as put forth in D4.1), this comprises all (HW/FW/SW) system components and modules the combination of which is responsible for enforcing a security policy. In order to achieve this, we need a Root of Trust (RoT), a part of the system that is assumed to be trustworthy and upon which all other results are built. Any RoT that can expose the fundamental functionalities for Root-of-Trust for Measurement, Storage and Reporting can be considered as the trust anchor in the overall ENTRUST ecosystem. However, for supporting the implementation activities of ENTRUST, the entire ENTRUST TCB of high-end CMDs has been built featuring the OP-TEE Trusted Execution Environment. Regarding low-end CMDs, ENTRUST is the 1st of it's kind to introduce an open source implementation of a trust anchor leveraging the emerging PUF as a security element. As such, we are providing the necessary mechanisms of how we can use such a cheap trust anchor to enable functionalities spanning from authentication between low-end to

high-end CMDs, all the way to the construction of Conformity Certificates binded to the CMD's ID.

In what follows, we first summarize the execution flow of the actions that need to be taken by a CMD during onboarding/enrollment to a medical domain of interest. Medical domain, in the ENTRUST ecosystem, comprises a set of (HW and SW) assets and elements to which various medical services and application workloads can be deployed. The produced ENTRUST Zero-touch Onboarding protocol, and all internal building blocks, prepare the CMD for its secure and trustworthy participation in the deployed medical-service-graph-chain: Domain Managers (acting as orchestrators of the service deployment in a particular domain) accommodate service workloads only over elements that can exhibit the Required Trust Level (RTL). ENTRUST separates trust at the CMD and at the domain level and provides all the necessary security mechanisms that enable the bootstrapping of trust from the former to the latter.

After the CMD's secure onboarding, it is ready to interact with the other domain elements while monitoring any changes in the trust level of the target CMD that may indicate a possible compromise. This is again facilitated through the ENTRUST TCB. The (auditable) security and trust policy enforcement is facilitated through the ENTRUST Blockchain infrastructure and the Trust Assessment Framework that allows for the secure execution of data sharing agreements. This overall information flow sets the scene for the detailed description of the overall crypto operations that take place as well as the internal building blocks for allowing the equipment of the device with Verifiable Credentials embodying device attributes that can depict its trust state (see D3.2 for more details on trust assessment).

2.1 Device- & Domain-level Trust Assessment, Anchored to ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base

This section presents the Updated ENTRUST Trusted Execution Architecture for Secure Lifecycle Management. The following text covers the high-level information flows (presented as steps throughout the text, referencing Figure 2.2) and the justification of the various design choices made during design. Regarding the steps numbering in the figure, steps that have a single number refer to all types of CMDs while the ones that contain also the letter 'a' (high-end CMDs) or 'b' (low-end CMDs) refer to specific types of devices.

In ENTRUST, the Secure Lifecycle Management of CMDs starts from the need to on-board an ENTRUST TCB-enabled Connected Medical device into a medical domain while preserving the trust state of the domain and the already established medical-service-graph-chains. Trust can be defined through a variety of properties including integrity, resilience, robustness, safety, etc. This requirement arises from the broad attack surface that could be exploited to compromise not just an individual CMD but potentially many devices and systems if a CMD without adequate trust levels is allowed to join the medical-service-graph-chain. Therefore, the Domain Manager (DM) must have trust policies that include the RTL a device must demonstrate before enrollment. The RTL, as previously described, is determined based on the types of risks with the highest impact on the specific medical domain and is essentially a list of trust evidence that must be monitored during both the CMD on-boarding and its runtime operation. This evidence, derived from the ENTRUST attestation mechanisms, represents the necessary trust properties in the form of security claims, such as whether a device has the expected configuration integrity and/or has booted up correctly.

To this end, ENTRUST adopts and extends the Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD) profile proposed by the IETF standard to define the intended use of specific-purpose devices (see D3.2). We refer to these extended MUDs as eMUDs. The primary objective is to limit the attack surface of a given CMD by establishing profiles that depict its expected behavior. These profiles can include the reference values of configuration hashes for all binaries in the CMD's software stack (enabling runtime device integrity

checks), the configuration hashes for the booted firmware of the CMD (enabling secure boot checks), and the type and size of keys used per deployed service (enabling safety checks). These profiles are initially designed by the CMD manufacturer and later extended by the combined forces of the Security Administrator of the medical domain and the ENTRUST platform itself, as reference values against which runtime system measurements will be evaluated.

In continuation of the work presented in D3.2, we assume that the Risk Assessment process has already been done from the Manufacturer side in the CMD-level. The output of this procedure is already part of the MUD profile that is stored in the MUD Server. After the initialization of the CMD's Bootstrapping process, the Privacy CA fetches it with the MUD URL in order to retrieve its policy hashes and create the corresponding VCs (Step 3).

In ENTRUST, these reference values are converted into policy hashes that define the key restriction usage policies for governing the usage of Attestation Keys (AK). This design choice was made in order to overcome the current limitation of the existing remote attestation schemes which is the fact that in order for the evidence to be verified, an inherent assumption for the trustworthiness of the verifier must be made. ENTRUST, inspired by the emerging zero-trust principles, is the first of its kind to introduce key restriction usage policies that enable the proof of ownership of specific attributes without disclosing them (something that may lead to implementation disclosure attacks). Essentially, a CMD creates a policy-restricted Attestation Key by executing the JOIN phase with the Domain Manager, which dynamically restricts the device's AK (secured in its ENTRUST TCB) to the policies chosen by the (authorized) Domain Manager. By basing its ability to use its AK for signing on its trust properties/attributes, we can verify a device's conformance using a simple challenge-response protocol that neither requires nor reveals any configuration information (Step 11a).

Additionally, to update a device's "trusted configuration state" during runtime (e.g., in response to patches and software updates), ENTRUST introduces the use of verifiable key restriction usage policies. This allows the Domain Manager to reactively or proactively authorize new policies that restrict the CMD's attestation key to a new reference value without needing to create a new AK. This mechanism also protects against adversaries attempting to manipulate the software update process by reloading a previous key restriction usage policy, which, while obsolete, has not been invalidated in the policy hierarchy of the RoT.

The eMUD Profile is accessed by the Domain Manager for a specific CMD through the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure (eMUD profiles are deployed and enforced via specially crafted smart contracts as detailed in D5.1), upon receiving a "request to register" from the device. (Steps 6-7 and a-d) As defined in the MUD standard, this process first requires authenticating the CMD before allowing the DM to request the ID of the MUD file stored on the Blockchain. The initialization of the CMD's enrollment begins with a request from the device to be enrolled. Then, the DM requests an authentication token which states that the CMD is authenticated with the Privacy CA and is equipped with the appropriate identity credentials to establish trust relationships within the domain. CMD authentication relies on the Root ID Key, a pre-established cryptographic key provided to the device during manufacturing. Upon receiving the registration request, the DM contacts the Privacy CA to mediate a challenge-response protocol for authenticating the requesting CMD. At the end of this process, the DM is informed of the MUD Profile ID, which it uses to query the actual CMD profile (containing the reference values) from the Blockchain infrastructure. This allows the DM to extract the policy hashes (after the calculation of the Domain-Specific eMUD), which are then deployed to the device, establishing the necessary set of key restriction usage policies to predicate the use of its AK (Steps 1-13a and 1-11b).

Due to the high sensitivity of medical services, different privacy requirements may be present, both as it pertains to the anonymity of the CMD but also to the characteristics of the device that need to be disclosed during runtime for representing its trust. As an example we will take an operational room. In this context, there must be an efficient way for all the devices to establish trust relationships with one

another. To achieve this, CMDs must be able to disclose their attributes, based on which it can establish trust relationships. An example of such attribute could be that the sensor that measures the patient's heart rate is at an expected state. On the other hand, there are examples like the Smart Ambulance scenario in the Digital Assistance Towards Enhancing the Health and Well-being of Patients and Carers use case there is a communication between two medical domains. Namely, the ambulance and the hospital. In this case, an ambulance may need to establish a trust relationship with a new hospital, causing serious privacy considerations. Trust should be established without disclosing the details of the type of HW that is running as part of the ambulance. Consequently, that patient's information should be disclosed in a zero knowledge manner regarding the capabilities of the domain itself. For this reason, those characteristics of the CMD that trust assessment revolves around are depicted as attribute keys. On the other hand, during runtime, based on those credentials, Conformity Certificates that are to be presented at an external auditor are created (Steps 14a and 12b). The differentiating factor here is that Conformity Certificates should be consumed by any auditor. This means that they need to comprise of evidence and appraisals on the trust state of a CMD in a plaintext format. As such, the TAF can create a Conformity Certificate for a device and also for the domain (e.g., the domain has integrity if all the devices within it have integrity). The domain-level certificate is held by the domain manager, who provides it to auditors. We must enable CMDs to assess trustworthiness levels during runtime efficiently: depending on the safety criticality of a domain or device, it might be necessary to perform a device-level trust assessment, which may then need to be elevated to a domain-level trust assessment. This approach is taken because, in many cases, the focus is not on individual devices but on the entire domain, since CMDs have collaborative functions. This is why, as it will be seen in Chapter 5, ENTRUST separates between VCs that are used for establishing trust relationships during runtime and p-ABCs based on which Conformity Certificates with trust appraisal abstractions can be disclosed.

Trust assessment is based on monitoring various trustworthiness evidence, as discussed in D3.2. Depending on the capabilities of the devices, we differentiate between static and runtime properties (Step 15a). For high-end CMDs equipped with advanced tracing capabilities, we can monitor and extract dynamic properties such as CIV and CFI, attempting to identify any possible misconfigurations during the device's runtime phase. On the other hand, for low-end devices with limited computational capabilities that cannot monitor these properties, we can only verify static properties (e.g., secure boot). Therefore, for low-end devices, the Conformity Certificate is established during enrollment, allowing the device to show during runtime that the specific attribute has not changed. In ENTRUST, we aim to evaluate the weight of this evidence in the trust assessment.

The AK is used for signing the runtime measurements of the CMD's configuration and execution properties, which the DM (or any other entity acting as a verifier) assesses to determine the CMD's trust state. These signatures, provided as security claims, are produced by the ENTRUST TCB's Attestation Agent using the designed attestation schemes described in Chapter 5. As outlined in D3.1, ENTRUST combines formal verification of a CMD's profile during design-time (to identify the trust model/boundaries within which various applications operate) with runtime security (attestation) controls. Specifically, ENTRUST advances the state-of-the-art by defining a methodology where only CMD behaviors that cannot be formally verified are subjected to runtime monitoring and attestation. These policies dictate the type of security claims the CMD must provide to the DM during enrollment and periodically monitor during runtime to detect any changes in the CMD's trust state. This enables domain-wide trust assessment by the TAF based on asynchronous trust state monitoring of all included CMDs (Step 15a). Furthermore, all extracted trustworthiness evidence is stored either on the Blockchain infrastructure or the off-chain storage with a pointer in the DLT. This results in the creation of a "hygiene pool" by recording the history of trust levels (per CMD) and low-level system evidence (traces) in case of a failed attestation result. It also provides the Security Administrator with access to detailed logs and traces to pinpoint new types of vulnerabilities that were exploited. This triggers the ENTRUST Risk Assessment process to recalculate the overall risk graph, based on which new security policies can be created, potentially leading to the

deployment of patches in response to newly identified vulnerabilities.

To enable the creation and sharing of trustworthiness evidence in a verifiable manner, ENTRUST has developed a secure and efficient cryptographic protocol called the ENTRUST SignCryption Scheme (Step 10a). This protocol encodes claims as attributes within Verifiable Credentials (VCs). It is crucial to have flexibility in who can generate these claims, such as claims based on attestation evidence created by the ENTRUST TCB, which typically have a short lifespan (Conformity Certificates). The Conformity Certificate can aid the privacy of the CMD by the usage of the p-ABC scheme, by selectively disclosing through zero-knowledge proofs the information in the VC according to a specific policy.

The ENTRUST TCB can adjust the integrity, confidentiality, and privacy levels of the Verifiable Presentations (VPs) based on the recipient of these claims. For instance, when VPs are shared with the DM or other devices within the same domain, the focus is primarily on maintaining integrity, which is ensured through the attribute-based signature capabilities of the SignCryption scheme. When claims are shared with external entities for audit purposes, both integrity and confidentiality are essential. These are achieved through a combination of attribute-based signatures and encryption operations. The control policies governing this process are managed and deployed by the DM using appropriate access control trees.

However, for the CMD to self-issue such Verifiable Presentations (VPs) depicting the required trust properties in a privacy-preserving manner, it must first obtain the necessary Verifiable Credentials (VCs) containing all possible trust attributes through separate attribute keys (Steps 1-4). This process is illustrated in Figure 2.3, where the device communicates with the Privacy Certification Authority (Privacy CA), a trusted entity that issues attribute keys to this specific type of device (Steps 1-4). The VCs include attributes representing any hardware-based security controls of the target device, which are used to prove trust assurances. The Privacy CA issues VCs under the CMD's binding property, that is the CMD's unique identifier. This unique identifier, as part of the ENTRUST's envisioned solution is based on an HW-based key for enhanced level of assurance. While this can be any type of HW-based key that can be created by the CMD, hence, in the subsequent crypto schemes there exists a generation of an asymmetric key pair, in the context of ENTRUST, and as part of the high-end CMD, it is the HW-based Root ID key that is used for this binding. This means that the Privacy CA binds the VCs to the public part of the Root ID key of the device. A combination of these attributes proves the overall trust state of the device. This is achieved through the self-issuance of VPs capable of selectively disclosing a subset of attributes based on the construction of "trust predicates." These predicates enable the zero-knowledge proof of ownership of specific attributes without disclosing the type of attributes or their exact values, which could otherwise lead to implementation disclosure attacks. Once the VCs have been issued, then the device can present the necessary VPs to the DM proving its RTL based on which the DM enrolls the device to the target domain and allow its further participation to the established service-graph-chains.

When a CMD is properly enrolled, a shared secret between it and the DM is created. In order for this secret to be sent to the device, the DM creates a key (the shared secret) that is signed and encrypted under the Attribute-based Access Control Tree that the CMD must satisfy in order to participate into the domain. This protected secret is then sent (after the VC authentication with the Privacy CA) to the CMD that, if it is possessing the correct attributes, can decrypt it and then sign a challenge to be sent to the DM. This will complete the enrollment to the domain. Nevertheless, a clarification about the attributes is needed. The attributes span from static properties of the CMD (e.g. secure boot, possession of a valid TCB, secure tracer) to runtime ones. A crucial runtime property is the equipment with a Attestation Key that is binded to the key restriction usage policies based on with, the CMD can create the attestation reports that contain it's trust claims during runtime. So, when the CMD receives the encrypted secret from the DM, this attribute fails because it doesn't have an AK yet. To be able to decrypt this secret and properly enroll to the domain, the device must initiate a JOIN process with the DM to create the AK (Steps 8 and 9a-13a).

After the CMD enrollment into the domain, it is equipped with all the appropriate cryptographic material that enable it to attest its state and bootstrap trust from itself to the domain-level. This can be made possible with the various functionalities that it can perform. Based on the trust policy that is defined for the domain, the synchronous or asynchronous process of monitoring the system measurements of the CMD that will be processed by the TAF for the runtime trust assessment, is initiated. Also, during runtime, the TAF, when requested or triggered by an auditing policy, creates the Conformity Certificates for the CMD (Step 15a). The Conformity Certificates include trust appraisals and can be created as domain or device-level. As an example, a trust appraisal can be the fact that the domain satisfy the requirement of integrity. Additionally, the Conformity Certificates are binded to the public part of the Root ID key of the devices. As such, the CMD can create the p-ABCs that selectively disclose only those trust appraisals that are required each time. Furthermore, during runtime, a CMD may have to communicate with another CMD in a different or the same domain. In the case of the same domain communication, privacy constrains are not present and the CMD can create a ABS and present evidence in a verifiable manner regarding its trust level. As a result, they can bootstrap a trust relationship. In the case of a different domain, the ABSC scheme is used instead to preserve both integrity and confidentiality. ENTRUST is the first of its kind to merge the usage of Access Control Trees with FABIO matrices for an efficient implementation of SignCryption.

The aforementioned security mechanisms require a CMD that has a rich TEE-enabled Trusted Computing Base. Nevertheless, in ENTRUST, we envision two types of CMDs, namely, high-end (TEE-based TCB) and low-end (PUF-based TCB). The low-end CMDs, given their low computational capacity and the lighter cryptographic building blocks that the PUF provides, are not able to perform asymmetric cryptography. For all the asymmetric cryptography-based operations that the ENTRUST platform provides for the Secure Lifecycle Management of CMDs, a "parent" high-end CMD is assigned to each low-end, by the DM. The high-end CMD acts as a proxy or relay for those operations and acts on behalf of the low-end CMD. In order to do so, the low-end CMD must be authenticated (with the help of the DM) to the high-end and a shared secret must be established between the former and the latter for a secure and authenticated symmetrically encrypted channel. In ENTRUST, we solve this problem with the use of a Merkle Signature Scheme (see Section 5.4.1). Regarding attestation, a low-end CMD can attest its state with the help of its PUF, either alone, with a signature based on the PUF output or in a "swarm" with the help of a high-end CMD, based on the concept of a hash-chain. Also, The high-end CMD's Device and System Data collection component communicates with its "child" low-end device in case that the former must relay attestation reports of the latter. This is achieved through an authenticated channel between the two and is of high importance in the novel swarm attestation mechanism presented in ENTRUST. Finally, regarding VCs, a low-end CMD can't selectively disclose its attributes. As such, it is not equipped with VCs as attribute keys. When enrolled, due to its PUF-based TCB, the low-end device can be provided with VCs as p-ABCs that can present them during runtime with evidence that its state is correct.

Figure 2.2: ENTRUST Architectural Flow of Zero Trust Onboarding

2.2 Core Crypto Structures & Primitives Vocabulary

Before presenting the ENTRUST Runtime Assurance & Certification Framework, we summarize the high-level description of the core cryptographic structures, used for supporting the secure lifecycle management of CMDs; from the design, to the secure on-boarding and to the provision of operational assurance of the device using the security enablers of ENTRUST (attestation, VCs, VPs, etc):

Structure	Description & Need
Key Restriction Usage Policies	The security of the ENTRUST ecosystem is heavily based on local attestation, under which the CMD is unable to access a specific structure unless a defined set assertion is satisfied. This assertion results, if successful, to a hash digest call key restriction usage policy that represents state correctness.
Key Hierarchy	As Key Hierarchy we define a multi layer tree like structure such that each node represents a cryptographic key and each branch pointing from one node to another indicates a key derivation from one key to another.
Domain Identifier	We refer to Domain Identifier the Unique identifier of each Domain Manager. The Domain identifier can act as proof of which domain region a device belongs to.
Verifiable Credential	The Verifiable Credential is a construction, used in order to represent the attributes of a device in a Trustworthy and Verifiable manner. Eventually the Verifiable Credential (VC), are used from the device so as to report on its own attributes.

Verifiable Presentation	The Verifiable Presentation (VP) is the data structure used for disclosing a subset or the whole set of the security-related information needed for the receiving entity to evaluate different security aspects of the attested device.
p-ABC	The p-ABC is a signature structure for attributes of a device that allows the derivation of zero-knowledge proofs. Both signatures and zero-knowledge proofs generated will be integrated within the Verifiable Credential structure.
Conformity Certificates	Conformity Certificates are a data structure that certifies the high-level trust aspects (such as resilience, integrity...) of a device or system according the domain's trust model. They will be later presented in a privacy-preserving way to auditors. To this end, they will be instantiated through the VC and p-ABC structures.

Table 2.1: Core Cryptographic Structures of ENTRUST

In the same direction, in the following Table 2.2, we document all the types of crypto keys that are created and managed by ENTRUST's TCB for supporting the provision/execution of all relevant trusted services.

Keys	Description & Need
Root ID Key	This is an asymmetric key inside the Trusted Component for high-end devices and a symmetric PUF root key for low-end devices, both injected at manufacturing time. The Root ID key (RK) is unique for every trusted component, acting as the device identifier, and the key cannot be changed, removed, or used outside of the device. It is considered as the device identity key.
Attestation Key	The attestation identity keys (asymmetric) are bounded to the root ID key of the high-end device. This key must be certified by the Domain Manager (DM) before being used for the attestation services.
Software Update Key	To verify the integrity of FW such that confidentiality and authentication are ensured using a static pre-shared key (long-term SW update symmetric key). In ENTRUST, this key should be stored in the RoT, in a policy-protected manner, to prevent leakage. Attesting the correct device state is crucial to creating a key restriction policy on the SW update key, stored in the RoT.
HW-based TEE Key	A type of endorsement key used for the verification of the validity of the secure element hosted on the device. The key is unique, created during manufacturing, is not user-specific, remains fixed, and identifies the secure element, which is the underlying root of trust.
Domain Id Key (per CMD)	This is a secret that is created between the DM and a high-end CMD during enrollment.
VC secret key	The CMD creates a secret key pair, binded to the VC, in order to achieve device and holder binding. In the context of ENTRUST's onboarding protocol, this key is equivalent with the Root Id key of the device.
Tracer Key	Asymmetric key pair pre-loaded as part of the ENTRUST tracing capabilities used for enforcing the correct reception of only authentic traces to be exchanged between the (untrusted-world-instantiated) binary and the ENTRUST Attestation Agent as part of the trusted computing base. Thus the key pair is used for signing and validating the collected traces.
Attribute Keys	An Attribute Key can be a signing or encryption key. Attribute keys are used in the ENTRUST Attribute-based Encryption (ABE), Attribute-based Signature (ABS), and Attribute-based Signcryption schemes. The generation of those keys is described in Figure 5.1. Attribute keys are issued by the Privacy CA and should be certified before being used.

Table 2.2: Cryptographic Keys

2.3 Notations

Table 2.3 summarizes the notation used throughout the whole document:

Table 2.3: Notation Summary

Symbol	Description
Privacy Certification Authority	Privacy CA
DM	The Domain Manager
Edge device	E
Low-end device	D
q	A prime number that defines the order of cyclic groups
g_1, g_2	Basepoints of the groups \mathbb{G}_1 and \mathbb{G}_2 respectively
e	Type III pairing defined by $e : \mathbb{G}_1 \times \mathbb{G}_2 \rightarrow \mathbb{G}_T$
(csk, cpk)	The DM private and public key pair
(Msk, Mpk)	The manufacturer's private and public key pair
(SK_{CA}, PK_{CA})	The Privacy CA private and public key pair. $SK_{CA} = \alpha \leftarrow_{\mathbb{Z}_p}$ and $PK_{CA} = e(g_1, g_2)^\alpha$
$RK : (rsk, rpk)$	The Edge(high-end) device Root Key pair
$AK : (f, F = g_1^f)$	The Edge device Attestation Key
CRED	The Attestation key Credential
Domain Key DK_E	The domain key used by the Edge device for accessing a specific domain. It is issued by the Privacy CA as an attribute key when the device is enrolled in the domain
$\leftarrow_{\mathbb{S}}$	Indicates that an element is randomly chosen
\mathcal{U}	Universal attribute set
\mathcal{S}	The user attribute set
\mathbf{M}	The general policy matrix
(n_1, n_2)	The number of rows and columns respectively in the policy matrix \mathbf{M}
$\pi(i)$	The attribute in the i^{th} row of the matrix \mathbf{M}
\mathcal{I}	The row indices for the attributes belonging to \mathcal{S} in the policy matrix \mathbf{M}
$sk_1, sk_{2,i}$	The sets of attribute keys
ENC, DEC	The asymmetric encryption and decryption functions respectively
sENC, sDEC	The symmetric encryption and decryption functions respectively
SIG	The signing operation
MAC	Message Authentication Code function used to authenticate the origin and nature of a message
KDF	Key Derivation Function which is a one-way function used to derive key material from another source of entropy
λ	Security parameter
σ	Signature output
ch	Challenge
H_1	A hash function defined as $H_1 : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{G}_1$
λ	Security parameter
G_i	A group, particularly a cyclic abelian group e.g. an elliptic curve
\mathbb{Z}_r	Modular integers of order r
$\Gamma = (r, G_1, G_2, G_3, e)$	A pairing, with e denoting the pairing function.
H_0	A hash function defined as $H_0 : \mathbb{Z}_r^k \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_r \times G_1^*$
H_0	A hash function defined as $H_0 : \mathbb{Z}_r^k \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_r \times G_1^*$
H_1	$H_1 : G_2^{n(k+2)} \rightarrow \Theta^n \subset \mathbb{Z}_r^n$ with $1/ \Theta $ negligible in λ
H_2	A hash function defined as $\{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_r$ for computing challenge from context
A, R, H, P	Sets of indexes of attributes (A), split on revealed (R), hidden (H) and linked to a predicate (P)
\vec{a}	A vector of attributes (elements in \mathbb{Z}_r) involved in p-ABC protocol
NIZK	Non-interactive zero-knowledge proof of knowledge protocol
σ	A signature
π	A serialized NIZK proof token
V	A Pedersen commitment
ctx	Context of the ZK proof, including e.g. fresh nonce.
$Tracer_{pub}$	The public key of the Tracer.
$Tracer_{priv}$	The private key of the Tracer.
rand	Random 32 bytes number.
MRSIGNER	The Hash digest of the public key of the Security Administrator.
P	The policy that the Attestation Key is to be bound with.

Symbol	Description
<i>seed</i>	The random seed under which the Attestation Key is going to be created.
AK_{priv}	The private part of the Attestation Key.
AK_{HASH}	The hash digest of the private part of the Attestation Key.
AK_{pub}	The public part of the Attestation Key.
AK_{name}	The name of the Attestation Key, aka the hash digest of the public part of the Attestation Key.
$CC_{pabc_{priv}}$	The private part of the Conformity Certificate generation key controlled by the TAF for high-end devices using p-ABC scheme.
$CC_{pabc_{pub}}$	The public part of the Conformity Certificate generation key controlled by the TAF for high-end devices using p-ABC scheme.
$CC_{plain_{priv}}$	The private part of the Conformity Certificate generation key controlled by the TAF for low-end devices using plain signatures.
$CC_{plain_{pub}}$	The public part of the Conformity Certificate generation key controlled by the TAF for low-end devices using plain signatures.
VPE_{priv}	The private part of the VPE Key.
VPE_{pub}	The public part of the VPE Key.
VPE_{ENC}	The Encrypted private part of the VPE KEY.
VPE_{HASH}	The hash digest of the private part of the VPE Key.
$P_{authorized}$	The approved runtime configuration hash digest of the Attestation Agent.
<i>Ticket</i>	A signature over the $P_{authorized}$ provided by the Domain Manager.
<i>MRAA</i>	The enclave measurement of the Attestation Agent.
<i>MRTracer</i>	The enclave measurement of the Tracer.
<i>Secret1</i>	The secret that is targeted to be sent to the VPE.
$Secret1_{ENC}$	The encrypted <i>Secret1</i> .
$HMAC_{key}$	A random HMAC Key.
$Secret1_{MAC}$	The Authentication digest of <i>rand</i> over the $HMAC_{key}$.
$rand1_{ENC}$	The Encrypted random <i>rand</i> under the $RootID_{pub}$.
<i>Secret2</i>	The secret that is targeted to be sent to the Attestation Agent.
$Secret2_{ENC}$	The encrypted <i>Secret2</i> under the <i>rand</i> .
$Secret2_{MAC}$	The authentication digest of <i>rand</i> under the $HMAC_{KEY}$.
$rand2_{ENC}$	The Encrypted random <i>rand</i> under the $RootID_{pub}$.
$Secret1'_{MAC}$	The Authentication digest of <i>rand</i> over the $HMAC_{key}$.
$Secret2'_{MAC}$	The Authentication digest of <i>rand</i> over the $HMAC_{key}$.
<i>nonce1</i>	A random 32 bytes number.
<i>nonce2</i>	A random 32 bytes number.
<i>TraceHash</i>	The hash digest of the runtime configuration of attested applications.
σ_1	The signature of a hash digest containing the <i>nonce1</i> and the <i>TraceHash</i> over the private key of the Tracer.
σ_2	The signature of a hash digest containing the <i>nonce2</i> and the <i>MRTracer</i> over the private key of the Tracer.
<i>CC</i>	The command code of specific restriction policy command that needs to be enforced by the TCB's policy engine.
σ_3	The signature of a hash digest containing the <i>nonce1</i> and the <i>MRAA</i> over the private key of the VPE.
σ	The signature of a hash digest over the private part of the Attestation key.
a_{h0}	The Root node of the Merkle Tree

2.4 Cryptographic Operations for CMD Onboarding

In this section, we will outline the operations followed by a device, in order to join the infrastructure of a specific domain. To that end, a device will first request authentication by the privacy Certification Authority (Privacy CA), so as to receive attestable information about its security properties and characteristics (i.e., secure boot, cryptographic capabilities, Manufacturer identity, year of assembly etc.). The Privacy CA will issue a Verifiable Credential over those attributes, bound to the device. Furthermore, in the case of a high-end CMD, the Privacy CA will also return a set of attribute keys, that can be used by the device to privately showcase compliment to a required attribute policy.

Note that, the Privacy CA will only provide the device with the requested Verifiable Credential and attribute keys (in the case of a high-end CMD), if it successfully authenticates it. device authentication by the Privacy CA will happen on the grounds of the trust relationship maintained between the Privacy CA and the device Manufacturer.

Later, during the enrolment of a device in the domain, the Domain's Manager (DM) will request verifiable information about the device's properties, which will then check against their established (Domain specific) policies (security and privacy requirements etc.). In the case of a high-end CMD, the device will use its attribute keys, to showcase to the DM that it satisfies their policy in a privacy preserving manner. Low-end devices on the other hand, not able to use attribute based cryptographic primitives, will return their VC to the DM, who will verify it with the help of the device's Manufacturer. Then, the DM will check the attributes included in the low-end CMD's VC against their policy, as to admit the device in the Domain. In both cases, if the DM is convinced about the device's eligibility to join the Domain's infrastructure, they will establish shared secret cryptographic keys, as to facilitate secure communication with that device.

After the DM authenticates the device, it will request from the Trust Assessment Framework (TAF) the issuance of a Conformity Certificate (see Section 2.9). This certificate, in contrast to the VC issued by the Privacy CA, will contain security appraisals about the device made by the DM. In the case of a high-end device, those will include assessments over both static and run time properties (e.g., configuration and control flow integrity etc.). For low-end devices, not able to reliably track run time properties, the Conformity Certificate will only include appraisals based on static properties (e.g., successful secure boot etc.). Note that, since Conformity Certificates utilized by high-end devices include run-time trust appraisals, a mechanism will be needed for CCs to be re-issued, after the device is already enrolled to the Domain. There are two options to achieve this. First, the synchronous issuance of one-time use CCs. In detail, every time a trust assessment request is received by a high-end device, it will contact the DM, as to get a new CC over its current run-time trust appraisals. Second, the asynchronous issuance of CCs, where the high-end will request a new CC, either on its own, every time it detects a change on its run-time configuration, or periodically. Note that, asynchronous issuance of CCs necessitates the capability to revoke a certificate. In ENTRUST we will evaluate those two options on the basis of security, performance and scalability.

Note here the difference between the two credentials a device will hold; the Verifiable Credential (VC) and the Conformity Certificate (CC). On the one hand, a VC will contain Manufacturer attested information about the device's properties and characteristics. They are intended for use by external (highly privileged) auditors, or by the low-end device during Domain enrolment. On the other hand, a CC contains trust appraisals made by the DM, based on static or run-time (in the case of a high-end) device properties. Conformity Certificates are mainly meant to be used for both inner and cross Domain trust establishment. In the later case of cross Domain communication, presentation of a CC needs to be made in a privacy preserving manner. This necessitates another distinction between Verifiable Credentials and Conformity Certificates, namely, in contrast to VCs, CCs need to support selective disclosure of attributes and unlinkable verifiable presentations. This results to different cryptographic algorithms, used to issue each credential type. Specifically, VCs will always be signed by a typical digital signature algorithm (e.g., edDSA) while CCs, intended for the high-end device, will be signed using p-ABCs (see Section 3.6). This will allow the high-end device to use selective disclosure, and create unlinkable, zero-knowledge, presentations of its Conformity Certificate (CC's intended for the low-end CMD will not have this capability).

Note that the above high-level procedure, is followed by both high-end and low-end devices. Of course, the semantics and specific mechanisms utilised will differ, depending on the device's cryptographic capabilities. Lastly, inherent in the ENTRUST protocol are the following trust relationships; the Privacy CA trusts the device manufacturer, while the Domain Manager trusts the Privacy CA.

In the following sections we will examine in greater detail the steps with which a device will be authenti-

cated by the Privacy CA and later, be enrolled to a Domain.

2.4.0.1 Authentication

The goal of the authentication procedure is to allow the Privacy CA to verify the device, and provide it with the ability to attest its properties, in an authenticated manner. Later, the device will use this capability in proving its eligibility to join a Domain infrastructure. To that end, the device will be verified by the Privacy CA, based on its Root ID key, with the help of the Manufacturer's AAA server. If successful, the Privacy CA will issue a verifiable credential (VC) for that device, containing device specific security attributes, as identified by the Manufacturer. In the case of a high-end device, able to support Attribute Based cryptographic protocols, for each of those attributes, the Privacy CA will also generate and return an attribute key. Note that, those attribute keys will be bound to the device's Root ID key, in a way that only the specified high-end device will be able to use them.

In ENTRUST, Verifiable Credentials will be signed using the edDSA cryptographic algorithm by the Privacy CA. Note that although there are not any privacy requirements for the use of those credentials, there is still the need to guarantee device binding, i.e., that only the device for which the VC is intended can actually use it. This is done through the binding of the VC with the device's Root ID key. In the case of the low-end device, this also means that VC verification will require the support of the device's Manufacturer.

2.4.0.2 Enrollment

During the enrolment of a device to a Domain, the Domain's Manager (DM) will request from the device proof of its attributes. If the DM is able to verify those proofs, and the attributes of the device satisfy their policy, the device will be enrolled to the Domain. In that case, devices will establish new symmetric keys with the DM, used for authentication and secure communications. High-end devices will use Attribute Base Signcryption (ABSC) to prove ownership of attributes that satisfy the DM's policy and authenticate a Diffie-Hellman key exchange for symmetric key establishment. On the other hand, the low-end device will use its Verifiable Credential to prove possession of the required attributes, which in contrast to ABS and ABSC, used by the high-end, does not provide attribute privacy. After a low-end device is successfully enrolled to a Domain, the DM will retrieve from the Manufacturer a mapping between a set of predefined challenges and the corresponding outputs of the device's PUF. Those will be used to establish symmetric keys between the low-end device and the DM, using a Key Derivation Function (KDF).

In ENTRUST, each low-end device will be paired with a corresponding high-end, so as to offload the more resource consuming tasks (i.e., processing and relaying medical data to the backend system etc.) to the more powerful device. Assuming both device's have enrolled to the (same) Domain, the high-end will authenticate the low-end through the help of the DM. If successful, the DM will use a set of predefined challenges and calculated outputs of the low-end device's PUF, together with the expected and correct device state, as input to a KDF. The outputs of the KDF, which we will denote as one time use public keys PK_{OTS}^i (generated using challenge C_i), will be hashed and arranged to a binary Merkle tree, which we will denote as M , with the hash of each PK_{OTS}^i placed to a leaf node. The DM will send the root of the tree to the high-end device, together with each challenge C_i used to generate it. On the other hand, the DM will send to the low-end device only the leafs of M (i.e., the hashes of the one time public keys PK_{OTS}^i). The low-end device will use this construction to generate proofs that, given a challenge C_i (supplied by the high-end), they can generate on their own the corresponding leaf node of the Merkle-tree M . For the challenge C_i , this proof will consist of, the one time public key PK_{OTS}^i (used to generate the i_{th} leaf of the tree M), as well as the path leading from the i_{th} leaf node to the root of the tree (which is known by the high-end). Note that, to calculate that proof, the low-end needs to be in a correct state. Additionally, it needs to possess the correct PUF, otherwise it will not be able to calculate the expected PK_{OTS}^i , given the challenge C_i .

After successful enrolment to the Domain, each device will also receive a Conformity Certificate (CC) from the TAF, attesting to the device characteristics enabling its participation to the Domain infrastructure (security appraisals). Although only the high-end CMD will be able to use the privacy preserving properties of the issued CC (i.e., selective disclosure of attributes and unlinkable presentations), device binding is required for both high-end and low-end devices. In the case of the high-end device, the CC will be directly bound to the device's Root ID key, in a way that presenting that CC will require access to that key.

For low-end devices, the same procedure cannot be used, given its limited availability of cryptographic capabilities. In that case, the CC will be bound to keys generated by the device's PUF, by using a construction similar to the Merkle tree M described previously. In more detail, the TAF will select a set of challenges C_j and request from the DM the corresponding PUF outputs R_j , who on its turn, will request them from the device Manufacturer. The TAF will then calculate the one-time public keys PK_{OTS}^j , using the received R_j values, as well as the expected device state. Those values will then be used in constructing another binary Merkle tree M' , with the hash of each PK_{OTS}^j as a leaf node. The root of that tree will then be signed by the TAF, together with the security appraisals indicated by the Domain Manager, to generate in the Conformity Certificate CC. Finally, the TAF will return the created CC to the low-end device, along with the leaf nodes of M' (i.e., the hashes of the one time use public keys PK_{OTS}^j , corresponding to the challenge C_j).

Later, a Verifier can challenge the low-end to create a presentation of its CC using one of the challenges C_j . Given that challenge, the low-end will use its PUF to generate the one-time public key PK_{OTS}^j . It will then calculate a proof showcasing that PK_{OTS}^j does correspond to a leaf node of the tree M' , i.e., that there is a path leading from the hash of PK_{OTS}^j (acting as a leaf node), to the root of the tree M' , which is signed as part of the Certificate CC. The Verifier receiving CC, PK_{OTS}^j and the proof the low-end generated, will first validate the TAF's signature on the Certificate (note that this will also verify the integrity and authenticity of M' 's root), extract the root of the Merkle tree M' , hash the one-time public key PK_{OTS}^j to get one of the leaf nodes, and finally, validate the low-end's proof that there is a path leading from that leaf node to the root of the tree. If the above steps are successful, the CC presentation created by the low-end will be considered valid and the security appraisals it contains authentic. Note that the described protocol not only guarantees that the presentation was created by the indented low-end device, but also that the device was in the expected state during the presentation generation, since otherwise, the one-time password PK_{OTS}^j will have an incorrect value.

2.4.1 Secure Onboarding

Expanding on the high-level description of the onboarding and enrolment phases (put forth in Section 2.1), in what follows we provide the details of the cryptographic operations that take place at each step of the process. The CMD will authenticate with the Privacy CA and retrieve a set of attribute keys and a Verifiable Credential over its attributes. To be authenticated by the Domain Manager, the CMD will generate an Attestation key in the case of high-end CMDs (see Section 2.4.2). The CMD will then request the DM's policies hashes, based on which it's key restriction usage policies will be built. To finalise its domain enrolment, the device will prove ownership of the required attributes, by using Attribute Based Signcryption.

In ENTRUSTS's targeted use cases, a CMD will establish a secure and authenticated communication channel with other CMDs within a domain by using Attribute-Based Signatures and authenticated ephemeral symmetric encryption keys. On the other hand, communication with CMDs between domains will be secured with Attribute-Based Signcryption, as described in Section 5.1.2. To enforce the distinction between inner and outer domain communication, during enrolment to a Domain, the CMD, through the DM will retrieve from the Privacy CA an Attribute Key for the unique identifier of the domain it enrolled into. This key will permit the inclusion of the domain identifier as part of the Attribute-Based Signature

Figure 2.3: device Authorisation Flow

and Signcryption access policies. Note that the device will get access to that key, only in the case that it possesses the required attributes to be admitted in the Domain infrastructure. Only by showcasing that it successfully decrypted the correct domain identifier attribute key, will a high-end device be successfully enrolled.

In the rest of this section, we will examine the authentication of the device by the Privacy CA, with the support of the Manufacturer. Then, we will detail the device’s Domain enrolment procedure, making use of Attribute-Based Signatures, and utilizing the device’s VC and Attestation key. Note the details of the Attribute key creation is presented in Figure 2.4. The full description of the Attribute-based Based Signature and Signcryption protocols is presented in Chapter 5.

2.4.1.1 VC Issuance

To be authenticated and retrieve a VC over its attributes, the CMD will request a random challenge from the Privacy CA, which it will return signed by the Manufacturer. On its turn, the Manufacturer will only sign the challenge if the CMD can showcase possession of its Root ID Key.

To avoid impersonation attacks, each Verifiable Credential will be bound to a device specific key, in a way that only the device with that key will be able to use that VC. In the case of high-end devices, its Root ID Key (or any asymmetric key pair derived by that key) will be used for that purpose. Given that those keys are asymmetric, validation of the VC does not require the help of the Manufacturer, since the Verifier only needs to know the public part of the device’s VC binding key. In the case of low-end devices, the VC will be bound to the device’s symmetric Root ID Key, or any other key derived from it. However, since those keys are symmetric, validating the VC will require the help of the device Manufacturer. In both cases, we will denote with K_{VC} , the key that each device chooses to bind to their VC and with PK_{VC} , its public key

counterpart. Note that, in the case of a high-end device, where K_{VC} is asymmetric, then PK_{VC} is just the public part of that key pair. In the case of a low-end device, where K_{VC} is symmetric, PK_{VC} will be the digest of that key (i.e., $PK_{VC} = H(K_{VC})$).

The following steps outline the procedure with which the device (either a high-end or low-end) will be authenticated and receive a Verifiable Credential (see Figure 2.3).

- The CMD will initiate the authentication process by requesting a random challenge c from the Privacy CA.
- After retrieving c , the CMD will generate the key K_{VC} (either directly use its Root ID Key, or deterministically derive another key from it). Note the K_{VC} will either be an asymmetric key pair in the case of a high-end device, or just a symmetric key, in the case of a low-end device.
- The device will then initiate an authentication flow with the Manufacturer, including the returned random challenge c and the public counterpart of K_{VC} , PK_{VC} (either the public part of K_{VC} , in the case of a high-end device, or the hash of the K_{VC} , in case of a low-end).
- The Manufacturer will respond with a new random challenge c' . The CMD will then use its K_{VC} to sign the Manufacturer's challenge c' , as $sig_D = Sig(c||c', K_{VC})$. Note that, in the case the device is a high-end, Sig will be an asymmetric digital signature algorithm, like edDSA. The resulting signature in this case can be verified using only the public key PK_{VC} . On the other hand, if the device is a low-end, then Sig will be the *HMAC* algorithm, in which case the entire K_{VC} is needed for verification.
- After receiving sig_D , the Manufacturer will retrieve the key K_{VC} , PK_{VC} (depending the device) and attempt to verify the signature. If valid, the Manufacturer will sign the initial challenge c and the aforementioned supplied key PK_{VC} , to produce the signature $sig_M = Sign(c||PK_{VC}, sk_M)$, which they will return to the device.
- The device will return the key PK_{VC} and the signature sig_M to the Privacy CA, who will first check that they have not issued a VC bound to the received PK_{VC} before. If successful, they will attempt to verify sig_M over the challenge c and the PK_{VC} . If both signatures verify correctly, the Privacy CA will consider the device authenticated, and generate for it the Verifiable Credential (VC) and, in the case of a high-end device, the attribute keys SK_{Att} . See Figure 5.1, for details on the generation of those keys.

In the case of a high-end device, VC verification requires only the public key of the Privacy CA (note that the device's signature can be verified with just the public part of their asymmetric key K_{VC} , which is included on the credential). On the other hand, verification of a low-end device VC will require the help of the Manufacturer, as it requires knowledge of the key K_{VC} (given the symmetric nature of the signing algorithms used by the low-end device), which only the Manufacturer knows.

In ENTRUST, Verifiable Credentials play a role similar to Conformity Certificates, i.e., are used by external auditors to verify the device properties etc.. The main difference is that a CC contains Domain specific security appraisals for the device, while a VC contains device specific security properties, as attested by the Manufacturer. Additionally, VCs are used by the low-end device to attest their attributes (note that low-end devices don't have access to attribute based cryptographic capabilities).

2.4.2 High-End Device Enrollment

The Domain Manager (DM), upon receiving an enrolment request from the high-end device, authenticates the device based on its Root Key RK . The DM then generates a Domain ID for the device to be enrolled and sends this ID together with a domain key generation request to the Privacy CA. The Privacy CA is

Figure 2.4: Issuance of the Attribute Keys by the Privacy CA

the entity responsible for issuing the attribute keys, the device domain key which can be considered as an attribute key for the device should be bound to the other device’s attribute keys. The only entity that can do this binding is the Privacy CA since it can retrieve the seed r used to generate the attribute key and create the domain key from the same seed. Note that all the attribute keys are bound to the device’s Root Key to prevent sharing these keys among unauthorized devices. Upon successful issuance of the domain key from the Privacy CA, this key will be encrypted and sent to the DM. The DM then certifies this key and initiates an Attribute-based Signcryption, i.e. the DM first encrypts the domain key under a certain policy that allows the device to decrypt the message and retrieves the domain key only if it holds certain sets of attributes. The DM then creates an Attribute-based Signature on the generated cipher text (the encrypted domain key) under some of his attributes that satisfy a certain policy by DM. Finally, the DM sends the signcryption to the device. The device then verifies the DM signature and decrypts the cipher text as in Figure 2.5.

The device generates its Attestation Key AK: $f, F = g_1^f$ and sends it together with its public part of the Root Key to the DM. The DM then creates a shared symmetric key that is derived from the device Attestation key and domain key. The device then uses this key to create a symmetric signature \mathcal{T} and sends it to the DM. The DM upon successful verification of \mathcal{T} proceeds with creating the credential for the Trusted Component Attestation Key as in Figure 2.6. The DM wraps the credential and sends it to the Trusted Component through the device. The Trusted Component unwraps the credential. This Trusted Component operation is called “activate credential.” The device then verifies the credential, i.e., verifying that the signature provided on the Trusted Component public attestation key under the DM public key is valid. Finally, the device stores the credential and loads it whenever it needs to generate attestations.

Once the device is successfully enrolled with the DM where it certifies the created Attestation Key (AK), it is then directed to the TAF who verifies that the Trusted Component has a valid CA credential on the Trusted Component public key. If this verification is successful, the TAF then creates a Conformity Certificate (CC) that is stored as evidence of a secure enrolment process.

Figure 2.5: Enrolment Authentication for Edge devices based on AACKA[54]

Figure 2.6: Attestation Key Credential Issuance based on the enhanced privacy-CA solution (ePCAS) in [11]

2.4.3 Low-End Device Enrolment

For the case of a low-end device, enrolment to the Domain will be achieved through the use of the issued VC (in contrast to the attribute keys used by the high-end device, providing attribute privacy). More specifically, as outlined in Figure 2.7, the steps with which the low-end device will be enrolled to a Domain are the following:

- The low-end device will send a request to the DM, together with its PK_{VC} , as created in Section 2.4.2.1.
- The DM will respond with a random challenge c .
- The device will then sign the challenge c and their VC using their (symmetric) K_{VC} , to generate the signature $sig_D^{VC} = HMAC(VC || c, K_{VC})$. The device will respond with the VC and the signature sig_D^{VC} to the DM.
- After receiving the low-end device's response, the DM will forward the received signature, VC and challenge c to the Manufacturer.
- On its turn, the Manufacturer after receiving the -signature, challenge, VC- request from the DM, it will first retrieve the K_{VC} for that device based on its VC (recall, K_{VC} is either the low-end device's Root ID key, or another symmetric key derived from the Root id key). Then, the Manufacturer will check that the hash of the K_{VC} (i.e., the PK_{VC}) is included in the credential, and finally, will attempt to use K_{VC} to verify the received signature.
- If the signature is valid, the Manufacturer will return a success message on the DM, who, will then attempt to verify the Privacy CA's signature over the VC.
- If all the above steps are successful, the DM will check the attributes included in the VC to validate that the device satisfies their attribute policies, and as a result, is eligible to participate in the Domain.

Figure 2.7: Enrolment Authentication for low-end devices

Figure 2.8: Enrolment for Low-end devices

After successful enrolment, the DM will notify the TAF that a new low-end has been added to the infrastructure, providing it with the Attribute Appraisals to be included in the CC. The TAF will then select a set of challenges $\{C_i\}_{i \in [N]}$, for which it knows the output of the device's PUF $\{R_i\}_{i \in [N]}$, for some N . Each $\{R_i\}_{i \in [N]}$ will be passed through a KDF, together with the expected device state, to generate a set of keys $\{PK_{OTS}^i\}_{i \in [N]}$. The TAF will then generate a CC, bound to the set of those keys. The details are presented below:

- The Domain Manager DM chooses $N = 2^n$ predefined from the Manufacturer challenges C_1, \dots, C_N , where n is a security parameter.
- The DM sends the challenge set C_1, \dots, C_N to the manufacturer together with the PUF's ID.
- The Manufacturer with the knowledge of the PUF's outputs, creates the private keys R_i (using a key derivation function KDF) that are the responses to the challenges $C_i \forall i \in [0, N - 1]$.
- The Manufacturer creates a set of OTS keys. With input $R_i = SK_{OTS}^i$ and the *expected correct state* of the low-end device, the OTS-KEYGEN algorithm generates the corresponding one-time public key PK_{OTS}^i .
- The manufacturer then sends all PK_{OTS}^i to the DM who creates the Merkle tree as described in Chapter 5 where the root node represents the PUF master public key mpk .
- The DM forwards mpk , a set of attributes (Attribute Appraisals), and device ID to the TAF to create a Conformity Certificate CC for the low-end device.

- The creation of the Conformity Certificates CC for the low-end device is done by the TAF. The CC is a signature done by TAF using the first element x from the TAF's signing key $sk = (x, y_1, \dots, y_{k+1})$, used in the p-ABC scheme introduced in Chapter 2. TAF's signature is done on the root public key mpk , the device Attribute Appraisals, and the device ID. The Conformity Certificates is constructed follows:

$$CC = H_1(mpk, \text{Attribute Appraisals}, ID)^x$$

where H_1 is hash function defined as $H_1 : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{G}_1$.

- The TAF sends the CC together with the Attribute Appraisals defined for the device to the DM who verifies the TAF signature under the corresponding TAF public key g_2^x .
- The DM checks: $e(H_1(mpk, \text{Attribute Appraisals}, ID), g_2^x) \stackrel{?}{=} e(CC, g_2)$. If successful, the DM sends $(CC, mpk, \text{Attribute Appraisals})$ to the low-end device as a reference of a successful enrolment. DM publishes mpk . Note that every time a Merkle tree is created, a new CC should be issued by TAF.
- Each related high-end device receives a subset the challenges C_i to keep in their records to generate one-time signatures based on the PUF's responses $R_i \forall i \in [0, N - 1]$.

Figure 2.9: Conformity Certificates for Low-end devices

2.5 Cryptographic Operations for Runtime Operational Assurance

Towards providing operational assurance guarantees through the entire lifecycle of a device, ENTRUST leverages novel remote, runtime behavioral attestation services, targeting both the software and hardware layers and covering all phases of a device's execution.

2.5.1 High-End Trust Assessment Process

The high-end devices that are successfully enrolled in the ENTRUST services (i.e, have certified attribute keys as well as certified attestation keys issued during the onboarding and the enrolment phases described before) can now provide attestation evidence as well as creating Attribute-based signatures / signcryptions. To start the trust assessment process, the Verifier (which can be any device in the ENTRUST framework) initiates a remote trust assessment process based on a certain defined policy. The Verifier sends a fresh challenge ch with a policy \mathcal{P} requesting a piece of evidence that proves that a targeted device (Signer) is behaving as expected and possesses a certain set of attributes without disclosing the actual value of these attributes. In other words, the Signer is requested to issue a verifiable presentation proving that; it possesses a set of certified attributes that satisfy a signer policy \mathcal{P} without revealing the device's attributes and that it is in a correct state (where with state we denote a predefined

set of static or run time attributes). The Signer, with the help of its embedded Trusted Component (Verifiable Policy Enforcer (VPE)), reports the attestation data which includes static/ run-time configuration. The corresponding device OP-TEE then uses its attestation key $AK = (f, F)$ to create a signature over the received challenge ch . This signature can be a conventional signature σ or a Direct Anonymous Attestation (DAA) σ_{DAA} if user privacy is needed (note that in both cases, the public part of the attestation key will be certified by the Domain Manager). Note that during the issuance of the Attestation Key (AK), a key policy is enforced that restricts the usage of this key only if the device's current configuration matches the expected *Golden* one that was identified in the device's MUD profile. As a result, a valid signature generated from the key AK, indicates the correct configuration of the device.

The device is then required to generate a Verifiable Presentation (VP) using its certified attribute keys. If the Verifier and the Signer belong to the same domain, an ABS is created by the signer otherwise, an ABSC is required (i.e. generating a cipher text that is an encryption of the attestation data, then creating ABS on the cipher text). The Signer creates an ABS/ ABSC, using its attribute keys issued by the Privacy CA in the enrolment phase. Note that these keys are bound to the Root Key ($rsk = x, rpki$) of the device. The device then uses the secret part of its Root Key $rsk = x$ to generate the signature. The signature cannot be generated successfully without the knowledge of x . This prevents collusion attacks since sharing attribute keys is infeasible in our scheme. In ABSC, the signer further encrypts the attestation data based on the decryptors policy \mathcal{P}' that allows the decryptor to retrieve the original data if it has a set of attributes that satisfies \mathcal{P}' . The attribute anonymity is preserved in our schemes by committing the attribute and then signing them using Schnorr-type signatures. The details of the scheme are presented in Section 5.6.

Note that, other than ABS/ABSC, the high-end can also use its Conformity Certificate (see Section 2.9) for the purpose of establishing trust with other entities in the ENTRUST infrastructure, based on the appraisals made by the DM for the device. In ENTRUST, we provide cryptographic agility by supporting both capabilities, with the intention of benchmarking and evaluating them in the basis of performance and scalability.

2.5.2 Low-End Trust Assessment Process

Unlike high-end devices, low-end devices can only generate symmetric signatures that use the PUF response R as a signing key. Note that to verify a symmetric signature, an external Verifier needs to the PUF's response R , known only by the device Manufacturer.

Based on this construction, we propose using the Merkle signature that allows certifying a bunch of one-time public keys by the manufacturer and then using each key once during the trust assertion processes of the low0end device. This approach solves the problem of returning every time to the manufacturer to prove the construction of the PUF challenge responses.

In contrast to high-end devices, a low-end device will not be able to use the selective disclosure or privacy preserving presentation of a Conformity Certificate CC. In practice, this means that any Verifier receiving a CC from the low-end device, will get access to the entirety of information included in that certificate. Additionally, they will be able to infer if they have previously interacted with the specific device. On the other hand, using the Merle-tree construction presented in Section 2.4, we are able to guarantee device binding of Conformity Certificates, i.e., that only the indented device will be able to use an issued CC, while in a correct configuration.

To create a presentation of its Conformity Certificate during runtime, the low-end device will use its PUF to generate a one time key, bound to its configuration (secure boot etc.,) and then prove that there is a cryptographic relationship between the issued CC and that key. More specifically, lets assume an entity (which we will denote as a Verifier) that wants to validate the security appraisals made by the DM,

allowing the low-end device to participate in the Domain. After receiving the Verifier's request, the device will respond with its unique identity, which the Verifier, assuming it is the first time interacting with this device, will use to request from the DM the root of the binary Merkle tree mpk , (constructed by the TAF, as described in Section 2.4.4), which is bound to the Conformity Certificate CC , as well as the set of challenges C_1, C_2, \dots, C_N used to generate it. Then, the Verifier will request the presentation of a CC by the low-end device, supplying it with one of the challenges, C_i .

After receiving the challenge, the device will use its PUF and its current state to generate a one time use public key PK_{OTS}^i . It will then generate a proof that there is a path from the hash of that one time public key (PK_{OTS}^i) to the root of the Merkle tree (mpk), which is signed in the certificate CC . Note that the constructed proof will be valid only if the current state of the device (used to generate to one time public key PK_{OTS}^i) is correct, as defined by the Manufacturer.

The device will respond to the Verifier's challenge with its Conformity Certificate CC , the one time public key PK_{OTS}^i and the generated proof. The Verifier will validate the TAF's signature over CC , extract from it the Merkle tree root mpk , and use it, together with the one time public key PK_{OTS}^i , to validate the proof supplied by the device. If all checks are successful, the certificate and the device will be considered validated and the Verifier will delete the used challenge from its pool.

Note that, in order to guarantee freshness of a CC presentation, i.e., that the device will not be able to re-use one of the one time use public keys with the same or different Verifiers, it is necessary that the DM will supply disjoint pools of challenges to all parties that want to verify a Conformity Certificate of a low-end device. Since each Verifier will delete the challenge after it is used, this means that the device will always receive a C_i that it hasn't seen before, forcing it to generate a new one time use public key PK_{OTS}^i every time it wants to present its Conformity Certificate.

Even though the Conformity Certificate will provide Domain specific security appraisals made by the TAF, device specific security attributes attested by the Manufacturer are included in its Verifiable Credential (VC). Recall that the VC is bound to the device's root id key, which, in the case of low-end devices, is a symmetric cryptographic key. This means that only the Manufacturer will be able to validate a presentation of a low-end device Verifiable Credential.

Consider a Verifier (e.g., a DM, an external auditor etc.,) that requires a assessment of the device's configuration and attributes (rather than the security appraisals created by the TAF). The Verifier will ping the low-end device with a fresh (randomly chosen) challenge ch . The device will generate a cryptographic key AK bound to its current configuration, using its Root ID key. It will then use that key to sign (using the *HMAC* cryptographic algorithm) the Verifier's challenge ch and its Verifiable Credential, producing the signature sig . The low-end will respond with the signature sig and its VC to the Verifier, who, on its turn, will forward them together with the initial challenge ch to the Manufacturer of the device. The Manufacturer will then use the device's Root ID Key and expected configuration, to re-construct the key AK used by the device to sign the Verifier's challenge and it's VC. If successful, it will use that key to validate the received signature sig , over the challenge ch and the device's VC. Assuming the signature is valid and the hash of the device's Root ID Key is included in the VC, the Manufacturer will return a success message to the Verifier, who will then attempt to validate the Privacy CA's signature on the VC. If all checks are successful, the VC will be considered verified.

Note that, similar to the case of Conformity Certificates, verification is bound to the device's configuration. More specifically, for the Manufacturer to validate the signature sig generated by the low-end device, it is necessary to correctly reconstruct the key AK . Since that key is reconstructed using the expected device configuration, it is necessary for the device to be in that correct, "golden", configuration during the trust assessment process.

Chapter 3

ENTRUST Core Crypto Structures and Primitives

This chapter focuses on the core cryptographic structures and primitives required for the protocols and mechanisms designed in the context of ENTRUST, supporting the dynamic trust assessment of CMDs throughout the entire lifecycle. In the following sections, an overview of the main cryptographic building blocks utilized to construct the schemes reported in Chapter 5 will be presented, capturing the ENTRUST-identified security requirements highlighted below.

As explained in the previous Chapter 2, to enable the creation and sharing of trustworthiness evidence in a verifiable manner, ENTRUST has developed a set of secure and efficient cryptographic protocols that support the generation of Verifiable Credentials (VCs), where a set of certified attributes are issued by an authority. Based on the issued (VCs), a device can then create Verifiable Presentations (VPs) to demonstrate that a certain security policy, denoted as \mathcal{P} , is satisfied. These presentations take the form of Attribute-based Signatures (ABS) if the verifier and the prover device belong to the same domain or Attribute-based SignCryption (ABSC), in case they belong to different domains. To prove an enrolment into a specific ENTRUST domain, each domain is treated as a standalone attribute where each high-end device gets its corresponding key, called the Domain Key and denoted by DK_E , upon a successful domain enrolment. Therefore, the verifier can set the security policy considering a specific domain as an attribute. Then, upon a prover's (signer) request for a VP creation, it checks whether the corresponding domain attribute key exists. In case high-end CMD possesses such a key, ABS is utilized to satisfy the security policy \mathcal{P} , whereas ABSC is employed otherwise. An important distinction that needs to be made is: The ABS scheme does not provide attribute anonymity while the ABSC scheme does. So, when facilitating CMD communication within the same medical domain, where the anonymity of attributes is not a privacy requirement, the ABS scheme is used. On the other hand, in the case of different medical domains (e.g. different hospitals), where a CMD or a whole domain must prove their trust level without disclosing their specific trust properties (thus, possibly leading to implementation disclosure attacks), the ABSC scheme is used. Every time that a VP is created by the device, ENTRUST's Trust Assessment Framework (TAF) [20] generates a temporal Conformity Certificate, denoting a successful VP about a certain set of attributes. The Conformity Certificate supports the privacy of the CMD utilizing the p-ABC scheme, by selectively disclosing, through zero-knowledge proofs, the information in the VC according to a specific policy. Finally, we note that while the p-ABC and ABSC schemes achieve similar security and privacy requirements, the former is more appropriate for capturing the properties of a Conformity Certificate because it provides a well-defined crypto structure that can easily be converted to a CC and inspected by an external auditor. However, ABSC's endmost goal is to be efficient and thus, it doesn't have a structure that allows to be encoded as a CC.

The *newly designed* ENTRUST's ABS and ABSC schemes are built based on the ABE protocol (FABEO). FABEO leverages the Linear Secret Sharing Scheme (LSSS) matrix technique to convert an access tree to a policy matrix, leading to a more efficient construction of the Attribute-Based Encryption protocol, whereas the Lewko-Waters Algorithm describes the creation of such a matrix. It has to be noted that **the abovementioned schemes will be adopted by ENTRUST's high-end CMDs**, whereas **for their low-end counterparts**, a different approach has to be followed given their limited capacity to perform advanced cryptographic operations. For the latter family of CMDs, **a symmetric construction based on the Merkle tree signatures is proposed**.

This chapter is structured as follows. In Section 3.1 the ENTRUST's security requirements are presented, supporting the secure lifecycle management of a ENTRUST TCB-enabled CMD in the entire service graph chain. Then, in order to provide all the prerequisites for the creation of the ABS and ABSC schemes built to support the high-end devices considered here, the Lewko-Waters Algorithm is presented in Section 3.2, whereas the FABEO ABE protocol is described in Section 3.3.1. The high-level description of the ABS and ABSC is presented in Sections 3.4 and 3.5 respectively, followed by the ABC scheme in Section 3.6. An introduction to the Direct Anonymous Attestation concept is provided in Section 3.7, whereas the Merkle tree signatures-based approach considered here for the low-end CMDs is presented in Section 3.8.

3.1 ENTRUST Security Requirements

In Table 2.3 the main security requirements for the secure lifecycle management of an ENTRUST TCB-enabled CMD are presented. Three phases enable this procedure, namely: **1)** preparing a CMD for trust assessment, **2)** allowing a CMD to assess its trust, and **3)** re-establishing trust in case of a failed attestation. For the realization of each one of those phases, the corresponding security requirements have to be designed.

The preparation phase mandates secure enrollment processes, establishing cryptographic keys, and defining key restriction usage policies tailored to mitigate identified threats. Selective disclosure capabilities ensure that CMDs can reveal only necessary attributes during trust assessment, preserving user privacy and thwarting unauthorized access attempts. Additionally, the integrity of CMDs is ensured through mechanisms such as device root key binding, which binds credentials and attributes to individual devices, thus preventing credential misuse and collusion. Continuous authentication and authorization mechanisms, supported by attribute-based access control and Conformity Certificates, further safeguard CMDs against unauthorized access attempts. These comprehensive security measures not only ensure the integrity and confidentiality of CMD operations but also enable swift response and recovery in the event of security breaches, ensuring the reliability and trustworthiness of the entire ecosystem by the re-establishment of trustworthiness. With security requirements such as these, we ensure a strong foundation for designing secure attestation mechanisms using cryptographic schemes discussed in Chapter 5. These mechanisms guarantee the main goal of ENTRUST, namely the secure lifecycle management of CMDs.

The security requirements that are defined in this Section must be met by the designed cryptographic protocols and will be used as a base for the first (high-level) qualitative security analysis that is presented in Section 5.7. But, the detailed mathematical security proofs of the schemes will be part of D4.3.

Table 3.1: Security Requirements

Security Requirement	Description
Unforgeability	It should not be possible for any adversary to construct a forgery VC that will be accepted by a Verifier. The unforgeability of the Conformity Certificates and their presentation token is reduced to the Unforgeability of the p-ABC scheme that is built from the PS signatures. For low-end devices, the unforgeability of VCs is reduced to the unforgeability of the underlying signature scheme. The unforgeability of the VPs means that no adversary without the knowledge of the attribute keys, can create a valid Attribute-based signature that satisfies a certain policy. The unforgeability of our ABS scheme is reduced to the DL hard problem.
Selective Disclosure	VPs should constitute collections of claims that the high-end device can construct a VP showing that it acquires the needed attributes that satisfy a certain policy without revealing further information about the attribute values. This is achieved by our ABS, ABSC schemes presented in 5.6 that provide perfect attribute anonymity. Disclosure of information in CCs should be limited to the minimal information to fulfil a required policy, e.g. disclosing the achievement of appraisals like device integrity but no further information on other appraisals like resilience. This is achieved by p-ABCs in the case of high-end devices, while low-end devices will forgo this requirement because of the efficiency needs imposed by their constrained nature.
Integrity	It must be ensured that only authenticated and non-compromised high and low-end devices can access the attestation keys of their TCs for creating successful attestations. This definition ensures that a Verifier will accept a presented claim <i>if and only if</i> the device can provide verifiable evidence that its integrity has not been altered (from the time of credential issuance) in an unauthenticated manner. This necessitates the enforcement of key restriction usage policies for governing credential management, leveraging a TC's policy-based safeguards for the high-end devices as in Section 2.4.2. The integrity of the low-end devices is achieved by binding the generation of the one-time public keys PK_{OTS} , which represent the leaf nodes of the Merkle tree, to the correct state of the device as described in Section 5.4.1.
Preparing For Trust-Assessment	As in ENTRUST we need to enable dynamic Trust-Assessment for a single and multiple devices at once. To achieve this, each device in order to participate in the ENTRUST ecosystem has to undergo the Secure Enrollment module in order to set up their cryptographic keys and of course their corresponding key restriction usage policies that covers the defined threat model.
Re-establishing Trustworthiness	As each device handles data of immense sensitivity to eliminate dynamically any discovered vulnerabilities, thus minimising the attack surface of the respective device. Such actions lead require software and firmware updates, that will affect the configuration of the device. To avoid forcing the device to undergo once more, in ENTRUST we need to employ mechanisms that enables the Key Restriction Usage Policy verifiability and as an extension the verification that no obsolete software/firmware version resides within the device.
Device Root Key Binding	Issued VCs should be <i>bound</i> to the TC key embedded in the device. No device should be able to use or show this credential without proof of possession of this unique key. This definition further ensures the issuance of the attribute keys <i>bound</i> to the device's TC root key so that no other device shares these attribute keys. This also prevents collusion attacks where devices can share their attribute keys to perform a single ABS. The showing of CCs will also require the proof of possession of the unique key of the device. For the low-end device, the root key binding is achieved by the response uniqueness, described in Chapter 4, for every PUF based on the Root identity key. The Key generation algorithm takes the PUF responses R_i for generating the one-time public keys PK_{OTS} , this binds the one-time keys to the PUF root key.
Confidentiality	ENTRUST supports ABE which is part of the ABSC protocol which is used to ensure legitimate attribute-based access control to sensitive encrypted data.

Security Requirements (Continued)

Security Requirement	Description
User Privacy	Fundamental for the ENTRUST crypto primitives is to preserve the privacy of each user. User privacy is achieved by providing guarantees, that data cannot uniquely identify an individual. Importantly, user privacy is ensured not by masking their identity, but by making their activity private. For ENTRUST, we are planning to employ Direct-Anonymous-Attestation and other sophisticated crypto schemes in order to meet such requirements.
Revocation	ENTRUST will design a revocation protocol that enables the successful deactivation of a misbehaving device's credentials with/without disclosing its attributes. The device to be revoked should be successfully enrolled with the Privacy CA and the Domain Manager (DM). Additionally, Conformity Certificates should be revoked when the associated trust appraisals are no longer relevant, so that verifiers do not accept outdated trust appraisals.
Continuous authentication and authorization	Attribute-based Access Control is performed as a chain code after receiving the verifiable credentials including the list of attributes that are required for getting access to this specific service or information. The issuance of Verifiable Presentations (VPs) is protected through the use of hardware-based keys (Root identity Keys) for binding the VPs to the specific device and the set of required attributes. This, in turn, allows for continuous authentication, authorization, and access control based on such protected VPs which embody security claims as attributes.
Traces integrity	This is enabled by the underlying medical device supporting the integrity of a produced attestation report (based on authentic traces monitored on the device side) by providing the appropriate (and policy-protected) Attestation Key (AK) used for signing, as described in Section 2.4.2. The Attestation Key is securely created during the device Enrolment phase and is binded to the correct state of the device meaning that it can only be used when the device configuration has not been altered. The respective AK is used for signing the traces (attestation raw data) sent to the Verifier before being recorded on the ledger.

3.2 The Lewko-Waters Algorithm

In ENTRUST, we want to be able to support the attribute-based cryptographic operations that enable the secure lifecycle management of CMDs. The attribute combinations that an ENTRUST entity must satisfy in order to perform an operation are called policies and are represented by tree-based structures called access-control trees. The Lewko-Waters Algorithm is used for the transformation of an access control tree to an access control matrix for easier mathematical manipulation in our ABS and ABSC schemes. The input of the algorithm is an access tree, which represents a monotone boolean formula. The tree's non-leaf nodes are AND and OR gates and leaf nodes are attributes. The output of the algorithm is the corresponding Linear Secret Sharing Scheme (LSSS) matrix, whose size (i.e. the number of rows) is equal to the number of leaf nodes of the input access tree. The Lewko-Waters algorithm takes the access tree representation of this transformed boolean formula as input, then labels the root node of the tree with a vector of a single entity 1, and initializes a global counter c to 1. Then it goes down the tree and labels the nodes as follows:

1. If the parent node is an OR gate labeled with a vector \vec{v} , the algorithm labels both child nodes as \vec{v} and keeps the counter c unchanged;
2. If the parent node is an AND gate labeled with a vector \vec{v} , the algorithm pads \vec{v} with 0's at the end (if necessary) to make it of length c , then the algorithm labels its right child node with the vector $(\vec{v}||1)$ and the left child node with the vector $(0, \dots, 0||-1)$, where $(0, \dots, 0)$ is of length c , and increases the value of c by 1.
3. Once the algorithm finishes labeling the tree, the vectors labeled on the leaf nodes constitute the rows of an LSSS matrix, and if the vectors have different lengths, the algorithm pads the shorter

ones with 0's at the end until all the them are of the same length. Note that a set of the rows of the resulting matrix includes $(1, 0, \dots, 0)$ in its span if and only if the attributes corresponding to the rows in the set satisfy the input access tree.

For instance consider the following example in Figure 3.2 taken from [39].

Figure 3.1: Example

The policy can be translated to the following Boolean formula with only OR/ AND gates: $E \wedge ((A \wedge B) \vee (A \wedge C) \vee (A \wedge D) \vee (B \wedge C) \vee (B \wedge D) \vee (C \wedge D))$.

3.2.1 LSSS Matrix

We explain the steps of this transformation from an access tree to an LSSS matrix:

Figure 3.2: LSSS Matrix transformation

If we define $\pi : [1, 9] \rightarrow \{E, A, B, C, D\}$. $\forall i [1, 9]$, the rows of the matrix are $\pi(i) \in \{E, A, B, C, D, A, B, C, D\}$,

that corresponds to the leaf nodes of the access tree, as follows:

$$\begin{array}{l} \pi(1) = E \\ \pi(2) = A \\ \pi(3) = B \\ \pi(4) = C \\ \pi(5) = D \\ \pi(6) = A \\ \pi(7) = B \\ \pi(8) = C \\ \pi(9) = D \end{array} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

We encode an access structure by a policy (\mathbf{M}, π) , where $\mathbf{M} \in \mathbb{Z}_p^{n_1 \times n_2}$ and $\pi : [1, n_1] \rightarrow \mathcal{U}$ for some universal attribute set \mathcal{U} . Every row M_i in the matrix \mathbf{M} corresponds to an input to an attribute and the number of columns of \mathbf{M} is the same as the number of (AND) gates +1. If the mapping π is not injective, then define $\rho(i) : |\{z, \pi(i) = \pi(z) \text{ with } z \leq i \text{ to denote the } \rho(i) - \text{th occurrence of attribute } \pi(i)\}$. For instance, in the above example $\rho(1) = \rho(2) = \rho(3) = \rho(4) = \rho(5) = 1$, while $\rho(6) = \rho(7) = \rho(8) = \rho(9) = 2$.

Let $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$ be a set of attributes and $\mathcal{I} : \{i \in [1, n_1] \text{ such that } \pi(i) \in \mathcal{S}\}$ be the indices of rows in \mathbf{M} that are associated with \mathcal{S} .

(\mathbf{M}, π) accepts \mathcal{S} if the vector $(1, 0, \dots, 0)$ lies in the span of rows associated with \mathcal{S} . This means, there exist constants $\gamma_i \in \mathbb{Z}_p$ for $i \in \mathcal{I}$ such that $\sum \gamma_i M_i = (1, 0, \dots, 0) \in \mathbb{Z}_p^{n_2}$. On the contrary, (\mathbf{M}, π) does not accept \mathcal{S} if there exists a vector $\vec{w} \in \mathbb{Z}_p^{n_2}$ such that \vec{w} is orthogonal to all rows M_i for $\pi(i) \in \mathcal{S}$, but not to $(1, 0, \dots, 0)$.

For instance, let $\mathcal{S} = \{E, A, C\}$, then \mathcal{S} satisfies the the LSSS matrix since we define $\mathcal{I} = \{1, 2, 4, 6, 8\}$ that includes the indices of rows in \mathbf{M} that are associated with \mathcal{S} defined by the matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

We have $\pi(1) + p\pi(2) + p\pi(4) + \pi(6) + \pi(8) = (1, 0, 0, 0, 0) \pmod{p}$. If $\mathcal{S} = \{A, B, D\}$ then to prove that \mathcal{S} doesn't satisfy the policy, we construct a non-zero vector $\vec{w} = (1, -1, 0, 0, 0)$ that is orthogonal to every row in the following matrix and not orthogonal to $(1, 0, 0, 0, 0)$:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

3.2.2 ENTRUST Use Case LSSS Matrix Example

In this subsection we will present an example of the usage of the LSSS matrix. As a starting point, we consider a device which must satisfy the security requirement of integrity. During onboarding, the device was equipped with the appropriate credentials that represent it's system properties. To prove it's integrity, it should satisfy the requirement of bootstrap integrity (by disclosing the secure boot attribute) and runtime

integrity (by disclosing a set of attributes that prove so). Considering the domain’s privacy requirements, this CMD should prove that it satisfies this policy without disclosing the combination of attributes that make this possible.

To make this clear we consider this example: A device should have the following system attributes: Secure Boot and two of the following four attributes {Authenticated Tracer, Certified Trusted Computing base, Key Restriction Usage Policy, Verifiable Policy Enforcer }. A device that has Secure Boot, Verifiable Policy Enforcer, and Key Restriction Usage Policy satisfies the policy. However, a device having Certified Trusted Computing base, Key Restriction Usage Policy and Verifiable Policy Enforcer doesn’t satisfy the above policy.

The defined policy can be translated to the following Boolean formula with only OR/ AND gates:

$$\text{Secure Boot} \wedge ((\text{Authenticated Tracer} \wedge \text{Certified Trusted Computing base}) \vee (\text{Authenticated Tracer} \wedge \text{Key Restriction Usage Policy}) \vee (\text{Authenticated Tracer} \wedge \text{Verifiable Policy Enforcer}) \vee (\text{Certified Trusted Computing base} \wedge \text{Key Restriction Usage Policy}) \vee (\text{Certified Trusted Computing base} \wedge \text{Verifiable Policy Enforcer}) \vee (\text{Key Restriction Usage Policy} \wedge \text{Verifiable Policy Enforcer})).$$

Figure 3.3: ENTRUST Use-case example

Figure 3.3 represents the binary tree for the access control policy, the tree has 9 leaf nodes. We define the following function that maps each leaf node to the corresponding attribute that it holds

$$\pi : [1, 9] \rightarrow \mathcal{U}$$

Where \mathcal{U} is the *Universal* attribute set defined by the following attributes:

{Secure Boot, Authenticated Tracer, Certified Trusted Computing base, Key Restriction Usage Policy, Verifiable Policy Enforcer}.

The function π is defined on each node as in the access tree starting from left to right:

- $\pi(1)$ =Secure Boot
- $\pi(2)$ =Authenticated Tracer
- $\pi(3)$ =Certified Trusted Computing base
- $\pi(4)$ =Key Restriction Usage Policy
- $\pi(5)$ =Verifiable Policy Enforcer
- $\pi(6)$ =Authenticated Tracer
- $\pi(7)$ =Certified Trusted Computing base
- $\pi(8)$ =Key Restriction Usage Policy
- $\pi(9)$ =Verifiable Policy Enforcer

We construct the LSSS matrix \mathbf{M} that consists of nine rows and has the number of (AND) gates +1 columns which is 5 in our example. The transformation from an access tree to an LSSS policy matrix is explained before. The LSSS matrix \mathbf{M} that corresponds to the access tree example is defined as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Suppose that an ENTRUST device has a set \mathcal{S} of attributes with their corresponding attribute keys issued by the CA. Consider $\mathcal{S} = \{\text{Secure Boot, Authenticated Tracer, Key Restriction Usage Policy}\}$, then \mathcal{S} satisfies the LSSS policy matrix since the set of indices in \mathbf{M} that corresponds to the attributes in \mathcal{S} is defined by $\mathcal{I} = \{1, 2, 4, 6, 8\}$ defined by the sub-matrix that includes the 5 rows of \mathbf{M} with indices in \mathcal{I} :

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

We have $\pi(1) + p\pi(2) + p\pi(4) + \pi(6) + \pi(8) = (1, 0, 0, 0, 0) \pmod p$, there for the device satisfies the policy defined in \mathbf{M} . The device can then use its attribute keys to create a valid ABS or ABSC under the policy defined in \mathbf{M} .

If $\mathcal{S} = \{\text{Authenticated Tracer, Certified Trusted Computing base, Verifiable Policy Enforcer}\}$ then to prove that \mathcal{S} doesn't satisfy the policy, we construct a non-zero vector $\vec{w} = (1, -1, 0, 0, 0)$ that is orthogonal to every row in the following sub-matrix and not orthogonal to $(1, 0, 0, 0, 0)$ in as discussed in Section 3.2, where the sub-matrix that corresponds to \mathcal{S} is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

In this case, an ENTRUST device holding the set of attributes in \mathcal{S} fails to create a valid ABS or ABSC since it doesn't satisfy the policy defined in \mathbf{M} .

3.3 Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE)

Attribute-based encryption (ABE) enables fine-grained access control on encrypted data and has a large number of practical applications. ENTRUST will adopt an Attribute-Based Encryption mechanism that involves techniques of issuing keys that are bound to the devices' attributes. These keys are called attribute keys. Attribute keys consist of public (encryption keys) and private (decryption keys) portions. In the ENTRUST framework, some information should only be shared within a subgroup of supply chain stakeholders. For instance, consider the case of some sensitive medical data that should be accessible by only a specific subset of municipality official bodies. Towards this direction, ENTRUST should provide desirable support for Attribute-based Encryption (ABE). In this case, any requested entity will be able to have access to the (encrypted) data but only those that can produce the necessary attributes should be able to decrypt the encrypted data. There are two types of ABE defined, i.e. ciphertext-policy attribute-based encryption (CP-ABE) and key-policy attribute-based encryption (KP-ABE). In CP-ABE, a user encrypts the data according to a predicate (access policy) defined over attributes, such that only the party that possesses a secret key associated with the attribute set satisfying the predicate can decrypt the ciphertext. In KP-ABE, the idea is reversed. Here the ciphertext is associated with the attribute set and the secret key is associated with the predicate defined over the attributes. ENTRUST will adopt the FABEO KP-ABE scheme [52], pairing-based KP-ABE achieving the following properties:

- Support expressive policies described by the boolean formula and Monotone Span Programs (MSP).
- Put no restriction on the size of policies or attribute sets.
- Allow any arbitrary string such as patient names and hospitals, safety and integrity definitions to be used as an attribute.
- Achieve a strong and natural notion of adaptive security,

FABEO uses asymmetric (Type-III) prime-order bilinear groups $(\mathbb{G}_1, \mathbb{G}_2, \mathbb{G}_T)$ which support efficient hashing to \mathbb{G}_1 . Ciphertexts and secret keys in FABEO comprises mostly of elements in the smaller and faster group \mathbb{G}_1 , plus 1 or 2 elements in \mathbb{G}_2 . Computation for key generation, encryption, and decryption is mostly carried out in \mathbb{G}_1 , with 2 to 3 pairings for decryption.

3.3.1 FABEO KP-Attribute-Based Encryption Protocol

We summarise FABEO KP-ABE presented in [52] that constitutes the main building block for our ABS and ABSC schemes described in Chapter 5.

- **Setup**(1^λ): Given a security parameter λ , it picks a secret key $\alpha \in \mathbb{Z}_p$ and a hash function $H : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{G}_1$. Define the public parameters $pp : \{\mathbb{G}_1, \mathbb{G}_2, \mathbb{G}_T, g_1, g_2, e, H\}$. Output the master public key $(e(g_1, g_2)^\alpha, pp)$ and the master secret key α .
- **KeyGen**($m_{sk}, (\mathbf{M}, \pi)$): The KGC Picks up a random $\vec{r} \leftarrow \mathbb{Z}_p^\tau$ and $\vec{v} \leftarrow \mathbb{Z}_p^{n_2-1}$. Compute $sk_{1,j} = g_2^{\vec{r}[j]}$ where $j \in [1, \tau]$ and τ represents the maximum number of times an attribute is used in \mathbf{M} . $sk_{2,i} = g_1^{\mathbf{M}_i(\alpha \parallel \vec{v})^T \cdot H(\pi(i))^{\vec{r}[\rho(i)]}}$ for each row $i \in [1, n_1]$. $sk = (sk_{1,j}, sk_{2,i}) \forall j \in [1, \tau]$ and $i \in [1, n_1]$.
- **ENC**($mpk, \mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$): Pick $s \leftarrow \mathbb{Z}_p$, for each attribute $u \in \mathcal{S}$, calculate the cyphertexts: $ct_{1,u} = H(u)^s$ and $ct_2 = g_2^s$. Output $CT = \{ct_{1,u}, ct_2\}$ and $d = e(g_1, g_2)^{\alpha s}$.
- **DEC**($mpk, \mathcal{S}, (\mathbf{M}, \pi), CT, sk$): If \mathcal{S} satisfies (\mathbf{M}, π) , then there exists $\gamma_i \forall i \in I$, where $I \subseteq [1, n_1]$ is the set of indices of the rows in \mathbf{M} that are associated with \mathcal{S} , such that $\sum_{i \in I} \gamma_i \mathbf{M}_i = (\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{0}, \dots, \mathbf{0})$. Calculates d as follows:

$$d = \frac{e(\prod_{i \in I} (sk_{2,i})^{\gamma_i}, ct_2)}{\prod_{j \in \tau} e(\prod_{i \in I, \rho(i)=j} (ct_{1,\pi(i)})^{\gamma_i}, sk_{1,j})}$$

3.4 Attribute-Based signature (ABS)

An attribute-based signature (ABS) scheme was first proposed by [42]. The basic idea of an ABS scheme is to demonstrate that a user's attributes satisfy some predicate (policy) that signs the message. ABS can be categorized into two distinct strains, centralized and decentralized schemes. In either case, the scheme can take on numerous forms, such as multi-authority ABS, revocable ABS, and schemes with the user-controlled likability of signatures. Moreover, consider many applications of ABS, such as attribute-based messaging [42] and attribute-based authentication [6].

The authors of [47] systematically surveyed ABS systems up to 2022. Details provided in the survey include concrete constructions, extensions, and a thorough comparison of related work concerning performance, functionality, security notions, and open problems. We will provide an updated overview of key ABS properties in the proceeding. The ABS scheme in ENTRUST is used for the selective disclosure of a CMD's attribute subset to a verifier in the same domain.

Security The key security requirements of ABS include but are not limited to anonymity of the signer, privacy, and unforgeability of the signature. Further properties include the traceability [31, 34, 18, 26] of the scheme to extract a signer's ID if needed. Stronger security notions include the concept of non-frameability [24, 23] regarding signature keys. Specifically, attribute authorities (AA) are prevented from colluding or producing a sign key forgery assigned to a signer.

Policies The expressiveness of a given policy is important to capture statements concerning a user's attributes. The seminal work of Maji [42] utilised a monotone span program (MSP). The authors of [66, 17, 13, 27, 18] extend ABS literature using the MSP structure to express a given policy. Monotonic access structures [26] and threshold policies [61, 62, 43] enable a signer to prove the coexistence of attributes for a practical or efficient policy respectively. However, both struggle to encompass all possible statements about attributes within the policy. Thus, non-monotonic access structure policies [48, 25, 49, 53] were developed to allow a signer to include negative statements. Examples of non-monotonic policies include inner products (evaluation of polynomials) [23] and general circuits (the evaluation of arithmetic operations) [53]. More recently, [64] proposed a server-aided ABS scheme from a linear secret sharing (LSSS)-based access structure. Their scheme was in the prime group order, with non-adaptive security proven in the standard model, designed for multi-attribute authorities.

Revocation Revoking a user from a system, or more preferably, revoking the attributes of a user, is a requirement of an ABS. Shortly after the introduction of ABS by [42], the authors of [21] proposed an ABS scheme with anonymous revocation, proven secure in the standard model.

A mediated ABS scheme with key revocation was proposed by [10]. The idea is for a mediator to be given a component of the signing key from the attribute authority. Before signing their portion of the message, the mediator checks whether the user has been revoked. The obvious drawback of this solution is the high cost of communication. Further, the authors of [37] designed a more efficient ABS scheme, yet it came with more rigidity concerning the revocation technique. Namely, attributes could not be revoked in their scheme, instead, the user had to be revoked from the system. In [58], an ABS scheme was proposed such that a time parameter associated with the signature dictated the period in which attributes could be revoked. This implies the expiration and revocation of attribute keys. Server-aided ABS with revocation was introduced by [12] as a solution for low computational costs on the signer's side. In the decentralized setting, [57] proposed a blockchain-based ABS scheme relying on disjointed attribute authorities to support revocation. The authors of [23] introduced the idea of verifier-local revocable hierarchical ABS. Their proposal satisfies traceability, multi-authorities, delegation, and revocation properties.

3.5 Attribute-Based Signcryption

The signcryption gives a more efficient way of encrypting and signing a message in one scheme instead of using a signature and an encryption scheme separately. The scheme relies on the access structure tree that specifies the attribute-based access control to support predicates. The goal of using this access tree is to enforce the user's

access policy in a different operation such as encryption, or decryption. In ENTRUST, Signcrypt will be used for the enrollment of a CMD into a medical domain and the exchange of "trust predicates" between CMDs belonging to domains that have different privacy requirements.

The ABSC scheme comprises the next four algorithms.

- $\text{Setup}(\lambda)$: It's run by the Privacy CA, which takes a security parameter λ and generates a master secret key msk and the corresponding public key mpk .
- $\text{Keygen}(msk, S)$: Upon input of msk and an attribute set $S = (S_D, S_S)$ that corresponds to user encryption and signing attribute sets, the algorithm produces a set private of keys $SK = (SK_D, SK_S)$ where SK_D and SK_S represents the attribute-based encryption and signing keys respectively.
- $\text{Signcrypt}(m, T_D, T_S, SK_S)$: It's run by the encryptor/signer, it takes a plaintext m , access trees T_D and T_S , a private key set SK_S as inputs. In the end, it outputs the signcrypt ciphertext CT_s .
- $\text{De-signcrypt}(SK_D, CT_s, S)$: The De-signcrypt algorithm is run the decryptor/verifier, which takes the signcrypt ciphertext CT_s , and the attributes. At the end of this stage, it produces the message m if the user has enough attributes in the access policy and verifies the signature of the encryptor.

3.6 Attribute-Based Credentials

Attribute-based credentials are a mean to prove an entity's possession of some attributes to another party, based on the trust of the verifying party in the authority that issues the credentials. With privacy-preserving Attribute-Based Credentials (p-ABC), the credential holder can derive *presentation tokens* which may not include all the information contained in the credential. This minimal disclosure is enabled through Zero-Knowledge proofs, which also allow for unlinkability of presentation tokens between themselves and to the original credential.

In ENTRUST, p-ABCs will be used to instantiate Conformity Certificates (CC), to add an extra layer of privacy for high-end devices. Thus, the attributes will be the high-level trust appraisals of a device, such as its integrity, that result from attestation process of the device's state. The TAF will act as a trusted issuer of the CCs that certify these attributes. The properties of p-ABCs are taken advantage of to allow privacy preservation while ensuring formal guarantees of the validity of the CCs. That is, devices will receive the CC signed with the p-ABC scheme. Later on, they may need to show the information included in it according to a policy established by a verifier, which will be a third party acting as an auditor, for instance the Domain Manager after the enrolment process. The device will then be able to derive a presentation token that shows the information requested in the policy and hides any other information. The verifier can then check the proof, and still be assured that the TAF certified the revealed information.

Lastly, note that while the scheme that we describe in the following allows for distributed issuance as an additional security feature, the use cases in ENTRUST will rely on a single issuer because of their trust model. In other scenarios, the distributed issuance could be applied without needing to change later usage of the p-ABC scheme.

In the project, we rely on the Pointcheval-Sanders signature scheme [50]. Particularly, we use the variant introduced in [9] that allows multi-signatures for added security on the issuance process, with the modified presentation phase of [22] to enable modular extensions to the proof goals through commit-and-prove techniques, which we denote by PS-MS. Note

We describe the protocol interfaces for this scheme in the following, leaving formal proof of the security properties achieved of **existential unforgeability under chosen-message attacks** and **unlinkability** under the random oracle model and Modified q-Strong Diffie–Hellman assumption to the aforementioned publications.

The PS-MS scheme is composed of eight processes that can be grouped in three phases related to the usage of the scheme in practice: *setup*, *issuance* and *presentation*. In the *setup* phase, **PS-MS.Setup** establishes the public parameters (group instantiation, number of signers...); **PS-MS.KG** is used to generate key pairs; and **PS-MS.KAggr** to aggregate verification keys into a single public key. In the *issuance* phase, **PS-MS.Sign** is used

to generate signatures, which can be combined with **PS-MS.SAggr** into a single one, and verified by executing **PS-MS.Verf**. The **PS-MS.PresentZk** method allows a holder of a signature to generate a zero-knowledge proof that selectively discloses some of the signed messages. The token can then be verified through **PS-MS.VerifyZk**.

The following depicts these methods, given a pairing $\Gamma = (r, G_1, G_2, G_3, e)$ (with some security level λ) and two random oracles (plus a third one for computing the non-interactive ZK proof) which will be modeled as the hashing functions $H_0 : \mathbb{Z}_r^k \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_r \times G_1^*$ and $H_1 : G_2^{n(k+2)} \rightarrow \Theta^n \subset \mathbb{Z}_r^n$ with $1/|\Theta|$ negligible in λ . The presentation protocol assumes that the set of indexes for the attributes (A) will be divided in revealed (R), hidden (H) and involved in a commit-and-prove scheme (P), so $A = R \cup H \cup P$ with R, H, P disjoint. For each attribute $m_p, p \in P$, we have a Pedersen commitment $V_p = h_p^2 g^{m_p}$, where γ_p is a random blinding factor chosen by the holder. We denote the set of blinding factors as $\gamma_P = \{\gamma_j : j \in P\}$, and the set of Pedersen commitments as $V_P = \{V_j : j \in P\}$.

PS-MS.Setup(n, k, Γ) $\rightarrow pp$:

The parameters n and k denote the number of signers and the number of messages that will be signed at once, respectively. The elements $g_1 \in_R G_1^*$ and $g_2 \in_R G_2^*$ are chosen¹ as group generators. The public parameters of the scheme's instantiation $pp = (\Gamma, n, k, g_1, g_2)$ are returned.

PS-MS.KG(pp) $\rightarrow (sk, vk)$:

Choose the secret key $sk = (x, y_1, \dots, y_{k+1}) \in_R \mathbb{Z}_r^{*k+2}$ and compute the public key $vk = (X, Y_1, \dots, Y_{k+1}) \in G_2^{*k+2}$ where $X = g_2^x, Y_j = g_2^{y_j}$ for $j \in \{1..n\}$. Return (sk, vk) .

PS-MS.KAggr($\vec{vk} = (vk_1, \dots, vk_n)$) $\rightarrow avk$:

Compute $(t_1, \dots, t_n) = H_1(\vec{vk})$ and return $avk = \prod_{i=1}^n vk_i^{t_i}$, where multiplication and exponentiation are done by components.

PS-MS.Sign($sk, \vec{a} = (a_1, \dots, a_k)$) $\rightarrow \sigma$:

Compute $(a', h) = H_0(\vec{a})$ and the exponent $w = x + \sum_{j=1}^k y_j a_j + y_{k+1} a'$. Return $\sigma = (a', h, h^w)$.

PS-MS.SAggr($\vec{vk}, (\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_n)$) $\rightarrow \sigma$:

Take σ_i as $(a'_i, \sigma_{i,1}, \sigma_{i,2})$. Check all a'_i are equal, and all $\sigma_{i,1}$ too. Compute $(t_1, \dots, t_n) = H_1(\vec{vk})$ and $\sigma_2 = \prod_{i=1}^n \sigma_{i,2}^{t_i}$. Return $\sigma = (a'_1, \sigma_{1,1}, \sigma_2)$.

PS-MS.Verf(avk, \vec{a}, σ) $\rightarrow \text{True/False}$:

Take σ as (a', σ_1, σ_2) . If $\sigma_1 \neq 1_{G_1}$ and $e(\sigma_1, X \prod_{j=1}^n Y_j^{a_j} Y_{k+1}^{a'}) = e(\sigma_2, g_2)$ return true, else return false.

PS-MS.PresentZk($avk, \sigma, \vec{a}, R, P, \gamma_P, ctx$) $\rightarrow tok$:

Take σ as (a', σ_1, σ_2) and compute $(\sigma'_1, \sigma'_2) = (\sigma_1^w, (\sigma_2 \sigma_1^z)^w)$ for $w, z \in_R \mathbb{Z}_r$, and $V_j = X^{\gamma_j} Y_p^{a_j} j \in P$. Then, compute the modified Schnorr's signature:

$\pi = NIZK.Prove\{(\vec{a}_H, z, \vec{a}_P, \vec{\gamma}_P, \sigma) : PS - MS.Verf(avk, \vec{a}, \sigma) = True, V_p = X^{\gamma_j} Y_j^{a_j}, j \in P\}(ctx)$

That is, choose random $t_{a_j} j \in H, t_z, t_{\gamma_j} j \in P$ and $t_{a'}$ and compute

$$t = \prod_{j \in HUP} e(\sigma'_1, Y_j)^{t_{a_j}} e(\sigma'_1, Y_{k+1})^{t_{a'}} e(\sigma'_1, g_2)^{t_z} \prod_{j \in P} e(\sigma'_1, X)^{t_{\gamma_j}}$$

Then, the challenge is $c = H_2(ctx, avk, \sigma'_1, \sigma'_2, V_P, t)$ and the signature is

$\pi = (c, (v_{a_j})_{j \in HUP}, v_z, (v_{\gamma_j})_{j \in P}, v_{a'})$, for $v_{a_j} = t_{a_j} - ca_j j \in H, v_{a_j} = t_{a_j} - 2ca_j j \in P, v_z = t_z - cz, v_{a'} = t_{a'} - ca'$ and $v_{\gamma_j} = t_{\gamma_j} - c\gamma_j j \in P$.

Return $tok = (\sigma'_1, \sigma'_2, \pi)$.

PS-MS.VerifyZk($avk, tok, \vec{a}_R, V_P, ctx$) $\rightarrow \text{True/False}$:

Take $tok = (\sigma'_1, \sigma'_2, \pi)$ with $\pi = (c, (v_{a_j})_{j \in H}, v_z, v_{\gamma_j}, v_{a'})$.

¹The symbol \in_R means that the choice is random

Then, verify that the signature of knowledge π is valid. That is, compute:

$$t' = \prod_{j \in H \cup P} e(\sigma_1', Y_j)^{v_{a_j}} e(\sigma_1', Y_{k+1})^{v_{a'}} e(\sigma_1', g_2)^{v_z} \cdot \prod_{j \in R} e(\sigma_1', Y_j)^{-c_{a_j}} \cdot e(\sigma_1', X)^{-c} e(\sigma_2', g_2)^c \prod_{j \in P} e(\sigma_1', V_j)^c \prod_{j \in P} e(\sigma_1', X)^{v_{\gamma_j}}$$

Calculate $c' = H_2(ctx, avk, \sigma_1', \sigma_2', V_P, t')$. Return true if $c = c'$ and false otherwise.

3.7 Direct-Anonymous-Attestation

As described in Deliverable D4.1, **ENTRUST** aims to design a privacy-preserving and authenticated ecosystem, consisting of autonomous and intelligent edge devices. This ecosystem must ensure numerous properties such as anonymity, unlinkability, unobservability, and strict trust guarantees across a wide range of multi-vendor devices and platforms. To achieve these goals, ENTRUST plans to employ advanced cryptographic primitives alongside Trusted Computing techniques, facilitating such strict requirements in a variety of emerging applications.

In this context, Direct Anonymous Attestation (**DAA**) serves as a platform authentication mechanism that provides privacy-preserving and accountable services. DAA is based on group signatures, enabling the remote attestation of a device associated with a Trusted Component (**TC**) while offering strong anonymity guarantees. Generally, a Direct Anonymous Attestation scheme comprises a DAA Issuer, a set of Signers, and a set of Verifiers.

The DAA Issuer acts as a Trusted Third Party (TTP), creating DAA membership credentials for each signer that wishes to participate in the DAA scheme. A DAA credential corresponds to a signature of the signer's identity and the signer's attestation public key, produced by the DAA Issuer. A DAA signer typically consists of a (HOST, Trusted Component) pair; in ENTRUST, the DAA signer will consist of a (**HOST, TrustZone**) pair. Acquiring a DAA credential indicates a membership credential to the DAA community and a trustworthy validation of the signer.

In other words, by providing a DAA signature, a Verifier receives attestation evidence regarding the configuration of the signer's state. Moreover, the DAA signature includes a Zero-Knowledge Proof-of-Knowledge, a cryptographic construct used to convince the Verifier that the signer possesses a valid DAA membership credential without revealing any other information about the signer's identity. More concretely, the DAA provides the signer with the ability to create signatures anonymously while still convincing the Verifier of the possession of a valid DAA membership credential.

- **User-Controlled Linkability:** Two DAA signatures created by the same signer can be linked or remain unlinked from a Verifier's perspective. This linkability is determined by an input parameter called the basename. If a signer uses the same basename in two signatures, they are linked; otherwise, they remain unlinked.
- **Unforgeability:** When the DAA Issuer and the HOST's Trusted Environment, in ENTRUST **TrustZone**, are honest, no adversary can create a signature on a message μ with respect to the bsn unless the TrustZone enclave signed μ with respect to the bsn .
- **One-More Unforgeability:** When the DAA Issuer is honest, an adversary can only sign in the name of compromised TrustZone enclaves. Specifically, if n TrustZone enclaves are compromised, the adversary can create at most n unlinkable signatures for the same basename.
- **Anonymity:** An adversary given two signatures, with respect to two different basenames, cannot determine whether both signatures were created by one honest device or by two different honest devices.
- **Non-frameability:** No adversary can create signatures on a message μ with respect to basename bsn that links to a signature created by an honest device for the same basename if the honest device never signed μ with respect to bsn .

3.8 Hash-based Signatures

In ENTRUST, Hash-based Signatures are used for efficient utilization of PUFs in most low-end CMD operations, namely, authentication, attestation, creation, and presentation of Conformity Certificates.

Hash functions are mathematical functions that take input data of arbitrary size and produce a fixed-length output, known as a hash value or digest. Hash functions are used in various crypto-constructions such as data integrity verification, message authentication, and digital signature schemes. The two main security features of hash functions that make them securely used in building secure cryptographic schemes are:

- **One-Wayness:** It is computationally infeasible to recover the input data from the hash value. This property makes hash functions suitable for protecting the integrity of data and detecting any changes or tampering.
- **Collision Resistance:** It is computationally infeasible to find two different inputs that produce the same hash value. This property is essential for ensuring the security of many cryptographic applications, including digital signatures.

Some popular hash functions include SHA-256, SHA-3, and BLAKE-2.

3.8.1 One-Time Signatures (OTS)

A one-time signature (OTS) scheme is a digital signature scheme that can be used to sign one message per key pair, with no assurance of security if the key pair is reused to sign again. Lamport [36] and Rabin [51] proposed the first one-time signature (OTS) schemes that can be efficiently built from one-way functions. The design was later made more efficient by Winternitz [44], Bos and Chaum [7], and Hulsing's WOTS+ scheme [29], which is the current state of the art.

3.8.2 Merkle Signatures

Because OTS can only sign one message at a time, if multiple messages need to be signed, there must be many keys. The Merkle Tree Signature Scheme (commonly called "MSS") [44] was invented by Ralph Merkle to manage OTS keys. The basic idea is to use Merkle tree leaves to store OTS keys. Because the Merkle trees are binary, a Merkle tree of height h has 2^h leaves. The leaves are used to manage digests of OTS keys, and a Merkle tree can manage 2^h OTS key pairs. When signing a message, one OTS key pair needs to be picked up from the tree that has not been used before. The signature consists of the index of the leaf, the OTS public key, the digest of the OTS public key (the leaf), and the *authentication path* of that leaf. An authentication path contains the internal values of the nodes that constitute a path between the leaf and the root. We reveal the leaf node that is the starting node. Using the authentication path, the verifier can compute the end node which is the Root node (top of the tree). Note that the authentication path is unique for each leaf node. To verify the signature, the verifier checks if the value of the Root node that is calculated from the given authentication path matches the publicly known root value of the tree.

Chapter 4

ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base

4.1 ENTRUST Interoperable Security Stack

A medical-service graph chain consists of a highly **heterogeneous set of CMDs**, ranging from simple biometrics sensors to complex gateways with high computational capabilities that manage multiple "children" CDMs. The presence of such a **diverse ecosystem** presents unique **security challenges** and the problem of providing a solution for the **complete secure lifecycle management of CMDs** remains an open one.

ENTRUST envisions a solution to this problem with the design and provision of an **Interoperable Security Stack** that is **open, flexible and highly-portable** which is founded on the security assurances that **HW-based RoTs** can provide. Our project's vision of interoperability constitutes of the aspiration to create a security stack that is **agnostic to the underlying RoT** and is capable of securing highly diverse medical ecosystems with CMDs that possess different RoTs. This is depicted in Figure 2.1. Components in green enhance interoperability across different architectures by providing a consistent level of abstraction and improving existing security features. To address interoperability challenges, ENTRUST will supply the upper layers of the stack (such as the OS and applications) with a **standardized set of APIs** to utilize RoT functionalities and trusted services.

For this to happen there are two major aspects that must be considered by ENTRUST. The first one is to allow these types of layers between different CMDs to establish a secure and authenticated channel. For instance, through ENTRUST, a high-end CMD can establish such a channel with the RTOS through the Attestation Agent of the low-end CMD. The second dimension is to be able to provide a set of harmonized interfaces that can be exposed by this layer and be consumed by any type of RoT. This is already being followed and was one of the reasons for instantiating the high-end CMD's TEE with OPTEE [2] which implements TEE Internal Core API v1.3.1 and the TEE Client API v1.0. Those APIs are defined in the GlobalPlatform API specifications [3].

As stated in D4.1, the ENTRUST TCB will constitute of a PUF for the low-end CMDs and OP-TEE for the high-end CMDs. In the remaining of this Chapter, we will present the architecture of those TCBs, the underlying hardware and the security functionalities that they expose.

4.2 High-End device TCB

4.2.1 OP-TEE

OP-TEE is a Trusted Execution Environment (TEE) designed to work alongside a non-secure Linux kernel running on Arm Cortex-A cores using TrustZone technology. It implements the TEE Internal Core API v1.3.1, which is used by Trusted Applications, and the TEE Client API v1.0, which outlines how to communicate with a TEE. These APIs are defined by the GlobalPlatform specifications.

In TEE specifications, the non-secure OS is called the Rich Execution Environment (REE), typically a GNU/Linux

distribution or the Android Open Source Project (AOSP).

OP-TEE mainly relies on Arm TrustZone for hardware isolation but is designed to be compatible with any suitable isolation technology, including running as a virtual machine or on a dedicated CPU.

The primary design goals of OP-TEE are:

- **Isolation:** Ensuring TEE provides isolation from the non-secure OS and protects the loaded Trusted Applications (TAs) from each other using hardware support.
- **Small footprint:** Keeping the TEE small enough to fit within the on-chip memory typically found on Arm systems.
- **Portability:** Making the TEE easily adaptable to different architectures and hardware, supporting various setups such as multiple client OSes or multiple TEEs.

OP-TEE is composed of several components:

- A secure privileged layer running at Arm secure PL-1 (v7-A) or EL-1 (v8-A) level.
- Secure user space libraries for Trusted Applications.
- A Linux kernel TEE framework and driver (included in the official Linux kernel since version 4.12).
- A Linux user space library based on the GlobalPlatform TEE Client API specifications.
- A Linux user space supplicant daemon (tee-suppld) handling remote services for the TEE OS.
- A test suite (xtest) for regression testing and verifying API implementations.

4.2.1.1 Trusted Applications

User Mode Trusted Applications are loaded into memory by the OP-TEE core in the Secure World when a request is made by the Rich Execution Environment (REE) to communicate with a specific application UUID. These applications operate at a lower CPU privilege level compared to the OP-TEE core code. In this way, they are quite similar to regular applications running in the REE, but they execute in the Secure World. Trusted Applications utilize the GlobalPlatform TEE Internal Core API as outlined by the GlobalPlatform TEE specifications.

A TA can be authenticated using a subkey or a chain of subkeys, which enables the delegation of TA signing without sharing the root key. TAs signed with a subkey are restricted to the UUID-V5 namespace of that subkey to prevent TA UUID conflicts with other subkeys. SHDR_SUBKEY is a header type that supports chains of public keys. The public root key verifies the first public subkey, which in turn verifies the next public subkey, continuing this process until the TA is verified using the final subkey. These headers are placed in front of the TA binary so that everything necessary to verify the TA is available when it is loaded into memory.

User mode TAs are loaded into final memory using the user mode ELF loader, ldelf, in the same manner. The different TA locations share a common interface with ldelf, making user mode operations consistent regardless of how the TA is stored. After ldelf prepares a TA for execution, it remains in memory to support the TA if dlopen() and related functions are used. Additionally, ldelf is utilized to generate stack traces and detailed memory mappings if a TA is terminated due to an abort.

4.2.1.2 Trusted and Untrusted World Communication

OP-TEE OS operates in the secure world. A world switch is managed by the core's secure monitor level/mode, referred to as the Monitor. When the normal world calls upon the secure world, it executes an SMC instruction. The SMC exception is always intercepted by the Monitor. If the corresponding service is meant for the trusted OS,

the Monitor switches to OP-TEE OS world execution. When the secure world returns control to the normal world, OP-TEE OS executes an SMC that the Monitor catches, switching back to the normal world.

When a secure interrupt is signaled by the Arm GIC, it reaches the OP-TEE OS interrupt exception vector. If the secure world is currently executing, OP-TEE OS will handle the interrupt directly from its exception vector. If the normal world is executing when the secure interrupt occurs, the Monitor vector will handle the exception and invoke OP-TEE OS to manage the interrupt. Conversely, when a non-secure interrupt is signaled by the Arm GIC, it reaches the normal world interrupt exception vector. If the normal world is executing, it will handle the exception directly from its exception vector. If the secure world is executing when the non-secure interrupt occurs, OP-TEE OS will temporarily switch back to the normal world via the Monitor to allow the normal world to handle the interrupt.

4.2.1.3 Secure Storage

OP-TEE provides a trusted execution environment where sensitive data can be encrypted and isolated from the main operating system and other applications on the device. This ensures that even if the device is compromised or attacked, the data remains protected within the secure enclave provided by OP-TEE. Additionally, OP-TEE can facilitate secure data processing and communication within connected medical devices. By running critical operations within the trusted execution environment, OP-TEE can prevent unauthorized access to sensitive algorithms and cryptographic keys, reducing risks associated with malicious attacks, software vulnerabilities, or unauthorized access attempts. Moreover, OP-TEE supports secure communication between the medical device and external systems such as healthcare networks. By establishing secure channels for data transmission and implementing cryptographic protocols within the trusted execution environment, OP-TEE ensures the confidentiality, integrity, and authenticity of the data exchanged between medical devices and external entities.

Secure storage, as described above, is a vital function for the operation of connected medical devices. In OP-TEE, this functionality is implemented according to the specifications defined in GlobalPlatform's TEE Internal Core API (also known as Trusted Storage). This specification requires the capability to store general-purpose data and key material while ensuring the confidentiality and integrity of the stored data and the atomicity of operations that modify the storage. Atomicity here means that either the entire operation completes successfully, or no write is done at all.

4.2.2 ENTRUST Key Management

Defining a Key Management System (KMS) with OP-TEE is essential for the ENTRUST framework because keys are used for critical applications such as signing, encryption, and secure storage. Therefore, it is crucial that the ENTRUST crypto architecture includes a robust mechanism for managing all cryptographic keys within the security monitor, while also preventing any key-recovery attacks. Key management involves the processes of generating, exchanging, storing, protecting, and replacing cryptographic keys within a cryptosystem.

4.2.2.1 OP-TEE Key Hierarchy

OP-TEE implements a Public Key Hierarchy with Subkeys. Subkeys are an OP-TEE-specific implementation designed to create a public key hierarchy. The first key in the chain is verified using a root key.

Each subkey defines a UUIDv5 namespace to which another signed subkey or TA must belong. This ensures that one subkey cannot be used to sign TAs that should be signed with a different key. Due to this restriction, there is a special type of subkey called an identity subkey, which uses the same UUID as the TA it is meant to sign. A subkey consists of two files: a private key pair in a .pem file and the signed public key in a .bin file.

Subkeys reuse the signed header (SHDR) format used for signed TAs, followed by a payload containing a public key and UUID, among other fields. All subkeys in the hierarchy are included in front when a TA is signed using a subkey. The signed TA binary is self-contained, including all the public keys needed for verification, except for the public root key, which is embedded in the TEE core binary. The UUIDv5 name string is a separate field between subkeys and the next subkey or TA, allowing a subkey to be used to sign more than one other subkey or TA.

4.2.2.2 ENTRUST Key Hierarchy and Key Restriction Usage Policies

To this end, ENTRUST is expanding the existing Key Hierarchy by adopting a **Tree-Like** structure for implementing the secure creation and management of keys. Following this approach, ENTRUST aims to adopt, as part of its Key Hierarchy, guidelines from other secure elements well established in the literature (i.e., TPM). This creates a multi-layer key hierarchy where, in order to access each layer, the device needs to have access to the key stored in the layer above. This structure comprises three *key types*:

1. The HW-based TEE Key, which is a unique key and is considered the identification key of the device. This key is the the CMD's Root Id key and serves as the root node of the tree, placing it at the highest position in ENTRUST's Key Hierarchy.
2. The Primary Keys, derived directly from the Root ID key and a (trusted) random number generator, as part of the TEE. The Primary Keys are placed just below the SM key in the tree structure and are the root nodes of their respective sub-branches.
3. The Children Keys, derived from the secret key of their parent node and a random number generated by a Trusted random number generator. These keys are not considered root nodes of their respective sub-branches. To use any child key, the Key Management System requires authorization from the respective parent key.

As aforementioned, one of the core building blocks for enabling the trust assessment of a device is the management of appropriate crypto primitives (keys). Specifically, regarding the provision of verifiable trust-related evidence (e.g., attestation evidence) based on which the device's trust state can be quantified, the authenticity and integrity of such evidence is ensured through the use of well-predicated Attestation Keys. Thus, ENTRUST aims to adopt enhanced authorization mechanisms (Key Restriction Usage Policies) allowing different components/enclaves to access the attestation key *if and only if* certain assertions have been made.

More specifically, the **ENTRUST Key Management** needs to be configured in a way that strictly allows the administrator (Domain Manager) alone to define the set of actions that must be performed before a Trusted Application is granted access to a key that resides within the Key Manager. In this context, assertions play a pivotal role, representing statements that must be true for a policy to be satisfied. The **ENTRUST Key Management** supports a set of logical equations which, if all are satisfied, output a valid key restriction usage policy. To seamlessly integrate the enhanced key management system into OP-TEE, it is conceived as an extension routine that stores and manages requests from enclaves wishing to use a key.

To this end, ENTRUST's enhanced key management system embodies two distinct mechanisms: one for keys created by the edge device's Key Manager and one for keys created by external trusted entities and injected into the Key Manager.

- For the self-issued keys, the Key Manager uses the Key Restriction Usage Policy as a key co-seed generator. Specifically, the Key Manager provides the following parameters to its internal *KDF*:
 1. The private part of the parent key, according to the Key Manager's Key Hierarchy. The parent key can either be the Security Monitor Key (for creating a Primary Key) or a Primary Key acting as a root node of a respective sub-branch of the tree-like structure (for creating a child key). This binds the child key to its parent.
 2. A random number generated by a Trusted *RNG*, *rand*, to randomize the key creation algorithm. This *RNG* can be provided by the underlying Root of Trust (**RoT**) or by the Security Monitor itself.
 3. The Key Restriction Usage Policy to be enforced as the enhanced authorization mechanism.

By using the Key Restriction Usage Policy as a co-seed in the creation of the key, the Key Manager enforces the set of pre-defined assertions during runtime to calculate a runtime policy. With the runtime policy, the Key Manager attempts to re-calculate the secret key. *IF* the runtime policy matches the Key Restriction Usage Policy issued by the Domain Manager, the Key Manager will create the same key during Secure Enrolment and runtime.

- For the keys injected into the Key Manager, since the edge device cannot know the key seed generator, we can't use the same approach for binding the keys with the appropriate policy. Instead, each injected key is stored encrypted in the Key Manager, using the Key Restriction Usage Policy as the symmetric encryption key. During runtime, the Key Manager enforces the set of assertions corresponding to this key and computes a runtime policy. *IF* the runtime policy matches the Key Restriction Usage Policy issued by the Domain Manager, the Key Manager will be able to successfully decrypt and use the injected key.

4.2.3 OP-TEE Security Capabilities

The main security capabilities that are required from a Trusted Execution Environment for enabling the creation of ENTRUST's Interoperable Security Stack are **Attestation** and **Process State Verification**. Both procedures are not natively implemented in OP-TEE in a way that can be used in ENTRUST without modification. In the next paragraphs we will present the existing operations and how we will expand them in our project for enabling the Secure Lifecycle Management of CMDs.

We observe that OP-TEE doesn't even provide the baseline capabilities for attestation. This is why, in the context of ENTRUST we must provide the implementation of remote/local attestation to process and support all the trusted computing operations needed and described in ENTRUST. Understandably most of the components that constitute OP-TEE will be altered or enhanced in order to support all of the functionalities. The implementation of the high-end CMD TCB will provide APIs for all the security functionalities that are described in this deliverable.

As extensively discussed in earlier chapters, particularly in section ??, each cryptographic key is associated with a Key Restriction Usage Policy. This policy dictates the correct configuration state of the entire system, encompassing the configuration of both the attestation engine and any other critical applications included in the MUD profile. By binding each key with a policy, the device's correct state can be verified.

Expanding on device state verification, in ENTRUST we require not only device state verification but also process state verification. ENTRUST aims to implement these security measures across all devices wishing to participate in its ecosystem, regardless of the privacy requirements enforced by the Domain Manager. Specifically, for each device participating in the ENTRUST ecosystem without privacy requirements, process state verification involves creating a Proof of Knowledge (PoK) over the enclave's unique identification using the device's Attestation Key. The steps for this process are:

1. The Key Manager generates a signature over all unique enclave identifications that need to provide and sends it to the Privacy CA.
2. Upon receiving the signature, the Privacy CA verifies its validity to confirm both possession of valid credentials and correct configuration state. If verified successfully, the Privacy CA creates a certificate and establishes a revocation policy for each enclave identification.
3. The Key Manager then stores multiple certificates within for runtime use in generating signatures and establishing trusted, authenticated channels between enclaves.

4.2.4 ENTRUST Harmonized Set of TEE Key Management Extensions/Interfaces

Our vision is to develop a Key Management extension that will feature a Key Manager operating within the TEE, with interfaces accessible through API calls for specific functionalities. The goal is to ensure high interoperability, enabling the Key Management extension to function seamlessly across different architectures without being tied to any particular processor or root of trust. A crucial step in realizing this vision is the careful selection of a subset of interfaces from the comprehensive set defined by initiatives such as the Global Platform API. These interfaces must fully support key hierarchies and other essential components of robust Key Management. Once identified, these interfaces will be meticulously developed into an interoperable Key Management Software Stack, forming a key part of the ENTRUST initiative. After identifying the relevant subset of interfaces from initiatives like the GlobalPlatform API, it is important to understand the distinction between CPU-dependent and CPU-independent APIs as described

in the GlobalPlatform Technology TEE Internal Core API Specification. CPU-dependent APIs are customized to interact with or utilize features specific to the CPU on which they are implemented. They may directly access hardware resources or offer functionalities closely tied to the CPU's capabilities. In contrast, CPU-independent APIs are designed to be hardware-agnostic, abstracting hardware complexities to provide a standardized interface applicable across various CPU architectures. This abstraction promotes portability and compatibility, enabling applications to be developed once and deployed seamlessly across different hardware platforms without modifications. Given our emphasis on interoperability, we prioritize CPU-independent APIs. These can be seen in Table 4.1

Category	CPU	Functions
Random Number	Independent	TEE_GenerateRandom: Generates a random number using sudo-random function provided by the TEE. This interface will be invoked mainly during the creation of a key. Its entropy must be equivalent with the PUF's
Secure Storage	Independent	TEE_OpenObject: This function opens a handle on an existing persistent object. TEE_ReadObjectData: function attempts to read size bytes from the data stream associated with the object into the buffer pointed to by buffer. TEE_WriteObjectData: function writes size bytes from the buffer pointed to by buffer to the data stream associated with the open object handle object. TEE_CloseObject: function close a handle on an existing persistent object. Alternatively, a persistent object could represent an attested state of the enclave, which is stored for potential roll-back purposes. The authorised enclave may essentially wish to open a handle to it.
Transient Object Functions	Independent	TEE_GenerateKey: Generate key under the root key of the key hierarchy. It will take parameters such as the Trusted Application UUID, the hash of the enclave, and a random number which must be generated internally from TEE_GenerateRandom. TEE_InitValueAttribute: This function can be used to populate a single attribute with integer values. The TEE retains attributes per enclaves. Attributes could include the UUID, the hash of the Trusted Application, the software version of the application running in an enclave, which is necessary for the software update process. Therefore, this information is securely stored in the TEE.
Crypto Common	Independent	TEE_AllocateOperation: function allocates a handle for a new cryptographic operation and sets the mode and algorithm type. TEE_FreeOperation: function deallocates all resources associated with an operation handle. These functions facilitate the registration of additional cryptographic schemes supported by the TEE.
Authenticated Encryption	ENTRUST Specific	TEE_AE_Encrypt: Encrypts data using an authenticated encryption scheme. TEE_AE_Decrypt: Decrypts data encrypted using an authenticated encryption scheme. TEE_AE_Sign: Signs data using an authenticated encryption scheme. TEE_AE_Verify: Verifies the authenticity of data signed using an authenticated encryption scheme. To achieve resilience against physical attacks in the context of ENTRUST, it is essential for the software update key to support authentication encryption, as described in D3.2. The TEE is responsible for mediating access only for authorized enclaves. It will run on the key manager, enforcing access control and providing access to the secure element that holds the software update key.
Symmetric Cipher	N/A	No need for TEE interface because symmetric keys for communication with other domain devices will be kept by the enclaves.
Asymmetric Cipher	ENTRUST Specific	TEE_DAA_FinalSignature: function is specific to DAA operations. It performs the final signature step in the DAA process, which is used to authenticate a user or entity without revealing their identity. TEE_DAA_Commitment: function it generates a commitment, which is a cryptographic value that allows a user to prove possession of certain information without revealing that information itself. TEE_DAA_Verify: function verify the authenticity of a signature or commitment generated during the authentication process. The TEE retains the asymmetric private key pairs and certificates to perform specific operations, primarily revolving around DAA signature creation and management of DAA credentials.

Generic Operation	Independent	TEE_SetOperationKey :function programs the key of an operation; that is, it associates an operation with a key.
Key Derivation	Independent	TEE_DeriveKey : function takes one of the Asymmetric Derivation Operation Parameters as input, and outputs a key object.

Table 4.1: Key Management Interfaces

4.3 Low-End device PUF- based TCB

4.3.1 PUF-based Key Generation and Reconstruction Scheme

As mentioned in D4.1 [19], the main trust anchor of ENTRUST’s TCB, in case low-end CMDs are considered, is the SRAM-based PUF instance, developed to provide the cryptographic primitives for such resources-constrained devices. The core functionality of the aforementioned building block is the **key generation** (during the enrollment phase) and **reconstruction** (when the continuous authentication of the device is needed). In [19], the concept of the fuzzy extractor was introduced which can be leveraged to convert PUF’s noisy information into useful cryptographic primitives for relevant applications and services, along with the BCH error correction scheme which is highly recommended for fixing random errors introduced in a PUF-oriented bit sequence.

Having introduced the core features and the methodology followed towards a reliable and secure SRAM-PUF instance in the following paragraphs the key generation and reconstruction scheme utilized for the extraction of the PUF-based key is described in detail, along with the approach followed here to bind the PUF-key with the device’s secure boot hash, resulting to the final key.

4.3.1.1 Fuzzy Extractors

In general, when inherently noisy data (such as those generated from a PUF implementation) are utilized to generate strong cryptographic primitives an important issue is how the noisy nonuniform inputs can be converted into reliably reproducible, uniformly random strings. Towards that, fuzzy extractors are pursued in security applications to enable stable matching. Fuzzy extractors were first proposed to transform biometric data into random strings, while they are built from secure sketches (SS), which correct errors in the outputs [16]. During the generation phase, secure sketches output a public helper data string from the input with small information leakage, which will be used for error correction. In the reproduction procedure, if the hamming distance $HD(output, output') \leq t$, then $output'$ can be corrected to $output$ even with the presence of t -bit errors. Additionally, to achieve a uniform output as a cryptographic key an additional mapping process (typically a hash function) is applied usually, following the error correction [38].

Fuzzy extractors are extensively utilized in PUF-based authentication due to their ability to correct PUF response errors caused by environmental variations and enhance uniqueness. By correcting limited response errors, the fuzzy extractor’s secure sketches can be constructed or viewed as linear codes, including Hadamard, Hamming, repetition, Reed-Solomon, Reed-Muller, binary Golay, and BCH codes [55],[28]. Several error-correcting codes (ECC) and decoding strategies have been proposed to be used in fuzzy extractors for PUF-based key generation, e.g. in [8],[60],[41], [40],[65].

FE has two major steps:

1. correcting possible bit errors (noise elimination) and
2. extracting uniform random string from the non-noisy PUF output or the corrected one.

For the latter step, a universal hash function is generally used [63], whereas for the first step, error-correcting codes are utilized, like syndrome construction, code-offset construction, index-based syndrome coding, complementary

index-based syndrome, and differential sequence coding [14]. Code offset and syndrome construction are two prevalent constructions used with silicon PUFs, and they are classified as linear schema, due to the process of generation of the helper data and the secret key that is based on linear relationship between the PUF response and codewords of the error correction code. In the **code-offset approach**, to create the public helper data h , a sequence w of n bits of the PUF response is XORed with a random codeword c of an ECC (n,k,t) , so $h = w \oplus c$ [16]. In the **syndrome-based approach**, the syndrome is calculated by multiplying a sequence w of n bits of the PUF response with the transposed parity-check-matrix H^T of the ECC (n,k,t) , so $h = wH^T$, and the syndrome is stored as helper data [15].

Below the exact definitions of a secure sketch and fuzzy extractor are provided to assist the reader in the key generation and reconstruction scheme described here,

Secure Sketch: SS [16] is a primitive performing error correction on a noisy data w' by eliminating noises and recover (Rec) the original one w , clean from noise. SS takes w as input and produces a public sketch or a public helper data s , without revealing enough information about w . Rec uses s to recover w from w' by cleaning noise while $w' \approx w$.

Definition 1: An $\langle n, m, m', t \rangle$ -secure sketch for the metric space n with distance function dis , is a pair of randomized procedures, "sketch" (SS) and "recovery" (Rec), defined as follows.

- The sketching procedure (SS) takes $w \in n$ as input and returns a public helper data $h \in \{0, 1\}^*$.
- The recovery procedure (Rec) takes $w' \in n$ and h as input and outputs w .

Secure sketches have to satisfy the following properties:

1. Correctness or error tolerance: $\forall w \in n, h \leftarrow SS(w) : Rec(w', h) = w$ if $dis(w, w') \leq t$. If $dis(w, w') > t$, then no guarantee is provided about the output of Rec .
2. Security: It requires that h does not leak too much information about w . Specifically, for any random variable w over n with min-entropy m , the secure sketch must ensure that the average conditional min-entropy of w given $SS(w)$ is at least m' .

Fuzzy Extractor: FE [16] extracts uniformly random string from noisy non- uniform random data. This string can be used as a secure key in cryptographic applications.

Definition 2: An $\langle n, m, l, t, \epsilon \rangle$ -fuzzy extractor is a pair of randomized procedures, "generate" Gen and "reproduce" Rep , satisfying the following properties:

1. The generation procedure Gen on input $w \in n$ outputs an extracted string $K \in \{0, 1\}^l$ and a helper string $h \in \{0, 1\}^*$.
2. The reproduction procedure Rep takes an element $w' \in n$ and a bit sequence $h \in \{0, 1\}^*$ as inputs. The correctness property of fuzzy extractors guarantees that if $dis(w, w') \leq t$ and K, h were generated by $(K, h) \leftarrow Gen(w)$, then $Rep(w', h) = K$. In any other case, no guarantee is provided about the output of Rep .
3. The security property guarantees that for any distribution w on n of min-entropy m , the string K is nearly uniform even for those who observe h : if $(K, h) \leftarrow Gen(w)$, then the statistical distance between (K, h) and (U_l, h) is $\leq \epsilon$, where U_l is the uniform distribution on $\{0, 1\}^l$. The security property states that the extracted key K is very close to a randomly chosen l -bit key, with only a negligible statistical difference.

4.3.1.2 Key Generation and Reconstruction based on Fuzzy Extractors

4.3.1.2.1 Overview

As extensively discussed in [19], due to the manufacturing process of the integrated circuits, SRAM-PUFs are classified as a source of randomness and they can be employed to generate cryptographic keys without storing the key's information for future use. This advantage is guaranteed since the key can be generated on demand. Nevertheless, one of the biggest challenges with PUFs in general is to guarantee the stability of the key in each regeneration phase, which is caused by the environmental variables. To achieve the stability (zero error rate) of the PUF response, it usually needs to be post-processed. The latter is generally composed of two phases: *generation* and *reconstruction* (see Figure 4.1).

Figure 4.1: Overview of (a) generation and (b) reconstruction phases utilizing a PUF instance [67].

Generation phase: During this phase, the unique identifier (or the key) is generated from the initial PUF response. At the same time, the public helper data is also generated. Clearly, the key has to be kept secret as it is used in cryptographic applications. On the other hand, if the helper data does not reveal information about the secret, it can be classified as public and stored in non-secure non-volatile memory.

Reconstruction phase: At this stage, the stored public helper data is used to recover the enrolled key and to correct the bit errors that occurred in the actual PUF response (noisy response). This can be achieved since the helper data content describing the secret key allows a reliable key reconstruction, even under variations of the environmental conditions.

Deriving a uniformly random string from non-uniform randomness sources has two major obstacles. The first, called information reconciliation, by tolerating the noise in the sources without leaking any information. The second, converting those values into uniformly random secret strings is known as privacy amplification. Several approaches like fuzzy extractors accomplish both information reconciliation using the secure sketch and privacy amplification using randomness extractor [16] which can be constructed from cryptographic hash functions.

4.3.1.2.2 Constructing Fuzzy Extractor from Secure Sketch

Fuzzy extractors (FE) extract a uniformly random string and a public string from an initial input. The first string can be recovered from another noisy input using the second extracted string. This step can be achieved in the case where both inputs are close to each other. Secure sketch (SS) allows reconstructing the initial input from noisy input by making use of some helper data. The difference between these two techniques is that fuzzy extractors return a uniform string and a secure sketch returns a non-uniform string but it permits noise's elimination. Generating cryptographic keys from PUFs go through two phases, generation and reconstruction, and both phases can be achieved using fuzzy extractors. However, to generate a uniformly reproducible random string from a noisy source, secure sketches and strong randomness extractors are utilized in most of the cases to build fuzzy extractors [16]. In the following subsections, how fuzzy extractors can be used to generate uniform information from PUFs employing a secure sketch based on code-offset and a syndrome-based construction are described along with corresponding implementation examples.

Code-offset based Fuzzy Extractor

Generation Procedure:

Reproduction Procedure:

Figure 4.2: Code-offset fuzzy extractor construction scheme

The flow of the code-offset based fuzzy extractor is depicted in Figure 4.2. During the **generation procedure**, let $C[n, k, d]$ be an error correcting code, where n is the length of the code, k is the size of the message (if the code is linear, k is also called the dimension of the code), and d is the minimum distance of the code (which is the minimum Hamming distance between any two codewords). On input $w \in \{0, 1\}^n$, this procedure chooses $x \in \{0, 1\}^k$ randomly (utilizing a Random Number Generator) and computes $c = C(x)$, the encoding of the random secret x . It computes the helper data as $h = w \oplus c$. The generation procedure also utilizes a universal hash function H and extracts the key $K = H(w)$. It outputs (K, h) . Note that the helper data usually includes the choice of the universal hash function H . For simplicity, H is neglected from the helper data. In many practical implementations of fuzzy extractors [8], [40], [60], universal hash functions are replaced with an LFSR-based Toeplitz hash [35] or other cryptographic functions (e.g., SHA or HMAC). When a **request for reconstruction** is received, a noisy PUF response $w' \in \{0, 1\}^n$ is generated and along with the helper data string h and the universal hash function H , $c' = w' \oplus h$ is computed. Then, c' is decoded to calculate c , if $\text{diss}(w', w) \leq t$ and $w = h \oplus c$ is reproduced as well as the key $K = H(w)$.

In Figure 4.3, an implementation diagram of the aforementioned scheme is presented [33]. During the implementation of that scheme, there are two important considerations, i.e., a combination of information reconciliation and privacy amplification. The information reconciliation step guarantees the elimination of noise from the measured noisy data. Privacy amplification guarantees the uniform distribution of the derived key bits. A BCH code and SHA-256 hash function were used to address these two basic requirements. In key generation phase, a key R is produced by applying SHA256 hash function on a result of XOR operation between PUF response w and a random number x , where the latter is by utilizing a random number generator (RNG).

Syndrome based Fuzzy Extractor

After the description of the code-offset based approach, here, the other dominant construction is presented which is based on a syndrome. The secure sketch construction has a pair of functions, the same as the code-offset approach, Gen and Rep . During the key generation phase based on a PUF response w , helper data h is computed by using $Gen(w)$, where $h = wH^t$ and H is a parity check matrix of a linear error correction code. The key reconstruction described by $Rep(w', h)$ firsts constructs a syndrome, $s = (w'H^t) \oplus h = eH^t$, with e an error vector. Then through an error location algorithm, e is determined. Subsequently, the registered PUF response w is recovered through $w = e \oplus w'$. The recovered PUF response w may not ideally be uniformly distributed, therefore, an entropy extraction method such as a universal hash function compresses the PUF response into a cryptographic key with full bit entropy.

One of the main differences between the code-offset based construction scheme and the one described above

Figure 4.3: Implementation diagram using a code-offset based fuzzy extractor ($n=255$)[33].

is that the former sets as a prerequisite the existence of a random number generator for the successful key creation and recovery. Thus, its implementation is limited to devices equipped with such capabilities, as ENTRUST's high-end devices. For their low-end counterparts, the syndrome based approach is more adequate, without affecting the security requirements posed, and consequently it will constitute the fundamental building block for the implementation considered here. In the following subsection the scheme adopted is presented in details.

4.3.1.3 ENTRUST's PUF-based Key Generation and Reconstruction for Low-End Devices

In Figure 4.4 the key generation and reconstruction scheme, following a syndrome-based fuzzy extractor approach, utilizing the SRAM-PUF of the low-end device is presented. The proposed scheme is a modified version of [32] and it was successfully implemented very recently in [4] utilizing another type of silicon-based PUF class (arbiter-PUF) which is implemented on a device (Xilinx ARTIX-7 FPGA) with by far greater computational capabilities than a typical CMD. In subsection 4.3.2, the evaluation results of the proposed implementation will be presented, highlighting that the constructed scheme is also applicable when SRAM-PUFs and resource-constrained devices are considered.

As mentioned in [19], due to the embedded SRAM capacity of the Arduino Mega 2560 (i.e. 8K bytes), there are some crucial design aspects that have to be considered for the efficient operation of the proposed PUF. Those aspects revolve around the BCH error correction code parameters. BCH codes are a very flexible set of codes in that within certain bounds there is a great amount of choice in code parameters and are relatively efficient in message length and error correction. The code parameters are as follows [45]:

- q : The number of symbols used ($q = 2$ in binary field)
- m : The power to which to raise q to generate a Galois Field for the construction of the code. High m values are translated to elevated memory needs, thus the chosen m here is 6, requiring 4553 bytes i.e around 55% of total SRAM available in Arduino Mega 2560.
- d : The minimum designed Hamming distance between generated and reconstructed PUF responses

These parameters lead to several derived parameters which are standard parameters of linear codes:

- n : The size of the multiplicative group of Galois Field given by $n = 2^m - 1$. Here, is the length of the PUF response.

Figure 4.4: Implementation diagram using a syndrome-based fuzzy extractor for generating and reconstructing a key 256-bit long from the SRAM-PUF instance of ENTRUST.

- t : The number of errors that can be corrected where $d \geq 2t + 1$
- k : The number of message bits in a codeword i.e. the length of the PUF-based key

Having as a prerequisite that $m = 6$ based on the equation above $n = 63$. Such a combination, results in various k and t values that can be found from the corresponding tables in [46]. To maximize the error correction capability, $k = 7$ and $t = 15$ were selected. In order to generate a 256-bits long PUF-based key and since one block of the aforementioned BCH scheme needs 63 bits long response for 7 bit key strength, 37 blocks of this scheme are required. Thus, a PUF response of 2331 bits is needed.

As shown in the figure above, the **generation phase** was initiated upon a challenge (C) application on the PUF instance. The methodology followed for the creation of the challenges pool based on data remanence approach was described thoroughly in [19]. Following that, the PUF response of 2331 bits ($N = 2331$) on that challenge is generated and a key size of 256 bits ($K = 256$) is fed into the BCH encoder resulting in 2331 bit value. This value is then subjected to an XOR operation with the original, prior to the encoding, response. The $N - K$ bit sequence of the resulting value, which is 2075 bits here, constitutes the syndrome S . The syndrome S along with the corresponding challenge C , i.e. helper data, are stored in a database and include all the information needed to recover the PUF-based 256-bit key. During the **reconstruction phase**, in the presence of a challenge C and the corresponding syndrome S , a noisy PUF response of N bits is generated. The $N - K$ syndrome is subjected to a "0" padding process (256 "0"s are inserted prior the first bit of the $N - K$ sequence) resulting to a syndrome S' . Then, the noisy PUF response is XORed with S' and the resulting value is then subjected to BCH decoding, yielding the noise-mitigated version of the enrolled PUF-based 256-bit key.

4.3.2 Evaluation Metrics

Having described the PUF-based key generation and reconstruction scheme utilized in the context of ENTRUST to enhance the security posture of low-end CMDs, in this subsection the evaluation metrics of the aforementioned process are presented. To that end, the crucial characteristics of the proposed SRAM-PUF instance introduced in [19] are evaluated again but now at a key level. In [19], the essential PUF properties, namely robustness, unpredictability and unclonability, are initially determined from the raw PUF responses captured under the specific evaluation conditions that each property dictates (for the robustness measurement the same challenge applied in the same SRAM module, for the unpredictability different challenges applied in same SRAM module, whereas for the unclonability measurement the same challenges applied but in several SRAM modules). Despite the fact that the results acquired [19] revealed the exceptional characteristics of the proposed PUF instance, this preliminary analysis was limited to bit-level. Now, based on the key generation and reconstruction scheme presented in the previous section, the aforementioned properties at a key-level are described.

Here, in order to evaluate the robustness of the keys extracted following the scheme presented in Figure 4.4, an SRAM module was mounted in the experimental setup (see Figure 3.4 [19]), and a challenge was applied in order to generate the initial key along with the corresponding syndrome. Then, the resulting syndrome is used as an input along with the same challenge, to initiate the reconstruction phase. This procedure was repeated for 100 times over a reasonable time frame and the Fractional Hamming Distance (FHD) between the reconstructed keys and the initial was calculated. For the unpredictability, following its formal definition found in [5], in the same SRAM module different challenges (C_i) were applied and the corresponding syndromes (S_i) along with the PUF-based keys (K_i) were generated. During the reconstruction phase, the challenge C_{i+1} was applied to the PUF instance and a key was reconstructed by using the syndrome S_i . Then, the FHD between the corresponding reconstructed and initial keys was determined. Finally, for the unclonability evaluation, a set of challenges and syndromes as extracted from a specific SRAM module was applied to similar SRAM chips. Then, the FHD between the extracted keys from all SRAM modules tested was calculated. The FHDs of the aforementioned experiments are presented in Figure 4.5.

As seen from the figure above, in terms of robustness, it is evident that the proposed PUF instance along with the key generation and reproduction scheme employed, is capable of reproducing the enrolled key, upon the application of the corresponding challenge and the syndrome constructed during the generation phase, for 100 consecutive times. Thus, as expected, by utilizing the syndrome-based fuzzy extractor described above, the raw outputs of the SRAM-PUF in the same challenge (the FHD distribution at bit-level was centered around 2.14% as depicted in the inset of Figure 4.5) was decoupled from the noise effects (the FHD at key-level is 0%) and the proposed PUF instance exhibit the desired property which is crucial when authentication applications are considered.

In terms of unpredictability and unclonability, it is evident that by utilizing the scheme presented in Figure 4.4 their corresponding distributions are enhanced in terms of uniformity while maintaining their elevated characteristics in terms of randomness. Thus, with the selected error correction code parameters no entropy loss is observed. Also, robustness and unpredictability as well as unclonability distributions remained well-separated, without the presence of overlaps between them, highlighting the extracted PUF-key uniqueness feature and that the creation of an identical clone of such a module is almost not feasible even by the manufacturer per se. It has to be noted that the results presented here are extracted for the specific set of challenges and the specific SRAM modules tested. Since the crucial evaluation metrics of any PUF configuration are statistical magnitudes, the aforementioned experiments should be expanded by utilizing a more extended set of challenges to study the unpredictability, whereas more SRAM chips have to be tested in order to validate further the presented findings.

4.3.3 Key Derivation Function (KDF) in the Context of ENTRUST's Low-End CMDs

Since low-end CMDs have limited computational resources, advanced cryptographic operations can not be performed, in contrast with high-end devices. Thus, to support runtime attestation of low-end CMDs and towards creating an equivalent of the high-end devices approach where key-restriction usage policies are utilized to enable local implicit attestation, a novel Key Derivation Function (KDF) was introduced for the final key extraction.

In the context of ENTRUST, the proposed KDF is presented in Figure 4.6. In order to generate the final key, the KDF is fed with two distinct inputs. The former is the PUF-based key, which is generated following the procedure and

Figure 4.5: The SRAM modules’ crucial characteristics, namely robustness (red), unpredictability (orange) and unclonability (blue), in terms of FHD, as extracted utilizing the scheme presented in Figure 4.4 i.e. at key-level. In the inset, the corresponding bit-level analysis is depicted for comparison.

the scheme described above, whereas the latter is a device-specific system property extracted from the ENTRUST’ Tracer. Following that approach, the high entropy of the final key is maintained since the PUF-based key contains a sufficient amount of randomness, in a reproducible manner. In essence, this is the main feature exploited here for the authentication and verification of low-end CMDs. Also, by inserting a device-specific system property enables the local attestation capabilities of the CMD. For instance, one system property that can be utilized for the final key generation and reconstruction is the secure boot hash. Thus, by combining the aforementioned property with a PUF-based key, a verifier is capable of acquiring knowledge regarding the correct boot state of the device every time such a final key is reconstructed. Since the verifier is aware of the secure boot hash as well as the PUF-based keys, in case the secure boot of the specific device fails, the device will be not authenticated. Another system property that can be employed instead of a static property such as the secure boot hash, is the stack information, a device attribute that contains details regarding the stack usage including size and memory address crucial for memory management and debugging, which when extracted, control-flow integrity can be enabled. Since control-flow integrity is a dynamic measurement, upon a request for a final key reconstruction, if such a system property deviates from the expected one, which is an indication of risk, the verifier will not authenticate the specific CMD. It has to be noted that low-end CMDs are equipped with a real-time operating system from which information regarding the runtime system measurements can be extracted. Thus, by leveraging the proposed KDF any runtime property extracted, can potentially be used as a parameter for the final key generation and reconstruction to support the local implicit attestation.

Essentially, by utilizing the KDF proposed here to generate an HMAC-key binding the PUF-based key with a system property, two crucial for the security posture of the low-end devices aspects are fulfilled:

Figure 4.6: The context of KDF utilized for ENTRUST's low-end CMDs.

1. Establishment of a secret between the low-end device and any verifier that intends to authenticate such a device
2. Enabling of the low-end device authentication considering non repudiation, i.e. the high-end device will not be able to act on behalf of the low-end device without the approval of the latter (see subsection 5.5)

Chapter 5

ENTRUST Secure Lifecycle Management

This chapter delves into the cryptographic functionalities that underpin the ENTRUST Secure Lifecycle Management of CMDs. These functionalities facilitate the informational flow within ENTRUST's Trusted Execution Architecture, discussed in Chapter 2, by leveraging the cryptographic building blocks introduced in Chapter 3. These blocks are supported by ENTRUST's Trusted Computing Base, as outlined in Chapter 4.

Section 5.1 explores Zero-Trust Onboarding, followed by ENTRUST Runtime Trusted Execution Services in Section 5.2. Enhanced Authorization with Run-Time Verifiable Key Restriction Usage Policies is covered in Section 5.3. Section 5.4 discusses Low-End CMD Attestation, Section 5.5 details Conformity Certificates, Section 5.6 examines VPs during the Run-Time Phase, and Section 5.7 concludes with a Security Analysis.

5.1 Zero-Trust Onboarding

5.1.1 Device Authentication & VC Issuance

In the ENTRUST framework, each device is accompanied by a set of attributes that represent its hardware-based security controls that are used to prove trust assurances. The Privacy CA issues the corresponding attribute keys under the CMD's binding property, that is the CMD's unique identifier. This unique identifier, as part of ENTRUST's envisioned solution is based on the HW-based key for an enhanced level of assurance. In the context of ENTRUST, and as part of the high-end CMD, it is the HW-based Root ID key that is used for this binding. This means that the Privacy CA binds the attribute keys to the public part of the Root ID key of the device.

The attribute keys will be used by the device to demonstrate that it processes the necessary attributes that are needed to satisfy a certain policy during the onboarding or run-time phase. Note that the general policy is a form of an access control tree as in Figure 3.2. For instance, a policy can be defined so that a device has to prove that it has a combination of attributes that allows other CMD to evaluate its overall trust state when establishing a trust relationship with it. This is achieved through the self-issuance of VPs.

During the run-time phase, the device should be capable of selectively disclosing a subset of attributes based on the construction of "trust predicates." These predicates enable the zero-knowledge proof of ownership of specific attributes without disclosing the type of attributes or their exact values, which could otherwise lead to implementation disclosure attacks. To meet such requirement that allows a CMD to prove the ownership of a set of attributes that satisfy a certain trust predicate without disclosing the attribute value, ENTRUST designed the novel, efficient, Attribute-based Signature (ABS) and Attribute-based Signcryption (ABSC) schemes.

In our ABS and ABSC schemes, we follow the FABEO construction where the access control tree is translated to an access control matrix through the LSSS technique explained in Chapter 3. The Privacy CA defines the general policy matrix M , which contains the universal set of attributes that are defined by the CA under a general policy.

The attribute keys for each device are issued based on the policy M following the construction of the KP-ABE

schemes. Any sub-policy \mathcal{P} that ABS or ABSC should satisfy during the VP-issuance is then derived from \mathbf{M} . This has no impact on the ABS and ABSC schemes that don't support attribute anonymity (Section 5.1.2), however, it may increase the signature size in case anonymity is required by issuing extra Schnorr-signatures. In ENTRUST, we are dealing with a relatively small universe attributes set \mathcal{U} (around 20-30 attributes are defined in total), therefore our KP-ABS and KP-ABSC will still provide better efficiency than the existing schemes even when attribute anonymity is required.

Our construction leads to efficient ABS and ABSC protocols that heavily reduce the costs of signing and verification compared to the existing protocols. The efficiency of our ABS and ABSC protocols is achieved regardless of the number of attributes that are needed in the policy. The verification requires only a maximum of five pairings (two pairing in the schemes presented in Section 5.6) regardless of the number of attributes.

Figure 5.1 depicts the issuance of the attribute keys for the ABS and ABSC schemes presented in Section 5.1.2. We then present the details of creating and verifying ABS and ABSC in Section 5.1.2.

Figure 5.1: Issuance of the Attribute Keys by the Privacy CA

5.1.2 High- & Low-End device Enrollment to Target Domain

As explained in Chapter 2, the ABSC will be used during domain enrolment to sign and encrypt the user domain key DK_E under certain policies. This domain key (which is different for each device, the same as any attribute key) is used to prove the possession of a certain attribute that represents correct domain enrolment. Upon successful issuance of the domain key from the Privacy CA, the DM then certifies this key and initiates an Attribute-based Signcryption. The DM creates an Attribute-based Signature under some of its attributes that satisfy a policy \mathcal{P} . The DM then encrypts the domain key under a policy \mathcal{P}' that allows the device to decrypt the message and retrieve the domain key only if it holds a certain set of attributes satisfying the policy \mathcal{P}' . Finally, the DM sends the signcrypted message with the two policies to the device. The device then verifies the DM signature and decrypts the cipher text. Our attribute-based signcryption scheme used in the enrolment phase supports neither the signer's nor the receiver's attribute anonymity. This scheme does not include "a designated verifier signature", meaning that only the right receiver can verify it. In this scheme, given a signature, any verifier can check whether it was signed by using a certain policy with a specific set of attributes. On the other hand, only designated receivers can decrypt the message. Note that the domain key that is issued by the CA for a specific device is bound to the device's root identity key. So this key cannot be used by any other device with a different Root ID key. We now present the crypto details of the ABSC scheme that will be adopted in the ENTRUST enrolment phase:

Setup(1^λ) \rightarrow (PK_{CA}, SK_{CA}) .

- Take the security parameter λ as input.
- Pick $\alpha \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p$ and $H : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{G}_1$.

- Compute $\mathcal{G} := (p, \mathbb{G}_1, \mathbb{G}_2, \mathbb{G}_T, e, g_1, g_2)$ and $PK_{CA} := (\mathcal{G}, H, e(g_1, g_2)^\alpha)$.
- Let $SK_{CA} := \alpha$.

$sKeyGen(SK_{CA}, (\mathbf{M}, \pi)) \rightarrow sk$. This key generation algorithm outputs a set of attribute keys for someone who plays the role of a sender which is the DM in our case.

- The Privacy CA selects the attributes assigned to the sender and sends every attribute $\pi(i) \in \mathcal{S}$.
- The sender with a root key ($rsk = x, rpk = g_2^x$), replies with $\sigma_{(i)} = H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^x$, for all $\pi(i) \in \mathcal{S}$.
- The Privacy CA verifies each $\sigma_{(i)}$ under rpk . If the verification is successful, the Privacy CA proceeds as follows:
 - Pick $\mathbf{r} \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p, \mathbf{v} \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p^{n_2-1}$.
 - Compute $sk_1 := g_2^{\mathbf{r}}$, and $sk_{2,i} := g_1^{M_i(\alpha || \mathbf{v})^T} \cdot \sigma_i^{\mathbf{r}}$ for each row $i \in \mathcal{I}$.
 - Output $sk := (sk_1, (sk_{2,i})_{i \in \mathcal{I}})$.

$rKeyGen(SK_{CA}, (\mathbf{M}', \pi')) \rightarrow sk'$. This key generation algorithm outputs a set of attribute keys for someone who plays the receiver's role (the high-end device).

- The Privacy CA selects the attributes assigned to the receiver and sends every attribute $\pi'(i) \in \mathcal{S}'$.
- The receiver with a root key ($rsk' = x', rpk' = g_2^{x'}$), replies with $\sigma'_{(i)} = H_1(i || h_m || \pi'(i))^{x'}$, for all $\pi'(i) \in \mathcal{S}'$.
- The Privacy CA verifies each $\sigma'_{(i)}$ under rpk' .
- Pick $\mathbf{r}' \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p, \mathbf{v}' \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p^{n'_2-1}$.
- Compute $sk'_1 := g_2^{\mathbf{r}'}$, and $sk'_{2,i} := g_1^{M'_i(\alpha || \mathbf{v}')^T} \cdot \sigma'^{\mathbf{r}'}$ for each row $i \in \mathcal{I}'$.
- Output $sk' := (sk'_1, (sk'_{2,i})_{i \in \mathcal{I}'})$.

$SignEnc(sk, \mathcal{S} \cup \mathcal{S}' \subseteq \mathcal{U}, msg) \rightarrow \sigma$. \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{S}' include the sender and receiver's attributes respectively. To create a signcryption on the domain key, the DM proceeds as follows:

- Pick $s \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p$.
- Compute $\sigma_1 := sk_1^{x/s}, \sigma_{2,i} := sk_{2,i}^s$ for each row $i \in \mathcal{I}$ such that $\pi(i)$ is needed for the signer's policy (\mathbf{M}, π) , $\sigma_{3,i} = H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^s$ for each $\pi(i) \in \mathcal{S} \cup \mathcal{S}'$, $\sigma_4 := g_2^s, \sigma_5 = g_2^{1/s}, \sigma_6 = e(g_1, g_2)^{\alpha s} \cdot msg$, where msg represents the device's domain key, $\sigma_7 = H(\sigma_6)^s$.
- Output $\sigma := (\sigma_1, (\sigma_{2,i})_{i \in \mathcal{I}}, (\sigma_{3,i})_{\pi(i) \in \mathcal{S} \cup \mathcal{S}'}, \sigma_4, \sigma_5, \sigma_6, \sigma_7)$.

$VerifyDec(PK_{CA}, \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{S}', (\mathbf{M}, \pi), (\mathbf{M}', \pi'), \sigma, msg) \rightarrow 0/1$. The high-end device proceeds as follows:

- If \mathcal{S} does not satisfy (\mathbf{M}, π) or \mathcal{S}' does not satisfy (\mathbf{M}', π') , output 0.
- Otherwise, if

$$e\left(\prod_{\pi(i) \in \mathcal{S}} \sigma_{3,i} \cdot \sigma_7, g_2\right) \neq e\left(\prod_{\pi(i) \in \mathcal{S}} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i)) \cdot H(\sigma_6), \sigma_4\right),$$

output 0.

- Otherwise, if

$$\frac{e\left(\prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\sigma_{2,i})^{\gamma_i}, \sigma_5\right)}{e\left(\prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\sigma_{3,i})^{\gamma_i}, \sigma_1\right)} \neq e(g_1, g_2)^\alpha,$$

output 0.

If stopped here, this ABSC is reduced to the ABS scheme. The decryptor retrieves the encrypted message (domain key) as follows:

- Otherwise, output 1 and compute

$$\text{Domain key} = \frac{\sigma_6 \cdot \prod e\left(\prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}'} ((\sigma_{3,i})^{\gamma'_i}, \text{sk}'_{1,x'})\right)}{e\left(\prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}'} (\text{sk}'_{2,i})^{\gamma'_i}, \sigma_4\right)}.$$

Signer	Verifier
$(rsk, rpki), (sk_1, sk_{2,i})$	$S, rpki, M$
Pick $s \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p$ Compute $\sigma_1 := \text{sk}_1^{x/s}$ $\sigma_{2,i} := \text{sk}_{2,i}^s$ for each row $i \in \mathcal{I}$ $\sigma_{3,i} = H_1(i h_m \pi(i))^s$ for each $\pi(i) \in \mathcal{S} \cup \mathcal{S}'$ $\sigma_4 := g_2^s$ $\sigma_5 := g_2^{1/s}$ $\sigma_6 = e(g_1, g_2)^{\alpha s} \cdot \text{msg}$ $\sigma_7 = H(\sigma_6)^s$ $\sigma := (\sigma_1, (\sigma_{2,i})_{i \in [n_1]}, (\sigma_{3,i})_{\pi(i) \in \mathcal{S}}, \sigma_4, \sigma_5, \sigma_6, \sigma_7)$	
	$\xrightarrow{\sigma}$ Checks the following $\frac{e\left(\prod_{\pi(i) \in \mathcal{S}} \sigma_{3,i} \sigma_7, g_2\right)}{e\left(\prod_{\pi(i) \in \mathcal{S}} H_1(i h_m \pi(i)) \cdot H(\sigma_6), \sigma_4\right)} \stackrel{?}{=} \frac{e\left(\prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\sigma_{2,i})^{\gamma_i}, \sigma_5\right)}{e\left(\prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\sigma_{3,i})^{\gamma_i}, \sigma_1\right)} \stackrel{?}{=} e(g_1, g_2)^\alpha$

Figure 5.2: ABSC without attribute anonymity (Signcrypt phase)

Signer	Decryptor
$(rsk, rpki), (sk_1, sk_{2,i})$	$(rsk', rpki'), (sk'_1, sk'_{2,i})$
	$\xrightarrow{\sigma}$ $\text{msg} = \frac{\sigma_6 \cdot \prod e\left(\prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}'} ((\sigma_{3,i})^{\gamma'_i}, \text{sk}'_{1,x'})\right)}{e\left(\prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}'} (\text{sk}'_{2,i})^{\gamma'_i}, \sigma_4\right)}.$

Figure 5.3: ABSC without attribute anonymity (Decryption phase)

5.2 ENTRUST Runtime Trusted Execution Services

5.2.1 High-End Device Attestation

As have been previously outlined, **ENTRUST** employs sophisticated attestation mechanisms so as to ensure the validity of all *trust aspects* defined by **ENTRUST's** trust model, such as integrity, safety, and resiliency, ENTRUST employs advanced attestation mechanisms. One such mechanism is the **Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV)**. This mechanism enables the runtime monitoring of device state evidence in a verifiable manner, assessing various facets of the device's trust profile. The CIV ensures that the integrity, safety, and resilience of the device are continuously verified, providing robust security and trustworthiness in real-time.

To this end, we are presenting a *Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV)* attestation scheme for all High-End devices equipped with a Trusted Execution Environment (**TEE**), based on the notion of **Attestation by Proof**. Advanced attestation mechanisms are provided for both high-end and low-end devices, focusing on two important dimensions: efficiency and privacy-preserving attestation. This ensures the ability to provide proof of the trust level of a device without disclosing any details about its internal state.

More specifically, we introduce a challenge-response protocol, where a Verifier challenges the Prover to provide attestation evidence over its runtime configuration using a fresh nonce. **If** the Prover can successfully respond to the Verifier's challenge—by producing a valid signature with its Attestation Key—then the Verifier can ascertain that the Prover is in a correct configuration state. By constructing a valid signature, the Prover provides attestation evidence in a **zero knowledge** manner, as it does not disclose any information about the actual trace. This approach eliminates potential implementation disclosure attacks.

This attestation by proof modality is a novel approach we offer, facilitating implicit attestation to enable zero-knowledge device trust assessment, thereby reinforcing the security and trustworthiness of the device in a highly efficient and privacy-preserving manner.

Therefore, in the rest of this section, we present the design of the **ENTRUST** enhanced Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV) attestation scheme, which is capable of enhanced authorization key access by creating the **Key Restriction Usage** for separating the local from the global Attestation Keys.

In this scheme, the global attestation key is a cryptographic key used to provide trustworthiness evidence, enabling the trust assessment of the device. This key is central to verifying the device's overall security posture. On the other hand, the local attestation key pertains to a key restriction usage policy. This policy dictates the conditions under which the global attestation key will be accessible. Essentially, the local attestation key sets the requirements that must be met for the global attestation key to be utilized.

By establishing this separation, ENTRUST ensures a more granular control over the attestation process. The local attestation key enforces specific conditions and requirements, and only when these are satisfied is the global attestation key granted access. This layered approach enhances security by ensuring that the global attestation key, which is crucial for the device's trust assessment, is only used under stringent, predefined conditions.

In this context, the **ENTRUST** Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV) scheme aims to minimize the trust assumptions of any device participating in the **ENTRUST** ecosystem as we transition towards a **ZERO TRUST** architecture. Zero Trust is a security model that assumes no implicit trust and requires continuous verification of device trustworthiness, regardless of their location within or outside the network.

As previously outlined, the **ENTRUST** CIV scheme, which will be detailed in the following section, focuses on the **ZERO-KNOWLEDGE** variant of ENTRUST's attestation capabilities. It focuses on elevating the security of the system by establishing a Policy-Restricted Attestation Key as the pivotal trust anchor for the attestation process. It enables enhanced authorization mechanisms, thus ensuring that the Prover's Attestation Key can be used if and only if a specific set of policies are satisfied. These policies are defined by the Domain Manager and are representing the device's expected state based on the respective **Enhanced MUD profile**, where there are stored all the reference values of each security critical service and property of a device. To be more precise, these policies dictate how the Prover's key can be utilized, allowing it to sign challenges solely when its configuration complies with predefined criteria. This rigorous verification process encompasses both the configuration of the hosted application

and the enclave responsible for handling attestation mechanisms. Importantly, verification is achieved through a secure challenge-response protocol that safeguards the configuration details of a device by abstracting them in the overall attestation process.

Moreover, as described in deliverable D4.1, we need to provide support for both software updates regarding the software stack of the High-End devices and Software/firmware updates on the Low-End devices. Such updates shall take place, in order to introduce new functionalities, optimise routines and last but of paramount importance to eliminate any identified vulnerability, through the continuous vulnerability analysis performed in the Attack Emulation component established as part of the ENTRUST's Digital Twin. It goes without saying, such actions lead to a change of the configuration of the devices both on the Trusted world and the UnTrusted world. Consequently, the previously established Key Restriction Usage Policy becomes invalid, even if the software/firmware upgrade proceeds without errors. This scenario significantly broadens the attack surface by allowing a compromised HOST to maintain two distinct valid policies. This enables the creation of legitimate signatures even while the device engages in malicious behavior. By managing separate sets of policies—one benign and one malicious—the HOST can deceive verifiers, producing valid cryptographic signatures based on the expected legitimate policy. Consequently, verifiers are misled into trusting a compromised device, undermining the entire trust model. This dual policy capability complicates integrity verification, broadens the potential for undetected exploits, and erodes the system's overall security posture. To counteract this, the ENTRUST framework must implement more stringent validation mechanisms, continuous monitoring, and anomaly detection to ensure robust protection against such sophisticated attacks. To address this issue, ENTRUST's CIV introduces time-limited policies, empowering the Key Management to regulate which policy can be enforced at any given moment.

As previously mentioned, the ENTRUST CIV scheme aims to dynamically verify that the software or firmware hosted within a device is the current version and not an outdated one. Specifically, the enhanced Entrust CIV scheme aims to prevent any unauthorized rollback or denial of updates, unless explicitly permitted by a security policy, issued of course by the Domain Manager. This challenge is well-recognized in the community, and the enhanced Entrust CIV scheme addresses it directly.

Our innovation lies in enabling the Prover to present Attestation Evidence whilst verifying the correctness of the configuration and confirming the expected software version in a zero knowledge manner. To meet the security requirements for all the TEE-capable devices regarding the policy freshness, we introduce a new component into our Trusted Computing Base known as the **Verifiable Policy Enforcer (VPE)**. The VPE's role includes attesting to the version of the running TEE application and ensuring that outdated Key Restriction Usage Policies are deemed obsolete.

5.2.2 System Setup & Notation

In ENTRUST, as mentioned, we are planning to adopt a CIV scheme for all High-End devices within a medical ecosystem, To this end, all the TEE-capable devices that have been on boarded into ENTRUST's infrastructure must provide verifiable attestation evidence proving their configuration correctness while meeting the security requirements set by the Domain Manager. This process is dictated through the instantiation of trust policies, which outline the specific criteria and methods for attestation. The Trust Assessment Framework (TAF) initiates the attestation process based on these policies.

1. **Periodic (Synchronous) Attestation:** The TAF periodically requests attestation evidence from the device at regular intervals. This ensures continuous monitoring of the device's state and timely detection of any deviations from the expected configuration.
2. **Asynchronous Attestation:** The TAF triggers attestation when there is a change in the device's overall trust level. This could be due to events such as software updates, configuration changes, or detected anomalies. By initiating attestation in response to such changes, the TAF ensures that any potential security issues are promptly addressed.

Throughout this process, the TAF collects and evaluates the attestation evidence provided by the devices. The evidence must demonstrate that the devices meet the security requirements and are operating in their correct

configuration. By enforcing these trust policies and continuously monitoring the attestation evidence, ENTRUST ensures the integrity, security, and trustworthiness of its infrastructure. Specifically, to describe the ENTRUST-enhanced CIV scheme, we consider the following roles.

- **Prover:** A TEE-capable device equipped with a certified identity key by the manufacturer. In ENTRUST, we design our schemes agnostically in order to be adoptable by any Trusted Computing Base. That being said for implementation purposes we focus on **OP-TEE**-enabled devices, a well established solution in the Trusted Computing arsenal for developing trusted applications in ARM architectures. Each Prover is equipped with three internal functional components as part of their Trusted Computing Base:
 1. The **Key Manager:** Responsible for managing the creation and usage of the Attestation Key of the respective device, assumed to be running as part of the trusted world (protected/isolated by the OP-TEE TrustZone).
 2. A **Runtime (Attestation) Tracer:** Responsible for monitoring and reporting runtime measurements of applications/functions critical to the device's safety throughout its lifecycle. The tracer operates in both the trusted and untrusted worlds, but all security-critical functionalities are hosted within the trusted world. Specifically, the untrusted part of the Tracer fetches raw traces of the attested application, while the trusted part decodes these raw traces to calculate the runtime configuration hash and executes all cryptographic operations within the tracer.
 3. The **Verifiable Policy Enforcer (VPE):** Part of the Trusted Computing Base, trusted post-secure On-Boarding, and thus impossible to compromise during runtime. In ENTRUST, security mechanisms prevent denial of software update attacks. The VPE is authorized to check during runtime whether the versions of the Attestation Agent, the Tracer, and any other security-critical applications running within an enclave are as expected, defending against denial of software updates.
- **Verifier:** Moving towards a Zero Trust architecture, the Verifier is an untrusted device that wants to remotely check the correctness of the Prover's configuration. In ENTRUST, we are Our scheme is agnostic to the nature of the Verifier and does not inherently make any trust assumptions. However, in the case of low-end devices, the Verifier can be a high-end device, for which we make certain trust assumptions. Similarly, for high-end devices, the Verifier is typically the Trust Assessment Framework (TAF), which is trusted within the system. Nonetheless, this scheme can be expanded to include other Verifiers, such as external auditors, for which specific trust relationships must be established. Therefore, strong cryptographic mechanisms must be employed to enable the verification of every step in the attestation chain while preserving the Prover's privacy. These cryptographic mechanisms ensure that even when different Verifiers are involved, the integrity and confidentiality of the attestation process are maintained. The Verifier is also equipped with OP-TEE to host trusted applications.
- **Domain Manager:** In the context of ENTRUST, the Domain Manager is considered a trusted entity. For the CIV attestation mechanisms, the Domain Manager is responsible for:
 1. Managing the Secure On-Boarding of each device wishing to enroll in the ENTRUST infrastructure.
 2. Establishing a secret key into the VPE, blinded with the correct configuration of the other TCB components.
 3. Maintaining and authorizing each device's approved configuration, leading to the definition of new key usage restriction policies.

5.2.3 Enhanced CIV - High Level Overview

Having outlined all the entities and components involved in the ENTRUST CIV scheme, we will now delve into the architectural details and internal operations of the newly designed scheme. The protocol comprises two main phases, namely: i) **JOIN** and ii) **Runtime Attestation**. During the JOIN phase, the Domain Manager establishes the Key Restriction Usage Policies under which the attestation keys shall be bound and generates the VPE key. In the Runtime Attestation phase, the attested device is challenged by a Verifier to produce attestation evidence.

5.2.3.1 JOIN Phase

1. Consider a new TEE-capable High-End device that wishes to join the Connected Medical devices (CMD) ecosystem. First, the device must successfully complete the secure On-Boarding protocol to acquire a Verifiable Credential containing the necessary attributes that will grant the device access to the Domain Manager.
2. Once the On-Boarding protocol is successfully completed, the device creates its own Attestation Key pair, bound to the appropriate Key Restriction Usage Policy (i.e., authorization from the Domain Manager).
3. Next, the Domain Manager takes the necessary steps to authorize the Attestation Key. The Domain Manager extracts from the eMUD profiles the reference values of the applications targeted by the attestation mechanisms to compute the accepted configuration of the Prover. In addition to the reference values of safety-critical applications, the Domain Manager considers as the configuration of the Prover (High-End) device the reference values of the Prover's Enclave applications and validations from the Tracer and the VPE. The expected configuration is signed and sent back to the High-End device for use during runtime.
4. The On-Boarded High-End device receives the digital signature produced by the Domain Manager and proceeds to create the Attestation Key bound with the corresponding (issued) Key Restriction Usage Policy. The Attestation Key structure (including the Attestation Public Key, the Hashed Attestation Private Key, the Attestation Key Name, and the random co-seed key generator) is then stored in the Key Manager of the Trusted application.
5. The VPE then retrieves the Attestation Key Name from the Key Manager and requests the Domain Manager to create the VPE Key pair, which is bound to a key restriction usage policy representing the correct configuration and versioning of the Attestation Agent, the Tracer, and any other safety-critical artifact hosted on the High-End device. The VPE Key binding is achieved by encrypting its private part with the respective policy. The VPE Key is then injected into the High-End device's VPE.
6. When both the Attestation Key and the VPE key are set up correctly the Domain Manager, in respect to the privacy requirements dictated by the MUD profiles, proceeds to triggering the DAA Join phase. Thus converting the Attestation Key to a DAA key. As its High-end device will act as the gateway and Verifier for numerous Low-End devices, through the a DAA key, we are aiming to enable anonymous swarm attestation schemes for scalable runtime attestation of the Low-End devices.

5.3 Enhanced Authorization with Run-Time Verifiable Key Restriction Usage Policies

1. Considering a Trust Assessment Framework (TAF) that wishes to attest a High-End device participating in the service graph chain of the **ENTRUST** infrastructure, it will initiate a challenge-based attestation protocol. The TAF, acting as the Verifier, will send a challenge to the device to request attestation evidence.
2. When the Attestation Agent of the Prover receives the challenge, he goes off to create a fresh nonce and forwards it to the VPE to initiate the attestation process.
3. Upon receiving the Attestation Agent's nonce, the VPE generates another fresh nonce. Both nonces are then forwarded to the Tracer for signing, ensuring protection against replay attacks.
4. The Tracer executes its tracing algorithms to extract the runtime security measurements of the targeted application, whether we are attesting its configuration (CIV) or its execution flow (CFA/CFI). Upon extracting the appropriate measurements, the Tracer signs the extracted values bound to the nonce provided by the Attestation Agent. Additionally, it signs the measurement of the enclave environment, binding it to the nonce initially created by the VPE. Both signatures are then sent back to the VPE. By verifying these two signatures, both the VPE and the Attestation Agent acquire proof of the Tracer's liveness, ensuring the authenticity and integrity of the attestation process.

5. The VPE will then attempt to access its injected key by satisfying the Key Restriction Usage Policy set by the Domain Manager. If the Key Restriction Usage Policy is met, the VPE signs the accepted software version of the Attestation Agent, binding it to the nonce issued by the Attestation Agent.
6. The Attestation Agent receives the two signatures, the signed runtime trace of the UnTrusted application and signed software version, and initiates the enhanced access control mechanism to use the prover's Attestation key. To satisfy the Key Restriction Usage Policy, the Attestation Agent computes a runtime configuration from the enclave measurements and by verifying the two signatures. Upon successful completion of the policy enforcement algorithm the Key Manager creates a digital signature over the initial challenge received from the Verifier.

5.3.1 Architectural Blueprint & Mode of Operation

In what follows, we provide a detailed overview containing all the details of the ENTRUST CIV scheme, along with all the interactions between all involved components. Throughout this Section, we elaborate on each of the phases of the designed protocol.

5.3.1.1 JOIN & Verifiable Policy Enforcement Building Blocks

Next, we describe the **JOIN** interface initiated by the Secure Enrolment module, which is performed when a High-End device has completed the Secure On-Boarding protocol and acquired a Verifiable Credential granting it access to the Domain Manager. The Domain Manager, acting as a Trusted Entity, is responsible for issuing and validating the Key Restriction Usage Policies for each High-End device that wishes to participate in the ENTRUST ecosystem, as well as for creating unique key pairs for every VPE. It should be highlighted that the Verifiable Policy Enforcer (VPE) is instantiated in a different enclave as it is part of ENTRUST's Trusted Computing Base, alongside the Key Manager. Given all the above, the actions followed in the context of the Join phase are shown in Figure 5.4, and are described as follows:

1. Assuming that the Secure On-Boarding is completed successfully, the Secure Enrolment module initiates the Enhanced CIV JOIN phase.
2. If the device is granted access, the Domain Manager calculates the Key Restriction Usage Policy that is to be enforced to the Attestation Key. With the newly calculated policy the High-End device's Key Manager proceeds to create its own Attestation Key.
3. The Domain Manager then calculates the Key Restriction Usage Policy that the VPE Key should be bound and proceeds to calculate the Key pair of the VPE, $VPE_{priv} = KDF(random)$, $VPE_{pub} = VPE_{priv} * G$. Afterwards the Domain Manager with that Policy Digest, Encrypts the VPE_{priv} and computes its Hash Digest, $VPE_{HASH} = H(VPE_{priv})$, in order to finalise the creation of the VPE Key structure. The VPE Key structure is going to be wrapped properly and sent to the VPE enclave.
 - The **VPE Policy** represents that the VPE is indeed running on the approved version, that the application is actually signed by the Security Administrator and finally that the version of the Tracer is the expected one.
4. With the VPE key creation now finalised, the Domain Manager computes the accepted configuration of the High-End device and signs it with his own private key. Thus creating an Authorisation Ticket.
 - The High-End device's accepted configuration is dependent on the enclave measurement of the Attestation Agent, on the runtime value acquired by the Tracer and finally on the response of both the Tracer and the VPE.

Figure 5.4: ENTRUST Verifiable Key Restriction Policy Update: JOIN

5. The Domain Manager creates two encrypted and authenticated secrets, the first secret is determined for the VPE and contains the Encrypted VPE_{priv} , the VPE_{HASH} , the approved enclave measurement of the Attestation Agent and the approved enclave measurement of the Tracer. The other secret is destined for the Attestation Agent and contains the Authorisation Ticket and the VPE_{pub} . To create these encrypted and authenticated secrets we execute the following algorithm:
 - (a) Create a Random number with a secure RNG , $rand = random(32)$.
 - (b) Symmetrically encrypt the desired secret with the Hash of that freshly random generated number and the reference value of the enclave that is supposed to read it .
 - (c) Create an a MAC key derived by the freshly created random number and the Attestation Key name. $(MAC_{Key} = KDF(rand, AK_{Name}))$
 - (d) Compute an authentication digest over the secret we wish to encrypt, Using standardised hashing algorithms such as SHA256, SHA384 etc. $Secret_{MAC} = HMAC(Secret, MAC_{KEY})$.
 - (e) Encrypt the random number generated in the first step with the unique identity key of the High-End device. This unique identity key is considered to be a public RSA Key.
6. Both the VPE and the Attestation Agent receive their Encrypted and authenticate secrets respectively. The two components execute the following algorithm to extract their secrets:
 - (a) Decrypt using the unique identity key of the High-End device to extract the random number generated by the Domain Manager.
 - (b) With the extracted random number each component computes the symmetric encryption secret key $ENC_{Key} = H(rand, MR)$.
 - (c) Decrypt with the ENC_{Key} the encrypted secret.
 - (d) Create an a MAC key derived by the freshly created random number and the Attestation Key name. $MAC_{Key} = KDF(rand, AK_{Name})$.
 - (e) Compute an authentication digest over the secret we wish to encrypt, using standardised hashing algorithms such as SHA256, SHA384 etc. $Secret_{MAC} = HMAC(Secret, MAC_{KEY})$
 - (f) If the acquired and the computed authentication digest match then the component can accept the secret and store for future use.

5.3.1.2 Runtime Attestation Assertions

Next, we describe the **runtime attestation** interface initiated by a remote Verifier, performed each time we need to attest the configuration state of a High-End device, initiating a challenge-based protocol. Through this protocol the Prover creates evidence for the Verifier that he is indeed in a correct configuration but without disclosing any information regarding its state, fortifying itself from any implementation disclosure attack. Given all the above, the actions followed in the context of the Join phase are shown in Figure 5.5, and are described as follows:

1. A Verifier, which could be any device that participates to the ENTRUST ecosystem, issues a challenge that is sent to the Prover's Attestation Agent.
2. The Attestation Agent creates a fresh nonce, $nonce_{AA}$, that is sent to the VPE.
3. The VPE, creates on his end another fresh nonce , $nonce_{VPE}$, and forwards them both to the Tracer.
4. The Tracer takes security measurements for each requested UnTrusted application and creates two signatures one for the Attestation Agent σ_1 and one for the VPE σ_2 .
 - The first signature is to be sent to the Attestation Agent, signing a Command Code (CC) that represents the execution of a specific command policy, the nonce that was issued by the Attestation Agent and the measurements taken from the runtime execution of the requested UnTrusted application, $\sigma_1 = Sign(H(CC||nonce_{AA}||MR), Tracer_{priv})$.

- The second signature is to be consumed by the VPE, signing a Command Code (CC) that represents the execution of a specific command policy, the nonce that was issued by the VPE and the enclave measurement of the Tracer, $\sigma_2 = \text{Sign}(H(CC||nonce_{VPE}||MRTracer), Tracer_{priv})$
5. The VPE creates a fresh session and starts executing the policy enforcement algorithm in order to get access to his key, $RuntimePolicy = (00\dots00)$.
 - (a) Appends to the fresh session the measurement of the entity that signed his formal verification statuses, $RuntimePolicy = H(RuntimePolicy||MRSigner)$.
 - (b) Appends to the session the measurement of the enclave application that is instantiating the VPE, $RuntimePolicy = H(RuntimePolicy||MREnclave)$.
 - (c) Verifies the signature of the Tracer that is corresponding to the VPE, by first recomputing the signed Digest, $SignedDigest = H(CC||nonce_{VPE}||MRTracer)$ and using the public key of the Tracer completes the verification process, $Verify(\sigma_2, SignedDigest, Tracer_{pub})$. If the verification is completed successfully the VPE computes the name of the Tracer's key, $TracerName = H(Tracer_{pub})$, and appends it to the runtime policy, to complete the Hash chain.
 $RuntimePolicy = H(RuntimePolicy||TracerName)$.
 - (d) The VPE then uses the $RuntimePolicy$ to decrypt the encrypted VPE_{priv} that was injected to him by the Domain Manager. The now decrypted value is hashed and then compared with the VPE_{HASH} . If these two digests match, the VPE can use its secret key.
 6. With the acquired VPE_{priv} the VPE computes a digital signature over the nonce that was issued by the Attestation Agent and the approved measurement of the Attestation Agent,
 $\sigma_3 = \text{Sign}(H(CC||nonce_{AA}||MRAA), VPE_{priv})$. The σ_1 and σ_3 are forwarded to the Attestation Agent. The VPE_{priv} after the compilation of the signature gets destroyed.
 7. The Attestation Agent creates a fresh session and starts executing the policy enforcement algorithm in order to get access to his key, $RuntimePolicy = (00\dots00)$.
 - (a) Appends to the fresh session the measurement of the entity that signed his Formal Verification status, $RuntimePolicy = H(RuntimePolicy||MRSigner)$.
 - (b) Appends to the session the measurement of the enclave application that is instantiating the Attestation Agent, $RuntimePolicy = H(RuntimePolicy||MREnclave)$.
 - (c) Appends to the session the Security measurement that the Tracer extracted.
 $RuntimePolicy = H(RuntimePolicy||ReferenceValue_i)\forall i$ of the UnTrusted attested applications.
 - (d) Verifies the signature of the Tracer that is corresponding to the Attestation Agent, by first recomputing the signed Digest, $SignedDigest = H(CC||nonce_{AA}||ReferenceValue_i)\forall i$ of the UnTrusted attested applications and using the public key of the Tracer completes the verification process,
 $Verify(\sigma_2, SignedDigest, Tracer_{pub})$. If the verification is completed successfully the Attestation Agent computes the name of the Tracer's key, $TracerName = H(Tracer_{pub})$, and appends it to the runtime policy, $RuntimePolicy = H(RuntimePolicy||TracerName)$.
 - (e) Verifies the signature of the VPE, by first recomputing the signed Digest,
 $SignedDigest = H(CC||nonce_{AA}||MRAA)$ and using the public key of the VPE completes the verification process, $Verify(\sigma_3, SignedDigest, VPE_{pub})$. If the verification is completed successfully the Attestation Agent computes the name of the VPE's key, $VPEName = H(VPE_{pub})$, and appends it to the runtime policy, $RuntimePolicy = H(RuntimePolicy||VPEName)$.
 - (f) With the $RuntimePolicy$ the Attestation Agent will verify the Authorization Ticket that he acquired in the Join Phase, $Verify(RuntimePolicy, AuthorizationTicket, DM_{pub})$. If the verification is completed successfully the $RuntimePolicy$ is resetted to $RuntimePolicy = H(CC||DMName)$, where the CC is the command code of a specific policy command.

Figure 5.5: ENTRUST Verifiable Key Restriction Policy Update: Run Time Attestation

- (g) The Attestation Agent will recompute his AK_{priv} , using the same KDF that was used during the Join Phase. The newly derived key gets hashed and compared with the AK_{HASH} . If these two digests match, then the Attestation Agent has successfully recreated his AK_{priv} .
- 8. The Attestation Agent uses his AK_{priv} to sign the initial challenge the Verifier has sent to him and then discards the AK_{priv} .

5.4 Low-End CMD Attestation

As described in deliverable D4.1 apart from the High-End devices, the Low-End devices that consist the ENTRUST medical ecosystem should be able to provide valid and authenticated traces during their entire lifecycle. Contrary to the High-End devices, the Low-end devices do not have the computation power to perform complex cryptographic operations, such as elliptic curve cryptography and pairing bases cryptography, thus all attestation enablers that shall be adopted by the Low-end devices are based on symmetric crypto. To this end, we need to adapt the Configuration Integrity Verification scheme described in the section above, to leverage the Trusted Computing base and the cryptographic capabilities of the Low-End devices.

5.4.1 High-end and Low-end CMD Authentication

Authentication between low-end and high-end devices is necessary because low-end devices typically lack connectivity capabilities and cannot communicate with the Domain Manager or the Backend system. As a result, the high-end CMD must act on behalf of the low-end CMD, creating a "parent-child" relationship. In the envisioned ENTRUST use cases, most low-end CMDs are equipped only with Bluetooth adapters and cannot connect to an IP layer. In this context, two core properties must be achieved: efficient authentication between devices, considering that low-end CMDs only support symmetric cryptography, and ensuring that a high-end CMD can only act on behalf of its "child" if it can prove there was an authentic request from the low-end CMD (non-repudiation). As a first step, we have constructed appropriate authentication primitives based on the use of Merkle Trees. In D4.3, these will be enhanced to achieve non-repudiation.

We recall from Section 2.4.3 the enrolment of the low-end devices based on the Merkle Signature Scheme (MSS) [56, 30].

Whenever the low-end device wants to be enrolled in the domain. It notifies the DM who generates $N = 2^n$ challenges C_1, \dots, C_N and sends the challenge set to the manufacturer together with the PUF's ID. The manufacturer creates the private keys R_i (using a key derivation function KDF). With input $R_i = SK_{OTS}^i$ and the *expected correct state* of the low-end device, the OTS- KEYGEN algorithm generates the corresponding one-time public key PK_{OTS}^i and sends them to the DM who creates the Merkle tree using the following steps:

- For each $i \in [0, N - 1]$, the DM calculates $h_i = H(PK_{OTS}^i)$
- The hash values h_i are placed as leaves and hashed recursively to form a binary tree as follows: Let a_{ij} denote the node in the tree with height i , and left-right position j . The hash values $h_i = a_{0,i}$ are the leaf nodes. The inner nodes are calculated by

$$a_{i,j} = H(a_{i-1, 2j} || a_{i-1, 2j+1})$$

where $i = 1, \dots, h$ and $j = 0, \dots, 2^{i-1}$, where h denotes the height of the tree. An example is shown in Figure 5.6.

- The Conformity Certificate is constructed by the TAF using its secret key x as follows:

$$CC = H_1(\text{mpk}, \text{Attribute Appraisals}, \text{ID})^x$$

H_1 is a hash function defined as $H_1 : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{G}_1$.

- Finally, the DM publishes mpk together with the challenge set C_i . Note that every time a Merkle tree is created, a new CC should be issued by TAF.

Low-end device Attestation:

- Each tree can generate 2^h signatures. The PUF outputs the i^{th} response R_i that corresponds to the challenge C_i .
- The low-end device runs the KEYGEN algorithm that takes inputs R_i and the *current configuration* of the low-end device to generate the one-time public key PK_{OTS}^i .
- The low-end device signs the message using the corresponding secret key R_i resulting in a one-time signature σ^i .
- The signature consists of the index of the leaf, the OTS public key PK_{OTS}^i , and the authentication path $Auth_i$ of that leaf. The signature is

$$(i, PK_{OTS}^i, Auth_i, \sigma^i)$$

- The authentication path is described in Chapter 3. For instance, if the signature is generated from R_2 and following the tree defined in the example shown in Figure 5.6, the authentication path $Auth_2$ consists of the following set of nodes of the tree $\{a_{03}, a_{10}, a_{21}\}$ as shown in Figure 5.7.

Verify: Given the signature and message m , the verifier proceeds to verify the message-signature pair under the PUF master public key mpk .

- First, the receiver verifies the one-time signature σ^i of the message m using the one-time signature public key PK_{OTS}^i . Note that this C_i is only allowed to be used once, this prevents the edge device from impersonating the PUF.

If verified, then proceed further, otherwise abort the process and reject the signature.

- The Verifier computes $a'_{0,i} = H(PK_{OTS}^i)$.
- Using the authentication path $Auth_i$ computes the root of the Merkle tree (i.e. the PUF master public key mpk').
- If $mpk = mpk'$, the verifier declares the signature as valid otherwise rejects it.
- Note that the signature is only verified correctly if $PK_{OTS}^i = PK_{OTS}^i$ that was set by the manufacturer, i.e. the current device configuration matches the expected correct state set by the device manufacturer in the MUD profile.

Figure 5.6: Key generation of Merkle signature scheme with Merkle tree having height $h = 3$ and $2^h = 8$ leaves

Figure 5.7: Authentication path of the signature generated from R_2 with OTS-public key PK_{OTS}^2

5.4.2 Low-End Single-Device Attestation

Similar to the High-End device, **ENTRUST** shall monitor the device state of the Low-End devices so that the centralized **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)** can assess their level of trust. The Trust assessment of the Low-End devices revolves mostly around the integrity of their configuration state. However, it is important to highlight that due to the limited resources of the low-end devices regarding its runtime tracing capabilities, the focus is on verifying the correct bootstrapping of trust (secure boot) of the devices. This is an inherent limitation of such resource-limited devices and it is one of the barriers that ENTRUST wants to investigate: what is the impact of such trustworthiness evidence on the uncertainty of the trust level calculation of the entire CMD ecosystem. To this end, We shall offer equivalent capabilities of the High-End's **Configuration Integrity Verification** scheme, as it pertains to efficiency and privacy, but with a reduced footprint on accuracy in order to leverage to the fullest the capabilities of the underlying **TCB**, without obfuscating any of the Trust assumptions.

More specifically, we are presenting an attestation scheme for low-end devices for all Low-end devices, which are equipped with a **Physical Unclonable Function (PUF)** and have Tracing capabilities. We are not offering a traditional Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV) attestation scheme. Instead, we are supporting the implicit attestation of a device's bootstrapping mechanism by default. This means that the focus is on verifying the correct initialization and secure boot process of the device, rather than continuously monitoring its configuration integrity. This approach leverages the existing tracing capabilities available within the device, which are typically limited due to the resource constraints of low-end devices. By concentrating on the secure bootstrapping process, we ensure that the device starts in a known, trusted state, which lays the foundation for trust in the device's operations without imposing significant overhead on its limited resources. To be more precise, we are introducing a challenge based protocol, where a Verifier issues a fresh challenge to be handled by the Low-End device in order to acquire evidence over the state of the attested device during its bootstrapping: **if** the Low-End device, acting as a Prover, is able to produce a valid Hash-based signature, **then** the High-End device shall know that the Prover was in a correct configuration state.

Therefore, in the rest of this section, we present the design of the **ENTRUST** Low-End attestation scheme, which

uses live traces to elevate the Key Derivation Function from a simple key creation method to a fine grained access control mechanism. To clarify the role and enhance the functionality of the Key Derivation Function (KDF), it's important to understand its primary purpose and how it can be leveraged for security. The KDF is not merely a method for creating cryptographic keys; it plays a pivotal role in ensuring secure access and maintaining device integrity. Traditionally, a KDF is used to generate cryptographic keys from a secret value, but in our approach, we aim to extend its functionality beyond simple key creation. By incorporating mechanisms similar to those used in Merkle tree-based authentication, we can enhance the KDF with built-in verification capabilities. This means that the KDF will not only derive keys but also verify the device's state as part of its operation. This enhancement allows the KDF to serve as a security checkpoint, ensuring that the device is in a known, trusted state before granting access or performing sensitive operations. Therefore, rather than claiming to elevate the KDF to a fine-grained access control mechanism, it is more accurate to state that we are augmenting the KDF with state verification features. This approach ensures that the device integrity is continuously verified, thereby providing a robust security layer without the need for a separate, complex access control mechanism.

Moving towards a zero-trust relationship between the Verifier (High-End) and the Prover (Low-End) is indeed feasible, but it presents certain challenges. The primary difficulty, as previously outlined, arises from the reliance on symmetric cryptography, which is typically supported by low-end devices participating in the ENTRUST ecosystem. In a zero-trust model, every interaction is treated as potentially untrustworthy, requiring constant verification. For low-end devices that primarily use symmetric cryptography, implementing zero-trust requires a different approach compared to systems that can leverage asymmetric cryptography. This necessitates the inclusion of a Domain Manager (DM) in the verification chain, resulting in a more centralized system. The Domain Manager plays a crucial role in managing and verifying the symmetric keys and ensuring that the devices are in a trusted state before any operation is permitted. This centralization contrasts with the more decentralized nature of high-end devices, which can independently manage asymmetric keys and perform mutual authentication without relying on a central authority. Therefore, while zero-trust is achievable for low-end devices, it requires adapting the trust assumptions and system architecture to accommodate the limitations of symmetric cryptography, highlighting the inherent differences in trust management between high-end and low-end devices. That being said, we have to outline here that it should be difficult for any Verifier to infer/disclose any meaningful information regarding the TCB of the Low-End device.

5.4.2.1 System Setup & Notation

In ENTRUST, we are planning to adopt an implicit attestation scheme for all low-end devices within a medical ecosystem. To this end, all PUF-enabled devices that have been authenticated into ENTRUST's infrastructure must provide verifiable attestation evidence proving their configuration correctness while adhering to the trust policies established by the Domain Manager, so as to ensure that the type of trustworthiness evidence collected is appropriate for the capabilities of each device. Unlike rigid security requirements, these trust policies are dynamic guidelines that determine what kind of evidence is necessary to establish trust in a device's state. The Domain Manager plays a crucial role in defining these trust policies, taking into account the diverse capabilities and limitations of both high-end and low-end devices. For instance, high-end devices, which typically support more advanced cryptographic functions and possess greater computational resources, can provide robust and comprehensive evidence of their trustworthiness. In contrast, low-end devices, constrained by limited resources and reliant primarily on symmetric cryptography, require tailored policies that focus on fundamental aspects such as secure bootstrapping and integrity checks. By aligning the trust policies with the specific capabilities of each device, the Domain Manager ensures a flexible yet effective approach to maintaining the overall security and trustworthiness of the system. This adaptive method allows us to meet the necessary trust levels without overburdening the devices, thereby creating a balanced and efficient security framework. Specifically, to describe the ENTRUST implicit attestation scheme, we consider the following roles.

- **Prover:** A Low-End device with a Root ID key equipped by the manufacturer. In ENTRUST we focus on Low-End devices with a combination of a functional Physical Unclonable Function (PUF), a Tracer integrated into the device's Software Development Kit (SDK), and a Trusted Key Derivation Function (KDF).

1. The PUF provides a unique and secure hardware fingerprint for each device, which is crucial for secure

bootstrapping and initial authentication processes. This unique identifier helps in establishing a trusted identity for the device, forming the foundation of its trustworthiness.

2. The Tracer, embedded within the device's SDK, plays a critical role in evidence monitoring. The extent and granularity of the evidence that can be monitored, depend on the level of tracing capabilities supported by the device. For low-end devices, this typically includes tracking essential operations and ensuring that the device's state transitions adhere to expected patterns. This tracer monitors and records relevant security events, providing valuable data for verifying the device's integrity and operational status.
 3. Finally, the Trusted KDF not only generates cryptographic keys but also incorporates state verification features. By integrating state verification into the key derivation process, the KDF ensures that cryptographic operations are only performed when the device is in a known, trusted state.
- **Verifier:** A High-End device that is already enrolled to the ENTRUST infrastructure. All High-End devices should be equipped with OP-TEE to host Trusted Applications, that will handle the verification process of the one time signatures of the Low-End devices. In the case of attesting a swarm of Low-End devices, the high-end device acts as a worker, supporting the verification process managed by the Domain Manager. This collaborative approach ensures that the Domain Manager can efficiently and securely verify the integrity and trustworthiness of the low-end devices within the swarm.
 - **Domain Manager:** In the context of ENTRUST, the Domain Manager is regarded as a trusted entity with several critical responsibilities. Beyond overseeing Low-End Configuration Integrity Verification and ensuring secure on-boarding of participating devices into the infrastructure, the Domain Manager also plays a pivotal role in equipping high-end devices with the Merkle Tree Public Key (MPK). This enables high-end devices to verify the collected one-time signatures effectively, enhancing the overall security and integrity assurance within the ENTRUST ecosystem.

5.4.2.2 Low-End Single-device Attestation High-Level Overview

Having described all the entities and components that will participate in a Low-End Single-device Attestation, we will now provide a high-level conceptual overview of the scheme. More specifically, assuming that a Low-End device has successfully completed Secure On-Boarding (where the Domain Manager verified its Root ID key), in the rest of this section we will be describing the operations that take place for collecting evidence based on which the Trust Assessment can be conducted.

- **Towards Runtime Verification of Static System Properties**
 1. Considering that a High-End devices wishes to attest one of the Low-End devices, that it is responsible for, it will initiate a challenge response attestation protocol.
 2. When the Prover (Low-End device) receives the challenge, it gathers traces across the operating system to assess the integrity of the attested device. These traces serve as a fingerprint of all security critical static properties of the system being attested.
 3. After collecting the traces, the Low-End device generates a corresponding one-time public key, which serves as its Attestation Key. This key is used to sign the Challenge issued by the Verifier (High-End device).
 4. The signature will be sent back to the Verifier, who will on his end generate the one time attestation key (as we are using only symmetric crypto for this scheme). With the freshly calculated attestation key, the Verifier will try verify the provided signature over the initial issued challenge.

5.4.2.3 Low-End device Attestation - Architectural Details & Mode of Operation

In this section, we provide a detailed overview containing all the details of the ENTRUST single Low-End, along with all the interactions between all involved components. Through this protocol a Low-End device creates trustworthiness evidence for the High-End device to verify the integrity of its device state.

1. A High-End device acting as the Verifier, issues a challenge consisting of an one-time PUF-specific bit stream (C_i), provided by the Domain Manager during its enrollment, and a fresh nonce.
2. Upon reception of the challenge, the Low-End device, acting as the Prover, goes off to complete all the necessary actions to provide attestation evidence to the Verifier. Namely:
 - (a) With the C_i provided by the High-End device, the Low-End device parses it to the underlying **PUF** to get the R_i .
 - (b) Initiates the RTOs Tracer in order to collect system traces. This tracing primarily focuses on static properties, such as providing evidence of secure boot integrity, a common requirement for all low-end devices. Secure boot ensures that the device starts up using only trusted software, establishing a foundation of trust for further operations. Depending on the type of Low-End device, additional tracing capabilities may be employed to gather more detailed information about the attested system. For some devices, this could include monitoring specific runtime behaviors, tracking system calls, or checking for unexpected modifications in critical memory regions. These enhanced tracing capabilities enable a more comprehensive assessment of the device's integrity, tailored to the specific features and requirements of different low-end devices within the ENTRUST infrastructure.
3. With the freshly generated R_i and the system traces the Low-End device shall invoke the Trusted **KDF** protected by the isolation security controls offered by the RTOs, to generate the one-time public key PK_{OTS}^i based on the R_i and the extracted traces. By using the KDF in this manner, the process ensures that the derived key is securely generated within the isolated environment of the RTOS, minimizing the risk of tampering or unauthorized access. The one-time public key PK_{OTS}^i , created from both the R_i and the traces, serves as a robust attestation mechanism that implicitly verifies the integrity and state of the Low-End device. This method allows the system to authenticate the device's identity and trustworthiness efficiently, even within the constraints of resource-limited devices. the generated one-time Public Key, the Low-End device shall perform a One-time Signature (**OTS**) over the nonce issued by the High-End device. It will then calculate the authentication path, which consists of the sequence of hashes that connect the one-time public key to the Merkle Root. This path is used to verify that the one-time public key is part of the dataset represented by the Merkle Root, enabling its verification by the High-End device.
4. Upon receiving the response from the Low-End device, the High-End device initiates the verification process. First, it verifies the one-time signature (**OTS**) created by the Low-End device using the nonce it issued, ensuring the validity of the signature and the correctness of the one-time public key PK_{OTS}^i . If this verification is successful, the High-End device then calculates the hash digest $a'_{0i} = H(PK_{OTS}^i)$. Upon successful verification, the High-End device uses the provided authentication path to traverse the Merkle Tree. This path consists of the sequence of hashes needed to connect the one-time public key PK_{OTS}^i to the Merkle Root, representing the overall state of the device's traces. Starting from the hash digest a'_{0i} , the device combines it with the relevant sibling hashes in the authentication path, recalculating the parent hash at each level until it reaches the Merkle Root. The High-End device then compares the recalculated Merkle Root with the known Merkle Root, previously provided by the Domain Manager. If the roots match, it confirms that the one-time public key and the associated traces are authentic and have not been tampered with. This successful verification of the Merkle Root assures that the Low-End device's state is as expected, confirming its initial secure boot and subsequent operations were performed correctly. Thus, the High-End device effectively verifies the authenticity and integrity of the Low-End device, ensuring it adheres to the trust policies defined by the Domain Manager. This comprehensive process leverages the Merkle Tree structure, the one-time public key, and the robust tracing capabilities protected by the RTOS, maintaining the integrity of the ENTRUST infrastructure even within the constraints of low-end devices.

Figure 5.8: ENTRUST Low-End Single Device Attestation

5.5 Conformity Certificates

In this section, we describe the process of creating and sharing Conformity Certificates (CC) that certify *trust appraisals* such as integrity or resilience. These appraisals will be the result of the runtime attestation of the device trust properties and characteristics, as defined by the Domain Manager in the ENTRUST trust model. Thus, the creation of the CC will be carried out by the TAF when an attestation process leads to a change in the trust level of a CMD or medical domain.

Conformity Certificates will take the form that resembles a Verifiable Credential (VC), certifying appraisals of high-level trust characteristics that may later be presented to a third party acting as an auditor. There will be two main scenarios for CCs. First, a CC can be issued to a **specific device**, which will hold the credential and later present it to an auditor, such as the Domain Manager right after enrolment. Within this scenario, there are two possible instantiations to accommodate the heterogeneous constraints of devices: Low-end devices are not capable of selectively disclosing information about their attributes, i.e. no attribute privacy is guaranteed, instead the devices simply present the whole VC, which is bound to the outcomes of the device’s PUF-based TCB to prove their ownership. But, in the case of high-end devices, to improve the privacy of the solution, the VC will be signed with the p-ABC scheme, so that the device can later selectively disclose through zero-knowledge proofs part of the information contained in the VC according to a policy. We note that, while these privacy notions can be technically achieved similarly through the ABS scheme, the cryptographic structure of p-ABCs is a better fit for this specific use case and flow, as it follows the digital certificate forms and flows and allows for disclosing an abstraction of trust properties of a device in a domain. Additionally, it opens up the opportunity to evaluate and compare the application of both schemes to the IoT world. Furthermore, the second scenario involves the creation of a CC for a domain, certifying the achieved trust properties according to the attestation process of the whole domain and the medical-service-graph chains. The instantiation of this case will be equivalent to the creation and usage of CCs in high-end devices, with the caveat that the appraisals now refer to the domain system as a whole and that the credential holder will be the Domain Manager. Thus, we refer to Figure 5.11 for the details on the scheme and flow to avoid redundancy.

Next, we will present the crypto-operation of the Conformity Certificates for both the low and high-end devices:

5.5.1 Low-End Device's Conformity Certificates

The case of low-end devices is adapted to their constrained computational capabilities. They will not be able to selectively disclose information, and instead will simply present the whole VC, which is bound to the outcomes of the device's PUF-based TCB to prove their ownership. Additionally, their CCs will contain static properties issued during enrolment, although the possibility of creating runtime CCs is open depending on the attestation procedures. After successful authentication of a low-end device as presented in Section 5.4.1, TAF then creates Conformity Certificate CC when needed as follows:

- The creation of the Enrolment Conformity Certificates CC for the low-end device is done by the TAF after enrolment of the low-end device. The CC is a signature done by TAF using the first element x from the TAF's signing key $sk = (x, y_1, \dots, y_{k+1})$, used in the p-ABC scheme introduced in Chapter 2. TAF's signature is done on the root public key mpk , the device Attribute Appraisals, and the Low-end device's identity ID. The Conformity Certificates is constructed follows:

$$CC = H_1(mpk, \text{Attribute Appraisals}, ID)^x$$

where H_1 is hash function defined as $H_1 : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{G}_1$.

- After creating of CC, TAF sends the CC together with the Attribute Appraisals defined for the device to the DM who verifies the TAF signature under the corresponding TAF public key g_2^x , this mechanism is described in Figure 5.9.
- The run-time Conformity Certificates CC_i is a signature on the ID, the current challenge C_i , the root public key mpk , and the device Attribute Appraisals.

$$H_1(mpk, \text{Attribute Appraisals}, ID, C_i)^x$$

- TAF checks that this CC_i doesn't match any previously constructed CC_j , for $j < i$, for this device (i.e. C_i wasn't used before, this is due to the collision resistance property of H_1 discussed in Chapter 3).
- The pair (CC_i, C_i) will be kept in the records and can be verified by any verifier by checking:

$$e(H_1(mpk, \text{Attribute Appraisals}, ID, C_i), g_2^x) \stackrel{?}{=} e(CC_i, g_2)$$

Figure 5.10 describes the issuance of CC_i where the Verifier is the ENTRUST high-end device and the prover is the ENTRUST low-end device.

Figure 5.9: Enrolment Conformity Certificates for Low-end devices

Figure 5.10: Run-time Conformity Certificates for Low-end devices

5.5.2 High-End Device's Conformity Certificates

Figure 5.11 shows the details of the creation and usage of the certificate for a high-end device, which can be described as follows:

1. The TAF receives the current trust aspect attributes for a device along with its public device identity key ($RootID_{pub}$), for instance coming from the output of the runtime attestation of the device.
2. The attributes are parsed to fit the signing scheme, and are signed using the $CC_{pabc_{priv}}$ key used for CC generation, which is a secret key of the p-ABC scheme in Section 3.6.
3. The signature and attributes of the CC are sent in the form of a VC to the device.
4. The device may verify the validity of the VC, and store it in its secure wallet for later use in showing processes.
5. When a showing of the CC is needed, the verifier or auditor establishes a policy for which information will be shown, and sends it to the device.
6. The device parses the policy and performs a derivation of the zero-knowledge proof that selectively discloses information according to the policy, such as the public device identity key for which the credential was issued and part of the attributes, e.g. integrity.
7. The VP is generated from this derived credential and signed with the device's private device identity key, and sent back to the verifier.
8. The verifier validates the received VP, verifying the signature created by the device, along with the validity of the zero-knowledge proof with respect to the TAF's $CC_{pabc_{pub}}$.
9. The revealed information is assessed with respect to the expected values and policy.

Figure 5.11: High-end device: Creation of Conformity Certificate as VC, and usage of Conformity Certificate during interaction with third party.

5.6 VPs During Run-time Phase

To enable the creation and sharing of trustworthiness evidence in a verifiable manner during the run-time phase, ENTRUST designed the ABS and ABSC protocols that support the creation of Verifiable Presentations (VPs) based on a set of certified attributes issued the Privacy CA in the form of VCs. Based on the issued VCs, the device is required to generate a VP using its certified attribute keys to build a trust relationship between itself and other ENTRUST entities. These presentations take the form of Attribute-based Signatures if the Verifier device and the Prover device belong to the same domain or Attribute-based Signcryption if the two devices belong to different domains.

If the Verifier (the device that initiates the attestation process) and the prover belong to the same domain, an ABS is created by the prover under a policy \mathcal{P} , otherwise, an ABSC is required (i.e. generating a cipher text that is an encryption of the attestation data, then creating ABS on the cipher text). The signer(prover) creates an ABS/ABSC, using its attribute keys issued by the Privacy CA in the enrolment phase. Note that these keys are binded to the Root Key ($rsk = x, rpki$) of the device. The device then uses the secret part of its Root Key $rsk = x$ to generate the signature. The signature cannot be generated successfully without the knowledge of x . This prevents collusion attacks since sharing attribute keys is infeasible in our scheme. In ABSC, the signer further encrypts the attestation data based on the decryptor's policy \mathcal{P}' that allows the decryptor to retrieve the original data if it has a set of attributes that satisfies \mathcal{P}' . The attribute anonymity is preserved in our schemes by committing the attribute and then signing them using Schnorr-type signatures.

We now present ENTRUST ABS /ABSC schemes that will be used during the run-time phase. Note that these schemes have different construction of signatures from the ABSC scheme in Section 5.1.2. The run-time ABS and ABSC support attribute anonymity. This is achieved by hiding the attribute of the signer into a larger set of attributes through issuing Schnorr signatures on every signer attribute even if it is not used in the policy \mathcal{P} . An external verifier learns (nearly) nothing about the signer's attribute other than the signer has a set of attributes that satisfies \mathcal{P} . The notations that will be used in the schemes are explained in Table 2.3.

5.6.1 ABS with Attribute Anonymity and Root Key Binding for the Run-Time Phase

The ABS Setup algorithm takes a security parameter λ and as an input, then generates the CA public key $mpk := X = e(g_1, g_2)^\alpha$ and the corresponding secret key $msk := \alpha$. The Privacy CA publishes the system public parameters \mathcal{G} with its public key mpk . The Key Generation algorithm $KeyGen(msk, (\mathbf{M}, \pi))$ takes as inputs the CA secret key, the access matrix \mathbf{M} and a function π that maps each row in \mathbf{M} to its corresponding attribute, this algorithm returns the user attribute keys sk_1 and $sk_{2,i}$ bounded to the user's root key ($SK = x, PK = g_2^x$). This is done by letting the user creates $\sigma_i = H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^x$, where $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$, for each row $i \in \mathcal{I}$, where \mathcal{I} represents the indices of the rows in \mathbf{M} that corresponds to the user attribute set \mathcal{S} . The details of these algorithms are presented in Algorithm 1. This algorithm is run by the Privacy CA.

Algorithm 1 ABS Setup and KeyGen

- 1: Take the security parameter λ as input
 - 2: Pick $\alpha \leftarrow_{\mathcal{S}} \mathbb{Z}_p$, $H_0 : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_p$ and $H_1 : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{G}_1$
 - 3: Define $\mathcal{G} := (p, \mathbb{G}_1, \mathbb{G}_2, \mathbb{G}_T, e, g_1, g_2)$
 - 4: $\text{mpk} := (\mathcal{G}, H_0, H_1, X = e(g_1, g_2)^\alpha)$
 - 5: $\text{msk} := \alpha$
 - 6: $\text{KeyGen}(\text{msk}, (\mathbf{M}, \pi), \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow \text{sk}$
 - 7: Selects the attributes assigned to the user and sends every attribute $\pi(i) \in \mathcal{S}$
 - 8: $\sigma_i = H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^x$, where $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$
 - 9: The CA verifies each σ_i under PK
 - 10: Pick $r \leftarrow_{\mathcal{S}} \mathbb{Z}_p$, $\mathbf{v} \leftarrow_{\mathcal{S}} \mathbb{Z}_p^{n_2-1}$
 - 11: $\text{sk}_1 := g_2^r$
 - 12: $\text{sk}_{2,i} := g_1^{\mathbf{M}_i(\alpha || \mathbf{v})^\top} \cdot \sigma_i^r$ for each row $i \in \mathcal{I}$
 - 13: Output $\text{sk} := (\text{sk}_1, (\text{sk}_{2,i})_{i \in \mathcal{I}})$
-

The algorithm $\text{Sign}(\text{sk}, \mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{U}, (\mathbf{M}, \pi), \text{msg})$ takes an attribute set \mathcal{S} with the corresponding attribute keys, a message msg to be signed, and a policy matrix \mathbf{M} , then generates an ABS signature σ . The ABS signature includes proof of knowledge of the corresponding attribute keys without revealing which attributes are being used. This proof is achieved by Shnorr's signature of knowledge as described in Algorithm 2. This algorithm is run by the signer.

Algorithm 2 ABS Sign: $\text{Sign}(\text{sk}, \mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{U}, (\mathbf{M}, \pi), \text{msg}) \rightarrow \sigma$

- 1: Pick $s, t, r_\alpha, (r_i)_{i \in [n_1]} \leftarrow_{\mathcal{S}} \mathbb{Z}_p$
 - 2: $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$
 - 3: $\sigma_1 := \text{sk}_1^{xt}$,
 - 4: $\sigma_2 := \prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\text{sk}_{2,i})^{\gamma_i s}$,
 - 5: $\sigma_3 := \prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{\gamma_i s} = \prod_{i \in [n_1]} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{\gamma_i s}$, and
 - 6: $\sigma_4 := g_2^t$
 - 7: $Y = X^{s \cdot t}$,
 - 8: $Z = X^{r_\alpha}$,
 - 9: $W = \prod_{i \in [n_1]} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{r_i}$,
 - 10: $c = H_0(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, Y, Z, W, \text{msg})$,
 - 11: $s_\alpha = r_\alpha - s \cdot t \cdot c$, and
 - 12: $\forall_{i \in [n_1]} s_i = r_i - \gamma_i \cdot s \cdot c$.
 - 13: Output $\sigma := (\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, c, s_\alpha, (s_i)_{i \in [n_1]})$
-

To verify an ABS signature, the algorithm $\text{Verify}(\text{mpk}, (\mathbf{M}, \pi), \sigma, \text{msg})$ takes an ABS signature, the general access policy \mathbf{M} and a message msg and outputs 0 or 1. It verifies the the pairing to prove that the attribute keys are issued by the Privacy CA under mpk , it also verifies Shnorr signatures as described in Algorithm 3. This algorithm is run by the Verifier.

Algorithm 3 ABS Verify: $\text{Verify}(\text{mpk}, (\mathbf{M}, \pi), \sigma, \text{msg}) \rightarrow 0/1$

- 1: $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$
 - 2: $Y' = e(\sigma_2, \sigma_4) / e(\sigma_3, \sigma_1)$
 - 3: $Z' = X^{s_\alpha} \cdot Y^c$ and $W' = \prod_{i \in [n_1]} H(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{s_i} \cdot \sigma_3^c$
 - 4: $c' = H_0(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, Y', Z', W', \text{msg})$
 - 5: If $c' \neq c$, output 0; otherwise, output 1
-

Signer	Verifier
$(rsk, rpki), (sk_1, sk_{2,i})$ Pick $s, t, r_\alpha, (r_i)_{i \in [n_1]} \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p$ Compute $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$ $\sigma_1 := \mathbf{sk}_1^{xt}$ $\sigma_2 := \prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{sk}_{2,i})^{\gamma_i s}$, $\sigma_3 := \prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}} H_1(i h_m \pi(i))^{\gamma_i s}$ $\sigma_4 := g_2^t$. Compute $Y = X^{s \cdot t}$ $Z = X^{r_\alpha}$ $W = \prod_{i \in [n_1]} H_1(i h_m \pi(i))^{r_i}$, $c = H_0(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, Y, Z, W, \text{msg})$ $s_\alpha = r_\alpha - s \cdot t \cdot c$ $\forall_{i \in [n_1]} s_i = r_i - \gamma_i \cdot s \cdot c$. $\sigma := (\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, c, s_\alpha, (s_i)_{i \in [n_1]})$	$rpki, \mathbf{M}$ $\xrightarrow{\sigma}$ Checks the following Compute $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$. Compute $Y' = e(\sigma_2, \sigma_4) / e(\sigma_3, \sigma_1)$ Compute $Z' = X^{s_\alpha} \cdot Y^c$ $W' = \prod_{i \in [n_1]} H(i h_m \pi(i))^{s_i} \cdot \sigma_3^c$ $c' = H_0(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, Y', Z', W', \text{msg})$ If $c' \neq c$, output 0 otherwise, output 1

Figure 5.12: ABS with attribute anonymity

5.6.2 ABSC with Sender's Attribute Anonymity and Key Binding During Run-Time Phase

We now present the attribute-based signcryption scheme that will be used during the run-time phase to establish a trust relationship between two devices belonging to different ENTRUST domains. This scheme supports the signer's attribute anonymity which prevents a verifier from learning the signer's attribute set that was used in creating the ABS. Our ABSC scheme is an extension of the ABS scheme presented in Section 5.6.1. In this scheme, the signer also encrypts the message that is signed (Attestation data) under a certain policy through an Attribute-based Encryption (ABE) scheme. The decryption policy should be satisfied by the decryptor to allow a successful decryption of the cipher text.

- $\text{Setup}(1^\lambda) \rightarrow (\text{mpk}, \text{msk})$. It takes the security parameter λ as input. The CA picks $\alpha \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p$, $H_0 : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_p$ and $H_1 : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{G}_1$. The CA publishes $\mathcal{G} := (p, \mathbb{G}_1, \mathbb{G}_2, \mathbb{G}_T, e, g_1, g_2)$ and its public key $\text{mpk} := (\mathcal{G}, H_0, H_1, X = e(g_1, g_2)^\alpha)$. The CA secret key is $\text{msk} := \alpha$ as in Algorithm 1.
- $\text{sKeyGen}(\text{msk}, (\mathbf{M}, \pi), \mathcal{I}) \rightarrow \text{sk}$. The ABSC key generation algorithm (similar to Algorithm 1) outputs a set of attribute keys for someone who plays the role of a sender. The Privacy CA sends a set of attributes \mathcal{S} to be certified for the user. Then the user with a root key ($SK = x, PK = g_2^x$), replies with $\sigma_i = H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^x$, where $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$ for all $i \in \mathcal{I}$, where \mathcal{I} represents the set of indices of the attribute in \mathcal{S} . The Privacy CA verifies each σ_i under PK . Then proceeds as follows: The CA picks $r \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p$, $\mathbf{v} \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p^{n_2-1}$ and computes $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$ and the attribute keys $\text{sk}_1 := g_2^r$. $\forall_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \text{sk}_{2,i} := g_1^{\mathbf{M}_i(\alpha || \mathbf{v})^\top} \cdot \sigma_i^r$. Finally, the CA outputs $\text{sk} := (\text{sk}_1, (\text{sk}_{2,i})_{i \in \mathcal{I}})$.

- $\text{rKeyGen}(\text{msk}, (\mathbf{M}', \pi')) \rightarrow \text{sk}'$. This ABSC key generation algorithm outputs a set of attribute keys for someone who plays the role of a receiver. The Privacy CA sends a set of attributes \mathcal{S}' to be certified for the user. Then the user with a root key ($SK' = x', PK' = g_2^{x'}$), replies with $\sigma'_i = H_1(i || h'_m || \pi'(i))^x$, where $h'_m = H_0(\mathbf{M}')$ for all $i \in \mathcal{I}'$, where \mathcal{I}' represents the set of indices of the attribute in \mathcal{S}' . The Privacy CA verifies each σ'_i under PK' . The CA picks $r' \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p$, $\mathbf{v}' \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p^{n'_2-1}$. Compute $h'_m = H_0(\mathbf{M}')$ and the attribute keys $\text{sk}'_1 := g_2^{r'}$, $\forall_{i \in \mathcal{I}'} \text{sk}'_{2,i} := g_1^{\mathbf{M}'_i(\alpha || \mathbf{v}')^T} \cdot \sigma'_{i,r'}$. The CA outputs $\text{sk}' := (\text{sk}'_1, (\text{sk}'_{2,i})_{i \in \mathcal{I}'})$.
- **ABSC Signcrypt**: This algorithm is run by the encryptor/signer. We follow the construction of the ABS scheme presented in Section 5.6.1 and add the encryption part of the message that is signed (this is step 8 in Algorithm 4). The steps of this phase are presented in Algorithm 4. Note that the signature and the encryption parts are glued together using the same parameter t to prove that the signer is the encryptor to avoid man-in-the-middle attacks.

Algorithm 4 ABSC Signcrypt: $\text{SignEnc}(\text{sk}, (\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{S}') \subseteq \mathcal{U}, (\mathbf{M}, \pi), (\mathbf{M}', \pi'), \text{msg}) \rightarrow \sigma$

- 1: Pick $s, t, r_\alpha, (r_i)_{i \in [n_1]} \leftarrow_{\$} \mathbb{Z}_p$.
 - 2: Compute $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$ and $h'_m = H_0(\mathbf{M}')$,
 - 3: $\sigma_1 := \text{sk}'_1^{xt}$,
 - 4: $\sigma_2 := \prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\text{sk}'_{2,i})^{\gamma_i s}$,
 - 5: $\sigma_3 := \prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{\gamma_i s} = \prod_{i \in [n_1]} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{\gamma_i s}$ since we choose $\forall i \in [n_1]/\mathcal{I} \gamma_i = 0$,
 - 6: $\sigma_4 := g_2^t$
 - 7: $\forall_{i \in \mathcal{I}'} \sigma_{5,i} = H_1(i || h'_m || \pi'(i))^t$
 - 8: $\sigma_6 = X^t \cdot \text{msg}$
 - 9: $Y = X^{s \cdot t}$
 - 10: $Z = X^{r_\alpha}$
 - 11: $W = \prod_{i \in [n_1]} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{r_i}$
 - 12: $c = H_0(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, (\sigma_{5,i})_{i \in \mathcal{I}'}, \sigma_6, Y, Z, W)$
 - 13: $s_\alpha = r_\alpha - s \cdot t \cdot c, \forall_{i \in \mathcal{I}}$
 - 14: $s_i = r_i - \gamma_i \cdot s \cdot c, \forall_{i \in [n_1]/\mathcal{I}} s_i = r_i$
 - 15: $\sigma := (\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, (\sigma_{5,i})_{i \in \mathcal{I}'}, \sigma_6, c, s_\alpha, (s_i)_{i \in [n_1]})$
-

- **ABSC VerifyDec**: This algorithm is run by the decryptor/verifier. It takes a signcrypt and returns a verification result of 0 or 1. This algorithm also supports decryption and returns a message msg (Step 5 in Algorithm 5).

Algorithm 5 ABSC VerifyDec: $\text{VerifyDec}(\text{mpk}, \mathcal{S}', (\mathbf{M}, \pi), (\mathbf{M}', \pi'), \sigma) \rightarrow 0/1$

- 1: Compute $h_m = H_0(\mathbf{M})$ and $h'_m = H_0(\mathbf{M}')$.
 - 2: Compute $Y' = e(\sigma_2, \sigma_4) / e(\sigma_3, \sigma_1)$.
 - 3: Compute $Z' = X^{s_\alpha} \cdot Y^c$ and $W' = \prod_{i \in [n_1]} H_1(i || h_m || \pi(i))^{s_i} \cdot \sigma_3^c$.
 - 4: Compute $c' = H_0(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4, (\sigma_{5,i})_{i \in [n'_1]}, \sigma_6, Y', Z', W')$.
 - 5: If $c' \neq c$, output 0; otherwise,
 - 6: Compute $\text{msg} = \frac{\sigma_6 \cdot e\left(\prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}'} \sigma_{5,i}^{\gamma'_i}, \text{sk}'_1 x'\right)}{e\left(\prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}'} \text{sk}'_{2,i}^{\gamma'_i}, \sigma_4\right)}$
-

5.7 Security Analysis

This section provides a qualitative security analysis of the CIV, ABS, and ABSC schemes. It offers an initial high-level overview of the security proof for these schemes. A complete and formal proof of security for all the described cryptographic schemes will be presented in D4.3.

5.7.1 Configuration Integrity Verification

As described in Section 5.2.3, the goal of Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV) is to enable a remote entity to verify the configuration correctness of an edge device during its runtime phase. This verification covers both the targeted safety-critical application and the software stack that is instantiated as part of the ENTRUST's Trusted Computing Base (TCB). More specifically, as part of the entire ENTRUST attestation toolkit, the main goal is to establish trust relationships between all devices participating in the ENTRUST infrastructure. This is essential to enable the runtime and continuous trust assessment of each device, facilitating collaborative function execution within a comprehensive Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) and IoT ecosystem. The attestation process ensures that each device, whether high-end or low-end, TEE-capable or not, provides verifiable evidence of its configuration integrity and operational state. By enforcing trust policies and employing strong cryptographic mechanisms, ENTRUST ensures that devices can securely interact and execute functions while maintaining confidentiality and integrity. Such security guarantees are achieved through the provision of Zero Touch Configuration functionalities, where platforms wishing to join a domain must adhere to compiled trust policies by providing verifiable evidence of their configuration correctness. In other words, the framework needs to ensure that a node can be part of its ecosystem **if and only if** it can continuously prove that it is in a "Correct State".

ENTRUST's enhanced CIV extends beyond the device enrollment phase, as a device may be required to provide attestation evidence of its configuration at any given point. For instance, during a software update, it is vital for a device to provide verifiable proof not only of the correctness of the update output but also that the update did not compromise the Trust model for the overall device. To this end, the following properties are of interest:

Property 1 (Configuration Correctness). A device's load-time and run-time configurations must comply with the attestation policy compiled and authorized by the Domain Manager.

This property is satisfied as follows. Let an adversary A launch an untrusted application with a measurement of their choice and α be the configuration that the Domain Manager has requested to be measured. If α was altered without first recording its digest $d = H(\alpha)$, where $H()$ is a collision-resistant hash function, the adversary cannot win unless they launch an application whose configuration digest d' , where $d = d'$, or in other words, find an α' such that $H(\alpha') = d$. If α (the configuration of the application) is not changed, the adversary computes $d = H(\alpha)$ and supplies d to the attestation engine, thus not breaking Property 1. Now, assume the adversary has changed α to α' , but their chosen $d' = H(\alpha')$ is the correct one ($d' = d$). Thus, the adversary has managed to find two distinct inputs α, b_1 with $\alpha \neq b_1$ and $H(\alpha) = H(b_1)$. Remember now, that $H()$ is a collision-resistant one-way hash function, hence it is infeasible to find such α, b_1 . To this end, an adversary cannot unnoticeably change the configuration of an untrusted application. It must be noted here that we assume the device has undergone a secure boot proving that its TCB is operating as intended.

Property 2 (Enforced Policy Verifiability). As an extension of configuration correctness, a device's run-time configuration must comply with the latest policy compiled by the Domain Manager.

This property is satisfied as follows. Let an adversary A try to enforce a deprecated policy that the Domain Manager has issued or even a totally invalid policy. To achieve this, the adversary must launch the enclave that handles the enforcement of the Key Restriction Usage Policy (Attestation Agent) with an embedded vulnerability. To this end, let α be the configuration of the Attestation Agent's enclave, $H()$ a collision-resistant hash function, and $MRENCLAVE = H(\alpha)$ the enclave measurement. With the VPE Key that the Domain Manager injects within ENTRUST's TCB, the device attests to the versioning of both the Tracer and the Attestation Agent. To this end, the adversary A has two possible paths to unnoticeably use an obsolete policy.

1. The adversary A generates an enclave with configuration α' , which will lead to the correct calculation of $MRENCLAVE = H(\alpha')$. By finding an $\alpha' \neq \alpha$ with $H(\alpha') = H(\alpha)$, the adversary has found a collision of the hash function, breaking the initial assumption that $H()$ is a collision-resistant hash function. Thus, Property 2 is not compromised.
2. The adversary A tries to authorize the enforcement of deprecated or even unissued policies. To achieve this, the adversary A must use a collection of old authorizations received from the VPE and the VPE public key to forge valid signatures by recreating the VPE Key. In other words, the adversary A has managed to break the

ECDLP strong assumption. As this is not considered in our threat model, since our protocols are based on NIST-approved elliptic curves, Property 2 is not broken.

Property 3 (Zero Knowledge CIV). To keep configurations confidential, any verifier should only require the prover's Attestation public key to verify its configuration correctness.

When a device, \mathcal{X} , wishes to attest another device, \mathcal{Y} , it first queries the blockchain to download the appropriate policy to verify the correct state of \mathcal{Y} . Through the downloaded policy, it receives $C^{sk} AK^{\mathcal{Y}pub}, AK^{\mathcal{Y}pub}$. If the aforementioned properties hold, then \mathcal{Y} is correctly associated with $AK^{\mathcal{Y}pub}$. Thus, if \mathcal{X} chooses a random number n^t and \mathcal{Y} presents $AK^{\mathcal{Y}priv}n$, where $(AK^{\mathcal{Y}priv}n, AK^{\mathcal{Y}pub}) = n$, then \mathcal{X} knows that \mathcal{Y} was able to use $AK^{\mathcal{Y}priv}$ and consequently fulfills the Domain Manager's requirements. Keep in mind that to allow the use of the Attestation Key, all pre-defined assertions depicting configuration correctness must be satisfied. Hence, by providing a valid digital signature, a verifier knows that the attested device is in a correct configuration state without disclosing any information regarding its state.

5.7.2 Attribute-Based Signatures (ABS) & Attribute-Based SignCryption (ABSC)

For the ABS protocol, the goal of the adversary can be either one of the following:

1) To forge a signature with a predicate that his attributes do not satisfy. For instance, consider the use-case example presented in Subsection 3.2.2 where the signer attribute set is

$$S = \{\text{Authenticated Tracer, Certified Trusted Computing base, Verifiable Policy Enforcer}\}$$

We mathematically proved that S doesn't satisfy the policy in Subsection 3.2.2. Therefore, the signer cannot generate a valid ABS that satisfies the policy matrix \mathbf{M} . This is achieved in our ABS presented in Section 5.6.1 scheme because the keys that correspond to the attributes in S are not enough to verify the correctness of the pairing $Y = e(\sigma_2, \sigma_4)/e(\sigma_3, \sigma_1)$. Recall that the attribute keys constructed in Algorithm 1 have the following construction: $sk_{2,i} := g_1^{\mathbf{M}_i(\alpha||\mathbf{v})^\top} \cdot \sigma_i^r$ for each row $i \in \mathcal{I}$. Also, Algorithm 2 shows that $\sigma_2 := \prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (sk_{2,i})^{\gamma_i^s}$ is a part of the ABS signature. If the attribute keys $sk_{2,i}$ corresponding to the attributes in S are not enough to satisfy \mathbf{M} as in our case, then the simplification of the $\prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}} g_1^{\mathbf{M}_i(\alpha||\mathbf{v})^\top \gamma_i}$ is not possible because the equation $\sum \gamma_i M_i = (1, 0, \dots, 0)$ is invalid as explained in Section 3.2, and hence the ABS signature will not successfully verify. A corrupt signer might get the attribute key corresponding to the Secure Boot from another signer so to have enough keys to build an ABS valid signature, but this would not work in our scheme since the attribute keys are bound to the root-key of the device and generated from different seeds r for different users. This prevents any collusion between signers or impersonating attacks. Similar unforgeability arguments follow for our ABSC schemes.

2) To distinguish which attributes were used to generate a signature or any other identifying information associated with the particular signer amongst the users satisfying the given predicate. This might lead to the *device fingerprinting* which in turn can disclose information to the adversary of the internal device's characteristics (e.g., Operating System version, whitelist of binaries loaded as part of the operational stack) that can further lead to implementation disclosure attacks [XX]. The security requirements can be summarized as unforgeability and attribute-signer privacy. For the ABSC, in addition to the above two targets, the ciphertext does not reveal any information about the encrypted message, which we call "Indistinguishability against Chosen Plaintext Attack (IND-CPA)" security.

Property 1 (Attribute Privacy). Given two valid attribute-based signatures σ_1 and σ_2 generated from two different attribute sets \mathbb{A}_1 and \mathbb{A}_2 (associated with two attribute key sets SK_1 and SK_2 generated and certified by a trusted authority) and satisfying the same policy \mathcal{P} . Choose a random signature σ_i from $\{\sigma_1, \sigma_2\}$, the probability that an adversary knows which set of attributes in $\{\mathbb{A}_1, \mathbb{A}_2\}$ used to generate σ_i is $1/2$.

The privacy is achieved in our schemes by the construction of σ_3 and the Shonrr signatures as follows:

$\sigma_3 := \prod_{i \in \mathcal{I}} H_1(i||h_m||\pi(i))^{\gamma_i^s} = \prod_{i \in [n_1]} H_1(i||h_m||\pi(i))^{\gamma_i^s}$ since we choose $\forall i \in [n_1]/\mathcal{I} \gamma_i = 0$. Note that a Shonrr signature is created on all the attributes in the matrix policy \mathbf{M} that represents the policy for the Universe attribute set \mathcal{U} , this not only helps in verifying the construction of σ_3 and hence σ but also hides the attributes used by the signer to satisfy \mathcal{P} into a larger set \mathcal{U} .

Property 2 (Unforgeability). We consider that the ABS scheme is existentially unforgeable against chosen predicate and message attacks. Its formal definition is based on the following game involving a challenger \mathcal{C} and an adversary \mathcal{A} :

- Setup Phase: \mathcal{C} runs Setup. \mathcal{C} retains Privacy CA secret and public keys generated from Setup, sends the public key to \mathcal{A} ;
- Query Phase: \mathcal{A} can perform a polynomially bounded number of queries on (msg, \mathcal{P}) to private key extraction oracle and signing oracle, respectively. These queries will be answered by \mathcal{C} with a secret key.
- Forgery: Finally, \mathcal{A} outputs an ABS signature σ^* on messages msg^* using an attribute set ω^* that satisfies a policy \mathcal{P}^* .

We say that the adversary wins the game if σ^* is a valid signature on message msg^* for a policy \mathcal{P}^* , such that (msg^*, \mathcal{P}^*) has not been queried to the signing oracle and no attribute set ω such that there exists $\omega \subset \omega^*$ satisfying \mathcal{P}^* . The advantage of \mathcal{A} is defined as the probability that it wins the game and should be negligible. The unforgeability of our scheme is based on the security of the FABEO scheme together with the unforgeability of the Schnorr signature.

Property 2 (IND-CPA) The security model for our ABSC scheme used during run-time addresses the property that a ciphertext does not reveal any information about the encrypted message, which we call “Indistinguishability against Chosen Plaintext Attack (IND-CPA)” security and that a ciphertext does not reveal any information about the attribute set, which we call “Attribute Anonymity ” defined in Property 1. We model the adaptive IND-CPA security in a game running between an adversary \mathcal{A} and a challenger \mathcal{C} as follows:

- Setup Phase: \mathcal{C} runs Setup to obtain the Privacy CA public and secret keys. It sends the CA’s public key to the adversary and keeps the secret part.
- Phase 1. \mathcal{A} issues queries to a key generation oracle for a Key generation oracle that issues a set of attribute keys for an attribute set \mathcal{S} under a certain access matrix \mathbf{M} and sends the keys to \mathcal{A} .
- Challenge. \mathcal{A} outputs a challenging attribute set \mathcal{S}^* with the restriction that \mathcal{S}^* cannot satisfy any \mathcal{S} that has been queried in Phase 1 and two equal-length messages msg_0 and msg_1 . Then \mathcal{C} selects a random bit $b \in \{0, 1\}$, runs the encryption algorithm to get the ciphertext CT_b^* on a message msg_b under \mathcal{S}^* and returns the challenge CT_b^* to \mathcal{A} .
- Guess. \mathcal{A} outputs $b' \in \{0, 1\}$ and wins the game if $b = b'$.

An ABSC scheme is adaptively IND-CPA secure if the advantage function defined by the probability $|b' = b| - 1/2$ is negligible. This property follows from the security of FABEO scheme presented in Chapter 3.

Chapter 6

Towards Secure and Scalable Aggregate Attestation

Today's complex medical-supply-chain ecosystems consist of large networks of heterogeneous CMDs, such as biometrics sensors and medical gateways. These smart devices collaborate to provide all kinds of services to benefit a modern medical domain. Such networks are called swarms. However, for such distributed services to be trusted, one needs to ensure that each device in the network behaves correctly. A very effective way to ensure this is to prove the correctness of each device's configurational state. This can be done via remote attestation, which checks the software integrity by detecting modified execution flows or data. Unfortunately, these schemes on their own do not scale to many devices to be attested, such as a central Verifier attesting the entire collaborative network. For example, in a naive approach, individually attesting each device in the network would induce a linearly growing overhead in both communications and computations. Therefore, attesting large swarms requires a new and efficient approach.

These swarms usually consist of multiple groups of heterogeneous devices forming their own subsystems. In these compositions of systems, making valid statements about the security properties of single devices as well as groups is a key challenge ENTRUST tries to resolve. This section introduces the need of establishing federated trust between services and devices using decentralized solutions. Therefore, the so-called Swarm Attestation schemes are a promising technology to include in the ENTRUST framework, overcoming the imposed challenges.

The goal of this section is to, therefore, present a first release of the ENTRUST Secure and Scalable Aggregate Network Attestation towards establishing attestable trust to groups of devices in large-scale medical domains. By attesting the correct behavior of large groups of devices, trust can be established in the whole network by forwarding proof of this validation. In order to fulfill this goal, high and low-end devices need to be aware of this newly introduced overlaying attestation mechanism. The ENTRUST framework has to instruct devices already supporting attestation or verification mechanisms to utilize them for attesting groups or swarms of devices.

Furthermore, the employed swarm attestation strategy should enable the network of devices to continue to operate correctly even if some devices deviate from specified behavior, e.g., as the result of a compromise. The mechanism should therefore be robust and correct in different environments (e.g., centric, distributed, or mobile swarms) and device configurations (e.g., different TCBs). Efficiency is the main goal of this attestation strategy, enabling Verifiers to effortlessly validate the same attestation attribute or different ones in every Prover in an efficient way. To achieve this, the burden of attesting the whole network should be distributed equally among the network's participants.

Medical domains typically consist of a mix of low and high-end CMDs that work together to provide medical functions. To ensure swift responses to changes in the trust level of a subset of CMDs within a medical-service-graph-chain, managing CMDs as a swarm can improve the efficiency and scalability of attestation processes. This approach is advantageous because we often need to attest the same set of properties for CMDs that form static or infrequently changing topologies.

In Chapter 5, we discussed attestation for a single prover, where each CMD was managed as an independent com-

ponent with its trust level monitored. The next step for ENTRUST is to investigate how to elevate trust assessment from the individual CMD level to the swarm level.

6.1 ENTRUST Scalable Aggregate Network Attestation

Swarm attestation schemes aim to provide scalable attestation solutions that verify the trustworthiness of a large-scale network more efficiently than attesting devices individually. This is crucial for complex medical domains like those envisioned in ENTRUST, where the focus is on creating trust-aware medical-service-graph-chains comprising heterogeneous CMDs with different hardware capabilities, TCBs and disparate software configurations. However, the ultimate goal is not merely to reduce communication overhead compared to the naive approach of repeatedly applying single Prover attestation. It is also to enable attestation intelligence on which sets of devices need to be attested collectively during run-time. This might depend on the safety-critical nature and time-sensitivity of the functions and services running in such swarms, which in turn may require different types of assurance claims, affecting the timing of attestation tasks based on available resources, in a non-intrusive manner to avoid harming the overall execution profile of the device.

Consider for instance the “Assistive Healthcare and Remote Patient Monitoring Gateway” scenario, which involves deploying a gateway device (PHG) to the residence of each patient to connect with each medical sensing device that collects health information from the patient. All such PHGs are responsible for transmitting the received information to the TelluCare eHealth platform, where healthcare professionals can remotely evaluate the patient’s health status. This configuration defines a tree-like network structure, starting from the TelluCare server and reaching each low-end medical monitoring and sensing device. As the network expands with the addition of more patients, a method is needed for the fast, efficient, and trustworthy verification of each gateway device’s correctness, as well as the deployment of secure updates if a risk is identified. In this regard, ENTRUST offers the Swarm Attestation enabler, which aims to attest to the correctness of the configuration state of devices in a tree-like structure in a manner that is much more efficient than attesting to each device individually. This scenario entails evaluating the Swarm Attestation scheme dynamically during runtime and its capability to identify compromised gateway devices quickly and efficiently.

Overall, the main motivation is to have more efficient and scalable aggregate network attestation schemes, will enable ENTRUST to make intelligent decisions on how to adjust the execution of such security enablers to identify the optimal balance between converging security and safety without impeding the performance of the deployed devices. The main properties crucial in designing such a swarm attestation protocol are listed in Table 6.1 and elaborated in subsequent sections and chapters : Network Topology, Number of Verifiers, Trustworthiness of Verifiers, Prover’s Memory Regions considered at the Attestation, Verification of Exchanged Communication Data among Provers, Granularity of Attestation Result, Efficiency, and Privacy.

Property	Description
Network Topology	This property, as the name suggests, pertains to the topology followed by the devices in the swarm to be attested. As described in Section 6.1.1 such a topology can either be static or dynamic depending on whether devices demonstrate any mobility that will affect the construction of their routing trees when it comes to the parent node (with whom they communicate and might take the role of the Prover). Another aspect to take into consideration here is the need (or not) for establishing federated trust between the devices in the swarm . Essentially, this relates to whether a <i>hierarchical topology</i> is needed in a scenario where the device at each layer can act as the Prover for its children nodes or a <i>tree-based</i> structure is allowed where only the root node can act as the Verifier. This, of course, is directly related to the below property regarding the number of Verifiers that can be active in a swarm network. Depending on all the above, this affects the type of communication to be established per Prover device considering also the various security and privacy needs.

Number of Verifiers	This property depicts the number of devices that can act as the Verifier in a swarm network. It can either be the case that there is only one root Verifier that is responsible for assessing the received (aggregate) result of the entire swarm; or multiple Verifiers responsible for attesting the correctness of their children nodes/devices. The latter also considers the mobility aspects that some devices might exhibit which, in turn, will lead to changing parent nodes that should be able to act as Verifiers.
Trustworthiness of Verifiers	This property reflects any trustworthiness assumptions to be made for the correctness of the Verifier device. It can either be the case that Verifiers are considered <i>trustworthy</i> , thus, they can have full knowledge of a Prover's program execution details and in-memory layout without any privacy breach. This is what is the current state-of-the-art in the existing attestation landscape. However, in ENTRUST, we make no assumptions on the Verifier trustworthiness been aligned with the Zero Trust principle that dictates that no initial trust can be assumed between entities.
Prover's System Properties for Attestation	This property pertains to the type of system properties considered for attestation (the types of attributes that need to be attested). Another important aspect here is whether all swarm devices are attesting the same types of properties or whether different properties can be considered in the context of the same swarm.

Table 6.1: Swarm Attestation Properties

6.1.1 Swarm Topology

Swarm attestation schemes generally consider the attestation of two types of swarm networks: static or dynamic networks. In static swarms, the network is characterized by being static and always interconnected, which facilitates the construction of a spanning-tree where two connected nodes are neighbors in the communication graph. An important property of swarm attestation that relies on spanning-tree is that each device can communicate only with its direct neighbors. In these schemes, each device statically attests its children and reports back to its parent the number of children that successfully passed the attestation protocol. In the end, an aggregated report with the total number of devices successfully attested is transmitted to the Verifier. In dynamic swarms, the network topology does not remain static and changes even while the attestation protocol is executing. Thus, interactions in a dynamic swarm cannot be represented by a spanning-tree construction. Overall, in dynamic attestation protocols, devices first share their respective "knowledge" with other devices and then use consensus mechanisms to agree on a common knowledge about the whole network.

6.1.2 Verifiers in Swarms

Swarm Attestation (SA), as any other attestation can be verified by *one centralized verifier* where the attestation process is initiated by a centralized Verifier. At the end of the attestation, the verifier's role is to collect the final attestation result obtained as a consequence of running the remote attestation process over a swarm. Usually, a centralized Verifier is considered as a *trusted* entity by design. Swarm attestation also can be verified by many Distributed Verifiers. In a SA protocol with many distributed verifiers, one Verifier can attest to one or more Provers. In such schemes, the Verifier can be assumed as a *trusted* or an *untrusted* entity. In our SA model, we consider many distributed verifiers where we distribute the trust among verifiers, this leads to a *decentralized* approach of verifying the SA. Verifiers in our protocol are classified into two main entities: the high-end devices that verify the one-time signatures generated by their connected low-end devices and the external verifiers that verify the construction of the Merkle tree as will be explained in Section 6.3.

6.1.3 Prover's Attestation in Swarms

Each device participating in the swarm performs attestation and hence plays the role of a Prover. The attestation aims to attest to a certain attribute or combinations of attributes. These attributes include the swarm secure boot, key management, and an authentic tracer. The external verifier chooses the corresponding fresh challenge to attest the attribute(s) needed. Every low-end device will then prove that it possesses this identified attribute by sending the corresponding challenge response. The response includes a one-time signature that is verified by the high-end

device (which plays the role of the verifier here). The high-end also attaches its attestation with the necessary information to enable the verification of the Merkle tree construction and passes the branch attestation to its parent node to be sent to the external verifier.

6.1.4 CMD Service-Graph-Chain Attestation

The purpose of the ENTRUST framework is to provide operational assurance to large-scale Systems-of-Systems (SoS) of CMDs to achieve the **required level of trustworthiness of the entire supply chain ecosystem**. Unlike the conventional single-Prover and single-Verifier attestation schemes, there are cases where the attestation of a large number of connected medical devices separately to be performed by a single Verifier is not efficient, as it requires a large amount of time and computational resources. To this end, we have developed the ENTRUST Swarm Attestation (SA) enabler, which not only aims to attest to the correctness of a set (swarm) of devices, in a manner that is **more computationally efficient than attesting each device individually**, but also enable attesting the whole swarm security and safety attributes in a privacy-preserving manner. The first version of the ENTRUST SA scheme will be presented in this deliverable, where we provide information regarding the considered system and adversarial model, network topology, and a detailed description of the designed static attestation protocol.

6.2 Static vs. Dynamic Swarm Attestation in ENTRUST

In the 1st release of the ENTRUST, we consider *static attestation* of heterogeneous devices participating in *static network topology*, e.g., static attestation of devices deployed in a medical domain. This network is structured as a hierarchical fog computing model as shown in Figure 6.1.

This network consists of three layers with the following characteristics:

- **Low-End devices:** Each Low-End device is a resource-constrained CMD which are not equipped with a rich TEE-based TCB. Consequently, the Low-End CMDs support only PUF-based attestation, as described in Chapter 5.
- **High-End devices:** Each High-End device is equipped with a TEE-based TCB. High-end devices have a parent-child relationship with the low-end CMDs. Thus, the High-End devices are responsible for aggregating the attestation result they receive from their child CMDs.
- **Verifier:** In ENTRUST, the aggregated attestation result to be validated entities such as the Domain Manager.

In this first release of the system model, we have a static topology featuring multiple provers and one verifier. Additionally, a semi-trusted high-end CMD serves as a worker, responsible for collecting signatures and creating the evidence to be sent to an external verifier. The specifics of the aggregation scheme are detailed in ??.

By "semi-trusted," we mean that while the high-end CMD cannot replay messages or forge signatures due to the robust cryptographic primitives of swarm attestation, it can intercept messages (acting as an honest-but-curious middleperson) and choose not to forward the attestation evidence to the verifier. This design ensures a balance between security and functionality, leveraging strong cryptographic guarantees to prevent malicious actions while acknowledging potential passive observations by the CMD.

6.2.1 Trust Assumptions & Security/Privacy Requirements

In this section, we describe the security properties that the swarm attestation scheme in ENTRUST should satisfy in order to be resilient to any adversarial actions that can occur. The attestation of each *Prover* that belongs to the Swarm S should satisfy various security properties and trust requirements. Specifically, the individual attestation of each *Prover* should guarantee: *Integrity, Authenticity, Correctness, Completeness, Atomicity, and Freshness*.

Figure 6.1: System model of Swarm attestation in ENTRUST

These properties can be further enhanced with requirements that dwell on the **safety and time constraints** of real-time systems (as the ones envisioned in the context of the ASSURED use cases) and can be summarized as: **Remote Verify Integrity, Efficiency, and Swarm Topology In-dependency**.

SA Requirement	Description	Related Attacks
Remote Verify Integrity	This property relates to the ability of executing a secure attestation scheme as the enabler for the overall swarm attestation protocol capable of providing assurance claims, on the integrity of a swarm device, running tasks with real-time execution requirements that needs to overcome the inherent conflict between real-time execution guarantees and integrity guarantees for the measurement procedure to capture the Prover device's state. More specifically, this property translates to the need of the Verifier been able to make a decision on the correct configuration or execution state of a Prover based on correct and authentic measurements, as extracted by the Tracer, with verifiable evidence on their integrity.	Remote Software Attack; Network Attack; Man-in-the-Middle Attack; Unauthorized Swarm Attestation Attack; Selective Attestation Jamming Attack
Efficiency	This relates to the efficiency of the overall swarm attestation scheme, irrespective of the number of devices comprising the target swarm to be attested.	Network Attack; Man-in-the-Middle Attack; Unauthorized Swarm Attestation Attack; Selective Attestation Jamming Attack

Swarm Topology In-dependency	As described in Chapter 6.1.1, there can be multiple system topologies to cover various mobility and connectivity aspects as well as different number of Verifiers that can be encountered in complex medical-service-graph-chains: either static or dynamic topologies . These have different requirements as it pertains to how the swarm attestation scheme will operate - especially considering that one mobile node might need to change its parent (verifying) node as it changes its position which translates to having multi-hop verification, thus, the need to protect against unauthorized attacks.	Network Attack; Man-in-the-Middle Attack
-------------------------------------	---	--

Table 6.2: Swarm Attestation Generic Requirements

Additional properties that are introduced by the characteristics of the types of environments considered in AS-SURED and the features of the heterogeneous devices include **Malicious device Identification, Mobility Tolerance, and Opaque & Adjustable Privacy Level**.

ENTRUST SA Requirement	Description
Malicious device Identification	Irrespective of the level of detail that is included in the aggregate attestation result, the High-End CMD should be able to correctly trace back to the identity of any device with a failed attestation result which represents an indication of risk. This translates to the need of privacy-preserving traceability : In case of a “true” swarm attestation result where the root Verifier simply checks the sanity of the overall swarm network, the identities of the low-end devices can be protected. However, in the case of a failed attestation result been detected, it should be feasible for the high-end CMD to trace back this result to the High-End device and request to get access to the attestation result of the specific device with the failed attestation.
Mobility Tolerance	The attestation protocol should be efficient and it can tolerate device mobility to some extent. It means that the attestation scheme can efficiently and securely attest the swarm as long as the mobile node could re-join the attestation with different joining point (i.e., High-End device). This should also be able to protect against unauthorized swarm attestation attacks , especially for mobile nodes that re-join to a different part of the network: they should be verified by the new High-End device when it comes to the validity of their identity .
Opaque & Adjustable Privacy Level	This property focuses on two privacy aspects that are core to our scenarios: both when it comes to device identity privacy and attestation evidence privacy . For the former, as the name suggests, it should be possible to “hide” the identity of an Low-End device, as part of the swarm, or protect the <i>unlinkability and anonymity</i> of the High-End device that acts as the swarm head for aggregating the received measurements/results from the Low-End devices. For the latter, this pertains to safeguarding the information that can be implicitly extracted through the monitored system traces.

Table 6.3: ENTRUST-Specific SA Requirements

In addition to the functional specifications and trust requirements, the swarm attestation in ENTRUST must ensure several critical security properties. Firstly, it must be existentially unforgeable, meaning only authenticated devices with secret keys can produce valid message signatures, preventing impersonation and unauthorized attacks. Linkability is essential for associating signatures with devices or basenames, ensuring traceability within the swarm. Anonymity is preserved by preventing adversaries from distinguishing whether signatures came from one or multiple devices. Provenance ensures verifiers can confirm the aggregate result’s origins without compromising individual device privacy, except in case of failed attestation. Non-frameability guarantees no false attribution of signatures to honest devices. Traceability allows identifying the specific group member behind a signature, particularly when an attestation fails. Coalition resistance and exculpability prevent groups from producing untraceable signatures and ensure no member can sign on behalf of others. User revocation allows the removal of compromised devices. Overall integrity ensures that the aggregated attestation result accurately reflects the claimed integrity measurements. Privacy preservation ensures devices authenticate without exposing details to verifiers, and the integrity of communication data among devices is maintained throughout the process.

As previously mentioned, there are two privacy challenges that must be addressed in complex systems when attempting to simultaneously attest a swarm of devices: **device Privacy Identity** and **Attestation Evidence Privacy**.

The latter relates to the *absence of privacy* during the performance of all underlying attestation tasks, as Provers need to fully disclose program execution or configuration details, which is undesirable when such information should be kept confidential. **Allowing Verifiers to have complete knowledge of a Prover’s memory layout and configuration profile (e.g., type of OS loaded) makes them vulnerable to privacy breaches and implementation disclosure attacks:** “honest-but-curious” verifying entities can extract sensitive information on the device’s configuration, safety-critical functionalities, etc., which can be exploited to compromise its overall availability. Moreover, revealing all execution details for verification is contrary to the **Zero Trust** principle, which dictates that **no initial trust can be entrusted between entities**. Disclosing information on running processes of a system can enable adversaries to use such knowledge to launch run-time attacks against the program’s codebase.

To address this issue, it is necessary to verify the correct execution and/or configuration profile of a device (in the swarm) without being able to determine the actual device profile that is running. In other words, consider that each (swarm) Prover device produces (and signs) a message m as the result of the attestation process to be sent to the Verifier: **No verifying entity should be able to trace the content of m back to the device origin while simultaneously providing the Verifier with verifiable evidence of the device’s operational assurance.**

Regarding **device Privacy Identity**, this presents a double-edged sword: On one hand, it is necessary to **protect the system from malicious devices** by identifying the origin of a potential compromise, thus, revealing the identity of a device with a failed attestation result. On the other hand, it is also crucial to **protect devices from untrusted verifying entities**, especially those where the attestation history shows they have never been compromised or only rarely so, by enabling *unlinkability*: **No successful attestation result should be linked back to its device origin** as this could lead to attacks such as implementation disclosure attacks. It could also enable “honest-but-curious” entities that do not wish to interfere with the protocol’s functionality but are interested in creating device attestation profiles - *how often a device is required to perform an attestation task (which might reveal the type of safety-critical functions executed), the type of attestation task, the set of devices comprising the entire swarm, etc.*

6.3 ENTRUST Low-end Device (Swarm) Attestation

6.3.1 Setup Phase

Assuming the successful enrollment of a high-end CMD to the medical domain, then the Domain Manager can allocate low-end devices as it’s children. The DM generates $N = 2^n$ challenges C_1, \dots, C_N . The challenge set is divided into subsets in a way that allows each subset of challenges to attest to a certain low-end device attribute such as secure boot, integrity, etc. The DM sends the challenge subsets to the manufacturer together with the branch device IDs and the attributes that correspond to each subset of challenges.

For each subset of challenges, the manufacturer creates the k^{th} low-end devices’ private keys R_i^k (using a key derivation function KDF with the knowledge of the k^{th} PUF root key). With input R_i^k , the golden value of the *attribute to be attested* and the high-end device ID, the OTS- KEYGEN algorithm generates the corresponding one-time public key PK_i^k for the k^{th} low-end device. The manufacturer then concatenates PK_i^k for $k \in [1, B]$ to get the one-time public key of the low-end devices in the branch for a challenge C_i , i.e. $PK_i = (PK_i^1 | \dots | PK_i^B)$, where B is the total number of the branch low-end devices.

The manufacturer creates a shared revocation secret S^k for each k^{th} low-end device. This secret will be later used by the low-end device to perform revocation checks.

The manufacturer then sends PK_i s to the DM who creates the Merkle tree using the following steps:

- For each $i \in [0, N - 1]$, the DM calculates $h_i = H(PK_i)$
- The hash values h_i are placed as leaves and hashed recursively to form a binary tree as follows: Let $a_{i,j}$ denote the node in the tree with height i , and left-right position j . The hash values $h_i = a_{0,i}$ are the leaf nodes. The inner nodes are calculated by

$$a_{i,j} = H(a_{i-1, 2j} || a_{i-1, 2j+1})$$

where $i = 1, \dots, h$ and $j = 0, \dots, 2^{i-1}$, where h denotes the height of the tree. An example is shown in Figure 5.6.

- The DM publishes mpk together with the challenge set $\{C_i\}$ divided into subsets of challenges with their corresponding attributes to be attested for the branch.
- The DM sends the Merkle tree to the mother high-end device of the branch.

6.3.2 Attestation & Report Phase

- The external verifier that wants to attest a branch in the Swarm sends a challenge C_i that has not been used before to the high-end device.
- The high-end forwards C_i to its children low-end devices.
- The k^{th} PUF embedded in the low-end device k outputs the response R_i^k for the challenge C_i .
- The k^{th} low-end device runs the KEYGEN algorithm that takes inputs R_i^k , the value of the *attribute to be attested* and the mother high-end ID to generate its one-time public key $PK_i'^k$.
- The low-end device signs the challenge using the corresponding secret key R_i^k resulting in a one-time signature σ_i^k .
- When revocation check is required, the low-end device further creates an $HMAC(\text{Low-end device ID}, S^k, C_i)$.
- Each low-end device sends its $(PK_i'^k, \sigma_i^k)$ to the mother high-end device.
- After receiving the outputs of all its B children low-end devices, the high-end device verifies each σ_i^k under $PK_i'^k$ for $k \in [1, B]$. If any verification fails, the high-end aborts. Otherwise, the high-end calculates the OTS public key $PK_i' = (PK_i'^1 | \dots | PK_i'^B)$, then sends $(PK_i', Auth_i)$ and, if needed, $HMAC(\text{Low-end device ID}, S^k, C_i)$ to the external verifier.

6.3.3 Verification Phase

- Note that this C_i is only allowed to be used once, this prevents replay attacks. The authentication path is described in Chapter 3. The verifier with the knowledge of mpk verifies the authentication path. If this path leads to the same mpk , the verifier accepts, otherwise rejects. The verification steps work as follows:
 - The Verifier computes $a'_{0,i} = H(PK_i')$.
 - Using the authentication path $Auth_i$ computes the root of the Merkle tree mpk' .
 - If $mpk = mpk'$, the verifier declares the signature as valid otherwise rejects it.
- Note that the signature is only verified correctly if $PK_i' = PK_i$ that was set by the manufacturer, i.e. each $PK_i'^k$ matches the device's PK_i^k set by the device manufacturer in the MUD profile. Upon successful verification, the verifier is convinced that each low-end device satisfies that the attested attribute matches the golden value without knowing the exact current attribute value, this provides *Attribute Confidentiality*.

Revocation Check: We assume that all compromised Low-end devices are identified, and their revocation keys are extracted by the manufacturer and added to a set of revoked keys called the Key Revocation List KRL. The revocation check only checks if the low-end device was revoked before or not. This check doesn't identify a new compromise of low-end devices.

- To prove that the low-end device is not revoked, the device also sends a symmetric signature revocation token

$$HMAC(\text{Low-end device ID}, S^k, C_i)$$

where C_i is the challenge on which the attestation was created in the attestation phase and S^k is the device's secrete revocation key set by the manufacturer. The verification by the external verifier works as in the Verification phase. If the MSS is verified, the verifier sends C_i together with the Low-end device identity to the manufacturer to check that the device is not revoked.

- The manufacturer, with access to the **Key Revocation List (KRL)** defined by the following revoked key set $\{S_1^*, \dots, S_L^*\}$, can only do this check. The manufacturer verifies the *HMAC* with the knowledge of S^k , C_i and the identity of the k^{th} low-end device, then checks that none of the keys in KRL matches S^k , in this case, the check pass. The manufacturer notifies the verifier about the check output.
- If the verification and the revocation check pass then the verifier outputs 1 otherwise 0.

6.4 Scalable Attestation in Dynamic Topologies

Figure 6.2: Dynamic Swarm Attestation

An important feature that we will investigate, is to consider ENTRUST Swarm Attestation in the context of dynamic topologies where the mobility factor of devices is crucial. In such scenarios (consider for instance the case of “*Smart Ambulance*” where the connected medical devices frequently move from one IoT Gateway to another, as their parent), we need to re-design the **Setup** phase of our swarm attestation protocol (including both device and swarm initialization phases) to be able to consider **continuous authorization and authentication of Low-end devices as they are moving from one high-end device to another**. The idea is to let the manufacturer issue for each low-end device a public key as before PK_i^k but this public key differs if the low-end device is connected to a

different high-end device. Our proposal for the static swarm as described before considers only one mother high-end device for each Low-end device. In the dynamic swarm, the setup should consider all possible combinations of high-low-end devices, for each a specific public key will be issued by the manufacturer.

With input R_i^k , the golden value of the *attribute to be attested* and the high-end device ID_l , the OTS- KEYGEN algorithm generates the corresponding one-time public key PK_i^{kl} for the k^{th} low-end device connected to the l^{th} high-end device. Whenever the high-end device l sends a challenge C_i to its k^{th} low-end device, the latter responds by a one-time signature signed by R_i^k and its corresponding verification key PK_i^{kl} . The high-end device checks that PK_i^{kl} matches with the certified manufacturer PK_i^{kl} then verifies the one-time signature. This step is repeated for all the children's low-end devices then a concatenation of the low-end devices' outputs is done by the high-end device. Consider the example in Figure 6.2 where we have a Swarm two high-end devices and four low-end devices. We have eight possible combinations of high-low end devices, each low-end device can have the first high-end or the second high-end device as its mother. Based on these combinations, the manufacturer establishes eight PKs PK^{ij} where $i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ and $j \in \{1, 2\}$ as inputs of the KEYGEN function. These public keys are generated from the same challenge C_i and binded together to form a unique low-end public key PK_i for the challenge C_i for any possible combination of the low-high end device. The merkle tree is then formed by the DM as in Section 6.

Chapter 7

ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base Instantiation in Envisioned Use Cases

In the previous chapters, a comprehensive description regarding the functionalities offered by the ENTRUST's Trusted Execution Architecture was provided for the secure lifecycle management of CMDs, not only considering high-end but also their resources constrained counterparts. Here, a detailed mapping of the aforementioned functionalities that will be evaluated in the context of the envisioned use cases is presented in the following figure (Figure 7.1).

All functionalities aimed at preparing a CMD for establishing trustworthiness are evaluated across all use cases, allowing us to benchmark different medical services and assess ENTRUST's adaptability to various time constraints. For attestation, system properties to be traced and monitored are distributed based on the trust models defined in D3.2, enabling extensive evaluation of the overhead involved, considering the complexity of each measurement. Attesting static properties incurs less overhead than dynamic properties; however, efficiently identifying RTL changes and making trust decisions within a small time window requires accounting for the associated overhead. The same evaluation logic applies to ABSC and CCs regarding their testing. As detailed in D6.1, consistent and reliable measurements will be ensured by using the same underlying hardware in all scenarios.

The secure CMD onboarding, since it constitutes one of the most crucial aspects of ENTRUST, will be demonstrated in the context of all envisioned use cases as it includes both families of CMDs considered here (i.e. high- and low-end devices). The same holds for the attestation enablers, the main trustworthiness generators based on which the trust assessment will be conducted. Despite the fact that the attestation mechanisms as well as the trust assessment methodology proposed in ENTRUST are potentially applicable to a varying set of trust properties, the focus here is devoted to **integrity**. In the case of the high-end CMDs, integrity is provided through CIV, whereas in the case of their low-end counterparts, through secure boot outcome as extracted from the tracer, which will be also evaluated in all use cases. The provision of conformity certificates will be validated in the context of use case 1 and 3.1, enabling any external stakeholder to verify the correct execution of the CMDs, whereas swarm attestation scheme in use case 2 and 3.2 since the network configuration in both cases defines a tree-like structure. Finally, ABSC scheme will be tested for intra-domain trust establishment in all envisioned use cases, whereas for the inter-domain trust establishment will be validated in the context of the use case 2 and 3.1.

Use case 1, led by Kardinero, entails the use of the KardinBLU ECG and multi-parameter monitoring system, which is a Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) acquisition device capable of collecting patient's cardiological data utilizing a set of sensors. Those sensors collect and send the received data to the KardinBLU ECG device and then, utilizing a gateway, provided by partner TLU, are forwarded to the hospital backend so that it can be used for patient diagnosis purposes. In such a case, the ENTRUST TCB offers secure device onboarding for both high- and low-end CMDs (i.e. TLU gateway and KardinBLU respectively) to protect the integrity of such devices. Operational assurance is provided by the continuous assessment mechanisms that attest to the correctness of the configuration state of the device utilizing the attestation enablers and the tracer, whereas the ABS flavor of ABSC scheme is employed when a specific security policy has to be satisfied since both high and low-end devices belong in the same domain. The

aforementioned functionalities are also evaluated in the context **use case 2**, led by TLU, where remote assistance for patients suffering from chronic diseases is facilitated by employing the Tellu Personal Health Gateway, which is responsible for collecting data from various medical devices (i.e. KardinBLU) and sending them to the TelluCare cloud platform for medical processing, enabling medical personnel to access the collected data in order to perform remote patient monitoring and to record the data and events in the patient’s electronic health journal. They are also applicable to both scenarios of **use case 3** where the condition of the patient is continuously monitored, through a set of medical devices, during her/his transportation to the hospital (i.e use case 3.1 led by PARTICLE, ULS) and legacy, potentially outdated, CMDs are utilized for monitoring patients in an emergency care unit (i.e. use case 3.2 led by POLARIS), as well as in **use case 4**. In the latter, precision biomarkers and digital therapeutics are employed in order to facilitate the provision of healthcare services pertaining to the Mental Health of patients, thus facilitating the enhancement of their emotional intelligence and the development of appropriate coping mechanisms and behavioral techniques.

Functionalities to be evaluated per Use Case					
TCB Functionalities	Use Case 1 (Kardinero)	Use Case 2 (TLU)	Use Case 3.1 (PARTICLE&ULS)	Use Case 3.2 (POLARIS)	Use Case 4 (SL)
Secure CMD Onboarding	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Attestation Enablers	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Tracer	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Conformity Certificates	✓		✓		
Swarm Attestation		✓		✓	
Inter-domain ABSC		✓	✓		
Intra-domain ABSC	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Figure 7.1: The ENTRUST functionalities described in D4.2 to be evaluated in the context of the Use Cases.

Chapter 8

Technical Road-Map

In the following table, we outline the Technical Road-Map that we will follow for the Second Release of ENTRUST's Runtime Assurance & Certification Framework in D4.3:

Feature	Research Plan
CIV	Currently, we have implemented CIV with verifiable policy enforcement and key restriction usage policies. In the second release, we will enhance privacy by elevating the Attestation Key to a DAA Key. Additionally, CIV will be integrated with the software update process described in D3.2 to ensure post-validation of correct updates.
Verifiable Key Restriction Usage Policies	We will implement a mechanism to protect against roll-back attacks as described in D4.1.
Key Management Extensions	We will develop interfaces following the GlobalPlatform API to manage all of ENTRUST's keys.
Swarm Attestation	We plan to expand the functionality to support dynamic topologies.
Use Cases	We will integrate ENTRUST's Trusted Computing Base (TCB) into the use cases.
Crypto Schemes	We will conduct a mathematical security analysis for all schemes and implement the cryptographic schemes.
VPs	We plan to encode and wrap Attestation Keys (AKs) into Verifiable Policies (VPs).
Low-End and High-End Authentication	We aim to extend the scheme to achieve non-repudiation and establish secure, authenticated channels between low-end CMDs.

Table 8.1: Technical Road-Map

Chapter 9

Conclusions

This Deliverable presented the first version of ENTRUST's Runtime Assurance and Certification Framework for the secure lifecycle management of CMDs. ENTRUST aims to transform CMDs with hardened TC-based RoTs, enabling trust bootstrapping from secure boot to runtime trust assessment. This deliverable has detailed the mechanisms for trust assessment at both the CMD and domain levels, including protocols for runtime trust assessment and re-establishment in case of trust failures.

The ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base, leveraging both a TEE for high-end CMDs and a PUF for low-end CMDs, is presented. It is built so as to enable a Interoperable Security Stack that exposes trusted services that are agnostic to the underlying RoT.

In this context, a full documentation of the Zero-Touch onboarding, the Verifiable Credentials designs and the Sign-cryption schemes has been provided, and the deliverable elaborated on how those technologies are synthesised for the provision of an enhanced ZTO Scheme with Efficient Attribute-based Signatures in ENTRUST.

Additionally, the Enablers for the Secure Lifecycle Management of CMDs are documented. Those constitute cryptographic schemes for the CMD Attestation, Key-Restriction usage policies, provision of Conformity Certificates, and Verifiable Presentations. Different schemes were created for the two types of CMDs, enabling their interoperability. Also, the swarm attestation of low-end CMDs was extensively covered.

In conclusion, this deliverable has established a foundational framework for achieving ENTRUST's vision of secure lifecycle management for CMDs. By leveraging advanced Trusted Computing and cryptographic techniques, it sets the stage for building a comprehensive, interoperable security framework. The developments and insights presented here will guide the subsequent phases of the ENTRUST project, with the second version of the trusted execution architecture, including refinements and new developments, to be presented in D4.3.

Appendix A

Glossary

(Medical) Domain Refers to the entirety of the infrastructure of the medical organization where a Connected Medical Device (CMD) is deployed, including the backend infrastructure (servers), medical devices operating within the organization, and interconnectivity between all aforementioned entities.

AI-based Intrusion/Misbehavior Detection This component applies AI-based methods on the emulation performed on the Digital Twin (DT), as well as information collected during the runtime of the operation of the device using probes, in order to determine whether the behavior of the device deviates from the normal behavior of the device.

ATL The Actual Trust Level (ATL) reflects the result of an evaluation of a trust proposition, for a specific CMD, as defined in a trust model managed by the ENTRUST Trust Assessment Framework (TAF). It quantifies the extent to which a certain node or data can be considered trustworthy based on the available evidence.

Attestation Agent The component of the CMD which is responsible for the execution of the attestation logic of an attestation enabler, as well as communicating with external entities in order to share attestation-related information.

Authentication The process which aims to verify the authenticity of a device, prior to its Onboarding and Enrolment into the (Medical) Domain. This process is performed by the Authentication Server of the Manufacturing domain through the Domain Manager, using the Root ID Key of the device.

Authentication Server The Authentication Server is responsible for authenticating the device using its Root ID Key, in order to enable its enrolment and onboarding into the (Medical) Domain.

CMD A medical device that has been deployed, enrolled, and onboarded into a (Medical) Domain. Note that this term cannot be used during the Manufacturing (Design) Phase of the ENTRUST action workflow, since this phase considers the device in isolation, and can only be applied during the Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase and the Runtime Phase of the ENTRUST action workflow.

Conformity Certificate A certificate which is created after a successful attestation process on a device and is stored on the ledger, so that an external entity is able to audit the correctness of the attested set of attributes of the device. The Conformity Certificate utilizes Privacy Attribute-Based Credentials (PABCs) in order to share those attributes in a privacy-preserving manner.

Device Tracer The capabilities of the device (e.g., eBPFs) to collect types of trust evidence or attestation evidence specified by the Trust Policy of the device in order to prove the correctness of the required trust attributes of the device.

Device-level eMUD Defines the foundational security requirements of a device, outlining the necessary operational characteristics to mitigate threats and vulnerabilities, considering the device in isolation (i.e., before it is deployed to the actual medical domain).

Digital Twin The Digital Twin refers to a digital representation of a device, which is used in order to perform an emulation of the identified types of attacks and can provide the basis for the detection of deviations from the known and expected behavior of the device. It may also be used in the context of secure software updates, where an up-to-date contextual information of a device is required to perform the targeted assignment of software updates.

Domain Manager The Domain Manager is a centralized server deployed at the infrastructure level of a (Medical) Domain, responsible for the Authentication, Enrolment, and Onboarding of medical devices into the domain. It also acts as an orchestrator for the operation of all ENTRUST components between the medical domain, as well as the mediator between the device, the Blockchain infrastructure, and the MUD Server.

Domain-level eMUD Extends the Device-level extended Manufacturer Usage Description (eMUD) in order to include device characteristics, threats, and vulnerabilities that considering its positioning within the medical domain, and specifies security enablers for mitigating domain-level threats and vulnerabilities.

Enrolment Entails the issuance of the set of Verifiable Credentials (VCs) of a device through the Privacy Certification Authority (CA), after it has been successfully authenticated.

Formal Verification The Formal Verification component is the component of the ENTRUST framework which is responsible for checking whether the design of the device satisfies the security requirements identified for the particular device, by specifying and using models of the critical security protocols and schemes of ENTRUST and checking whether the security properties hold for the specific model.

Key Restriction Usage Policy A local attestation policy dictating that a specific cryptographic key cannot be used by a device, unless it is known to be in a correct and trustworthy state, based on the characteristics contained in the Policy Hash of the device.

LLM In the context of ENTRUST, this refers to a model used by the Threat Modeling (TM) component in order to create attack scenarios in natural language to set forth expectations regarding what types of attacks could occur in a specific infrastructure.

Manufacturing (Design) Phase The Manufacturing phase of the ENTRUST framework includes all actions taken from the construction of the actual device until it leaves the manufacturing domain and is deployed to the medical domain where it will be enrolled and onboarded. This phase includes the identification of threats and vulnerabilities by the Manufacturer and the Threat Modeling component, the Formal Verification of the source code and binaries on the device, the emulation of identified threats using the Digital Twin of the device, and an initial Risk Assessment (RA) of the device in isolation (i.e., before it is actually deployed to the medical domain).

Merkle Tree A Merkle tree is a data structure used in cryptography that efficiently verifies the integrity and consistency of data. It consists of leaves that represent data blocks and non-leaf nodes that are cryptographic hashes of their child nodes, culminating in a single root hash that securely represents the entire data..

MUD Server The MUD Server is responsible for the storage of the Device-level eMUD and the Domain-level extended Manufacturer Usage Description (eMUD) of the CMDs. They can be retrieved based on the MUD URL provided by the Manufacturer and contained within the device, so that the specified security controls can be applied by the device.

Onboarding Entails the integration of a medical device into the (Medical) Domain, after its successful Authentication and Enrolment. In this context, the device needs to provide a Verifiable Presentation (VP) to the Domain Manager containing the set of attributes that the device needs to verifiably prove ownership of in order to be enrolled into the domain.

OP-TEE OP-TEE (Open Portable Trusted Execution Environment) is an open-source project that provides a secure, isolated execution environment for running trusted applications on modern Arm-based systems. It ensures confidentiality and integrity of sensitive data and operations by leveraging hardware security features..

Policy Hash Values that can be used in order to verify the operational correctness of the device based on specific characteristics of the device (e.g., secure boot output, type of Secure Element, Trusted Computing Base (TCB) specification).

Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase The Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) phase of the ENTRUST framework includes the actions taken from the moment the device is deployed from the Manufacturer to the medical domain, until it begins its actual operation in the context of the domain. It includes two core phases: (i) The device authentication, enrolment, and onboarding, and (ii) the re-evaluation of the recalculation of the Required Trust Level (RTL) of the device based on domain-specific threats and vulnerabilities identified by the System Administrator, the Threat Modeling, the Digital Twin, and the Formal Verification component.

Privacy CA The entity responsible for the issuance of the Verifiable Credentials (VCs) of the CMD containing the device attributes or characteristics based on which Trust Assessment is performed, after it has been successfully authenticated through the Authentication Server.

Protection Profile The Protection Profile of the device is the part of the Device-level eMUD or Domain-level eMUD which contains the identified threats and vulnerabilities for the device, as well as the mitigation measures which can be employed for their mitigation during runtime.

PUF A physical unclonable function (PUF), also known as a physically-unclonable function (which represents a slightly less secure measure), is a unique physical object that cannot be replicated through physical means using the same technology. Given a specific input and set of conditions (challenge), it generates a distinct "digital fingerprint" (response) that serves as a unique identifier..

Remote Attestation A secure mechanism where a Verifier entity aims to verify the correctness of one or more attributes of a Prover device (e.g., configuration integrity or control flow). This is typically performed by the Verifier issuing an attestation challenge to the Prover, who needs to collect the appropriate data as attestation evidence (using its Device Tracer) and construct the appropriate response in order to prove the correctness of the specified attributes.

Risk Assessment The Risk Assessment component of ENTRUST is responsible for performing risk quantification on the device based on all the identified threats and vulnerabilities, both at the manufacturing domain considering the device in isolation, and at the medical domain considering the interdependencies of the device with other entities of the service graph chain. It is also responsible for the calculation of the RTL of the device based on the identified threats and vulnerabilities, as well as its recalculation in case new threats or zero-day exploits are detected during runtime.

RoT The (Hardware) Root of Trust (RoT) is the minimal set of security guarantees usually provided by the hardware that is sufficient to guarantee the security of a larger TCB.

RTL The RTL reflects the amount of trustworthiness a device considers required in order to characterize it as trusted, based on the identified threats and vulnerabilities for the particular type of device.

Runtime Phase The Runtime phase includes all actions in order to ensure the trustworthiness of the CMD during runtime. This entails the execution of security controls, such as Remote Attestation (RA) schemes and the runtime calculation of the Actual Trust Level (ATL) of the CMD. In case $ATL < RTL$, the device is determined to be in an untrustworthy state and additional mitigation measures may need to be applied, such as the deployment of a Secure Software Update.

Secure Software Update This process refers to the secure deployment of a software or firmware patch through the Digital Twin of the device, in case a vulnerability has been detected and needs to be addressed.

Software Verification The Software Verification component is responsible for checking the safety of software applications running on the medical device, as well as libraries running on the device, using Indices of Compromise from multiple intelligence sources based on the identified threat landscape.

System Administrator The person or entity who has in-depth knowledge of the (Medical) Domain and its specific requirements, is responsible for providing information on domain-specific threats and vulnerabilities to the Risk Assessment component, and is able to re-assess the risks identified by the ENTRUST component and the mitigation measures required in order to address them.

TAF A software framework which, given a trust model for a specific function running inside a CMD, is able to evaluate trust sources for trustworthiness evidence, as well as evaluate propositions within the trust model to obtain their ATLS. An RTL can also be evaluated and trust decisions can be taken and communicated to the application.

TCB The Trusted Computing Base (TCB) of a computer system is the set of all hardware, firmware, and/or software components that are critical to its security, in the sense that bugs or vulnerabilities occurring inside the TCB might jeopardize the security properties of the entire system. By contrast, parts of a computer system that lie outside the TCB must not be able to misbehave in a way that would leak any more privileges than are granted to them in accordance to the system's security policy.

Threat Intelligence Database A common database which contains the threats and vulnerabilities identified for a medical device by the ENTRUST framework, and can be accessed by other device manufacturers as threat intelligence knowledge towards increasing the security posture of devices operating within the medical domain.

Threat Modeling The Threat Modeling component is responsible for identifying known threats and vulnerabilities for a specific type of device based on existing threat intelligence databases, and aggregating them into an attack vector using an Large Language Model (LLM).

Trust Policy A smart contract deployed to the private ledger, which specifies the RTL of the device, as well as the types of trust evidence that needs to be collected in order to verify the correctness of the trust attributes of the device.

Bibliography

- [1] ISO/IEC TS 5723:2022 — iso.org. <https://www.iso.org/standard/81608.html>. [Accessed 26-07-2024].
- [2] OP-TEE Documentation & 2014; OP-TEE documentation documentation — optee.readthedocs.io. <https://optee.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>. [Accessed 09-07-2024].
- [3] Specifications Archive - GlobalPlatform — globalplatform.org. <https://globalplatform.org/specs-library/>. [Accessed 09-07-2024].
- [4] Mona Alkanhal, Mohamed Younis, Abdulaziz Alali, and Suhee Sanjana Mehjabin. Ferha: Fuzzy-extractor-based rf and hardware fingerprinting two-factor authentication. *Applied Sciences*, 14(8):3363, 2024.
- [5] Frederik Armknecht, Roel Maes, Ahmad-Reza Sadeghi, François-Xavier Standaert, and Christian Wachsmann. A formalization of the security features of physical functions. In *2011 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy*, pages 397–412. IEEE, 2011.
- [6] Sana Belguith, Nesrine Kaaniche, and Mohammad Hammoudeh. Analysis of attribute-based cryptographic techniques and their application to protect cloud services. *Transactions on emerging telecommunications technologies*, 33(3):e3667, 2022.
- [7] Jurjen NE Bos and David Chaum. Provably unforgeable signatures. In *Annual International Cryptology Conference*, pages 1–14. Springer, 1992.
- [8] Christoph Bösch, Jorge Guajardo, Ahmad-Reza Sadeghi, Jamshid Shokrollahi, and Pim Tuyls. Efficient helper data key extractor on fpgas. In *Cryptographic Hardware and Embedded Systems—CHES 2008: 10th International Workshop, Washington, DC, USA, August 10-13, 2008. Proceedings 10*, pages 181–197. Springer, 2008.
- [9] Jan Camenisch, Manu Drijvers, Anja Lehmann, Gregory Neven, and Patrick Towa. Short threshold dynamic group signatures. In Clemente Galdi and Vladimir Kolesnikov, editors, *Security and Cryptography for Networks - 12th International Conference, SCN 2020, Amalfi, Italy, September 14-16, 2020, Proceedings*, volume 12238 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 401–423. Springer, 2020.
- [10] Dan Cao, Xiaofeng Wang, Baokang Zhao, Jinshu Su, and Qiaolin Hu. Mediated attribute based signature scheme supporting key revocation. In *2012 8th international conference on information science and digital content technology (ICIDT2012)*, volume 2, pages 277–282. IEEE, 2012.
- [11] Liqun Chen, Ming-Feng Lee, and Bogdan Warinschi. Security of the enhanced TCG privacy-CA solution. In *Trustworthy Global Computing: 6th International Symposium, TGC 2011, Aachen, Germany, June 9-10, 2011. Revised Selected Papers 6*, pages 121–141. Springer, 2012.
- [12] Hui Cui, Robert H Deng, Joseph K Liu, Xun Yi, and Yingjiu Li. Server-aided attribute-based signature with revocation for resource-constrained industrial-internet-of-things devices. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, 14(8):3724–3732, 2018.
- [13] Hui Cui, Guilin Wang, Robert H Deng, and Baodong Qin. Escrow free attribute-based signature with self-revealability. *Information Sciences*, 367:660–672, 2016.

- [14] Jeroen Delvaux, Dawu Gu, Dries Schellekens, and Ingrid Verbauwhede. Helper data algorithms for puf-based key generation: Overview and analysis. *IEEE Transactions on Computer-Aided Design of Integrated Circuits and Systems*, 34(6):889–902, 2014.
- [15] Jeroen Delvaux, Dawu Gu, Ingrid Verbauwhede, Matthias Hiller, and Meng-Day Yu. Efficient fuzzy extraction of puf-induced secrets: Theory and applications. In *International Conference on Cryptographic Hardware and Embedded Systems*, pages 412–431. Springer, 2016.
- [16] Yevgeniy Dodis, Leonid Reyzin, and Adam Smith. Fuzzy extractors: How to generate strong keys from biometrics and other noisy data. In *Advances In Cryptology-EUROCRYPT 2004: International Conference On The Theory And Applications Of Cryptographic Techniques, Interlaken, Switzerland, May 2-6, 2004. Proceedings 23*, pages 523–540. Springer, 2004.
- [17] Ali El Kaafarani, Liqun Chen, Essam Ghadafi, and James Davenport. Attribute-based signatures with user-controlled linkability. In *Cryptology and Network Security: 13th International Conference, CANS 2014, Heraklion, Crete, Greece, October 22-24, 2014. Proceedings 13*, pages 256–269. Springer, 2014.
- [18] Ali El Kaafarani, Essam Ghadafi, and Dalia Khader. Decentralized traceable attribute-based signatures. In *Topics in Cryptology-CT-RSA 2014: The Cryptographer's Track at the RSA Conference 2014, San Francisco, CA, USA, February 25-28, 2014. Proceedings*, pages 327–348. Springer, 2014.
- [19] ENTRUST. Conceptual architecture of entrust customizable tc attestation models specifications. Deliverable D4.1, The ENTRUST Consortium, 5 2024.
- [20] ENTRUST. Entrust risk assessment collective threat intelligence framework – initial release. Deliverable D3.2, The ENTRUST Consortium, 7 2024.
- [21] Alex Escala, Javier Herranz, and Paz Morillo. Revocable attribute-based signatures with adaptive security in the standard model. In *Progress in Cryptology-AFRICACRYPT 2011: 4th International Conference on Cryptology in Africa, Dakar, Senegal, July 5-7, 2011. Proceedings 4*, pages 224–241. Springer, 2011.
- [22] Jesús García-Rodríguez, Stephan Krenn, Jorge Bernal Bernabe, and Antonio Skarmeta. Beyond selective disclosure: Extending distributed p-ABC implementations by commit-and-prove techniques. *Computer Networks*, 248:110498, June 2024.
- [23] Daniel Gardham and Mark Manulis. Revocable hierarchical attribute-based signatures from lattices. In *International Conference on Applied Cryptography and Network Security*, pages 459–479. Springer, 2022.
- [24] Daniel Lewis Gardham. *Hierarchical attribute-based signatures*. PhD thesis, University of Surrey, 2021.
- [25] A-J Ge, C-G Ma, and Z-F Zhang. Attribute-based signature scheme with constant size signature in the standard model. *IET Information Security*, 6(2):47–54, 2012.
- [26] Essam Ghadafi. Stronger security notions for decentralized traceable attribute-based signatures and more efficient constructions. In *Topics in Cryptology-CT-RSA 2015: The Cryptographer's Track at the RSA Conference 2015, San Francisco, CA, USA, April 20-24, 2015. Proceedings*, pages 391–409. Springer, 2015.
- [27] Ke Gu, Weijia Jia, Guojun Wang, and Sheng Wen. Efficient and secure attribute-based signature for monotone predicates. *Acta Informatica*, 54:521–541, 2017.
- [28] W Cary Huffman and Vera Pless. *Fundamentals of error-correcting codes*. Cambridge university press, 2010.
- [29] Andreas Hülsing. W-ots+—shorter signatures for hash-based signature schemes. In *Progress in Cryptology-AFRICACRYPT 2013: 6th International Conference on Cryptology in Africa, Cairo, Egypt, June 22-24, 2013. Proceedings 6*, pages 173–188. Springer, 2013.
- [30] Andreas Hülsing, Denis Butin, Stefan Gazdag, Joost Rijneveld, and Aziz Mohaisen. Xmss: extended merkle signature scheme. Technical report, 2018.

- [31] Yong Woon Hwang, Taehoon Kim, Daehee Seo, and Im-Yeong Lee. A study on the traceable attribute-based signature scheme provided with anonymous credentials. *Connection Science*, 36(1):2287979, 2024.
- [32] Hyunho Kang, Yohei Hori, Toshihiro Katashita, Manabu Hagiwara, and Keiichi Iwamura. Cryptographic key generation from puf data using efficient fuzzy extractors. In *16th International conference on advanced communication technology*, pages 23–26. IEEE, 2014.
- [33] Hyunho Kang, Yohei Hori, Toshihiro Katashita, Manabu Hagiwara, and Keiichi Iwamura. Performance analysis for puf data using fuzzy extractor. In *Ubiquitous Information Technologies and Applications: CUTE 2013*, pages 277–284. Springer, 2014.
- [34] Zhaozhe Kang, Jiguo Li, Jian Shen, Jinguang Han, Yuting Zuo, and Yichen Zhang. Tfs-abs: Traceable and forward-secure attribute-based signature scheme with constant-size. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, 2023.
- [35] Hugo Krawczyk. Lfsr-based hashing and authentication. In *Annual International Cryptology Conference*, pages 129–139. Springer, 1994.
- [36] Leslie Lamport. Constructing digital signatures from a one way function. 1979.
- [37] Yanling Lian, Li Xu, and Xinyi Huang. Attribute-based signatures with efficient revocation. In *2013 5th international conference on intelligent networking and collaborative systems*, pages 573–577. IEEE, 2013.
- [38] Wenchao Liu, Zhenhua Zhang, Miaoxin Li, and Zhenglin Liu. A trustworthy key generation prototype based on ddr3 puf for wireless sensor networks. *Sensors*, 14(7):11542–11556, 2014.
- [39] Zhen Liu, Zhenfu Cao, and Duncan S Wong. Efficient generation of linear secret sharing scheme matrices from threshold access trees. *Cryptology ePrint Archive*, 2010.
- [40] Roel Maes, Pim Tuyls, and Ingrid Verbauwhede. Low-overhead implementation of a soft decision helper data algorithm for sram pufs. In *Cryptographic Hardware and Embedded Systems-CHES 2009: 11th International Workshop Lausanne, Switzerland, September 6-9, 2009 Proceedings*, pages 332–347. Springer, 2009.
- [41] Roel Maes, Vincent Van Der Leest, Erik Van Der Sluis, and Frans Willems. Secure key generation from biased pufs. In *Cryptographic Hardware and Embedded Systems-CHES 2015: 17th International Workshop, Saint-Malo, France, September 13-16, 2015, Proceedings 17*, pages 517–534. Springer, 2015.
- [42] Hemanta K. Maji, Manoj Prabhakaran, and Mike Rosulek. Attribute-based signatures. In Aggelos Kiayias, editor, *Topics in Cryptology – CT-RSA 2011*, pages 376–392, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2011. Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- [43] Xian-ping Mao, Ke-fei Chen, Yu Long, and Liang-liang Wang. Attribute-based signature on lattices. *Journal of Shanghai Jiaotong University (Science)*, 19:406–411, 2014.
- [44] Ralph C Merkle. A digital signature based on a conventional encryption function. In *Conference on the theory and application of cryptographic techniques*, pages 369–378. Springer, 1987.
- [45] Robert Morelos-Zaragoza. Bch codes, 1996.
- [46] Robert H Morelos-Zaragoza. *The art of error correcting coding*. John Wiley & Sons, 2006.
- [47] Prince Silas Kwesi Oberko, Victor-Hillary Kofi Setornyo Obeng, Hu Xiong, and Saru Kumari. A survey on attribute-based signatures. *Journal of Systems Architecture*, 124:102396, 2022.
- [48] Tatsuaki Okamoto and Katsuyuki Takashima. Decentralized attribute-based signatures. In *Public-Key Cryptography-PKC 2013: 16th International Conference on Practice and Theory in Public-Key Cryptography, Nara, Japan, February 26–March 1, 2013. Proceedings 16*, pages 125–142. Springer, 2013.
- [49] Tatsuaki Okamoto and Katsuyuki Takashima. Efficient attribute-based signatures for non-monotone predicates in the standard model. *IEEE Transactions on Cloud Computing*, 2(4):409–421, 2014.

- [50] David Pointcheval and Olivier Sanders. Reassessing security of randomizable signatures. In *Proceedings of the RSA Conference on Topics in Cryptology - CT-RSA 2018 - Volume 10808*, page 319–338, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2018. Springer.
- [51] Michael O Rabin. Digitalized signatures. *Foundations of secure computation*, pages 155–168, 1978.
- [52] Doreen Riepel and Hoeteck Wee. FABEO: Fast attribute-based encryption with optimal security. In *Proceedings of the 2022 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security*, pages 2491–2504, 2022.
- [53] Yusuke Sakai, Nuttapon Attrapadung, and Goichiro Hanaoka. Attribute-based signatures for circuits from bilinear map. In *Public-Key Cryptography—PKC 2016: 19th IACR International Conference on Practice and Theory in Public-Key Cryptography, Taipei, Taiwan, March 6-9, 2016, Proceedings, Part I*, pages 283–300. Springer, 2016.
- [54] Raphael Schermann, Rainer Urian, Ronald Toegl, Holger Bock, and Christian Steger. Enabling anonymous authenticated encryption with a novel anonymous authenticated credential key agreement (AACKA). In *2022 IEEE International Conference on Trust, Security and Privacy in Computing and Communications (TrustCom)*, pages 646–655. IEEE, 2022.
- [55] Bernard Sklar. *Digital communications: fundamentals and applications*. Pearson, 2021.
- [56] Vikas Srivastava, Anubhab Baksi, and Sumit Kumar Debnath. An overview of hash based signatures. *Cryptology ePrint Archive*, 2023.
- [57] Qianqian Su, Rui Zhang, Rui Xue, and Pengchao Li. Revocable attribute-based signature for blockchain-based healthcare system. *IEEE Access*, 8:127884–127896, 2020.
- [58] Stephen R Tate and Roopa Vishwanathan. Expiration and revocation of keys for attribute-based signatures. In *IFIP Annual Conference on Data and Applications Security and Privacy*, pages 153–169. Springer, 2015.
- [59] tsbmail. Y.3057&xFFFD;:&xFFFD;A trust index model for information and communication technology infrastructures and services — itu.int. <https://www.itu.int/rec/T-REC-Y.3057-202112-P>. [Accessed 26-07-2024].
- [60] Vincent Van der Leest, Bart Preneel, and Erik Van der Sluis. Soft decision error correction for compact memory-based pufs using a single enrollment. In *International Workshop on Cryptographic Hardware and Embedded Systems*, pages 268–282. Springer, 2012.
- [61] Qingbin Wang and Shaozhen Chen. Attribute-based signature for threshold predicates from lattices. *Security and Communication Networks*, 8(5):811–821, 2015.
- [62] Qingbin Wang, Shaozhen Chen, and Aijun Ge. A new lattice-based threshold attribute-based signature scheme. In *Information Security Practice and Experience: 11th International Conference, ISPEC 2015, Beijing, China, May 5-8, 2015, Proceedings*, pages 406–420. Springer, 2015.
- [63] Yuejiang Wen and Yingjie Lao. Efficient fuzzy extractor implementations for puf based authentication. In *2017 12th International Conference on Malicious and Unwanted Software (MALWARE)*, pages 119–125. IEEE, 2017.
- [64] Hu Xiong, Yangyang Bao, Xuyun Nie, and Yakubu Issifu Asoor. Server-aided attribute-based signature supporting expressive access structures for industrial internet of things. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, 16(2):1013–1023, 2019.
- [65] Meng-Day Yu, Richard Sowell, Alok Singh, David M’Raïhi, and Srinivas Devadas. Performance metrics and empirical results of a puf cryptographic key generation ASIC. In *2012 IEEE International Symposium on Hardware-Oriented Security and Trust*, pages 108–115. IEEE, 2012.

- [66] Tsz Hon Yuen, Joseph K Liu, Xinyi Huang, Man Ho Au, Willy Susilo, and Jianying Zhou. Forward secure attribute-based signatures. In *Information and Communications Security: 14th International Conference, ICICS 2012, Hong Kong, China, October 29-31, 2012. Proceedings 14*, pages 167–177. Springer, 2012.
- [67] Fahem Zerrouki, Samir Ouchani, and Hafida Bouarfa. A generation and recovery framework for silicon pufs based cryptographic key. In *Advances in Model and Data Engineering in the Digitalization Era: MEDI 2021 International Workshops: DETECT, SIAS, CSMML, BIOC, HEDA, Tallinn, Estonia, June 21–23, 2021, Proceedings 10*, pages 121–137. Springer, 2021.

